

**IDENTIFICATION OF DROUGHT TOLERANT GENOTYPE
THROUGH MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR
SCREENING IN BARLEY (*Hordeum vulgare* L.)**

A THESIS

BY

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STUDENT NO. 1601107

SEMESTER: July-December, 2022

SESSION: 2021-22

**MASTER OF SCIENCE (MS)
IN
GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING**

**DEPARTMENT OF GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING
HAJEE MOHAMMAD DANESH SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
DINAJPUR-5200
DECEMBER, 2022**

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Certification

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**IDENTIFICATION OF DROUGHT TOLERANT GENOTYPE THROUGH MORPHO-PHYSIOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR SCREENING IN BARLEY (*Hordeum vulgare L.*)**” is a study, prepared by the examinee, bearing Registration No.: 1601107 of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur. The authoress has submitted this thesis to the Department as a partial fulfillment for the requirements of the degree “Master of Science in Genetics and Plant Breeding”, is a record of original research work carried out by her under my supervision. The work is an original, unique one and to the best of my knowledge, no part of the thesis has been produced elsewhere for any other degree or diploma.

.....

(Professor Dr. Md. Arifuzzaman)
Supervisor

In the Name of God

&

*My Beloved Parents and
Honourable Teachers*

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ABSTRACT

Drought causes enormous yield losses in barley. The experiment was conducted to find drought tolerant genotypes from 123 diverse European barley genotypes (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) at the Experimental Farm and in the laboratory of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University (HSTU), Dinajpur, Bangladesh during Rabi season, 2021-22 following strip plot design with two treatments viz. control and rainfed drought and with two replications. The analysis of variance showed that all morpho-physiological variables analyzed in both control and drought-stressed environments showed a wide range of genotype variation. The genotypic coefficient of variation was lower than the phenotypic coefficient of variance. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance as a percent of the mean was observed on the number of grains per spike and yield per plant (168.41% and 186.98%, respectively). Maximum values for yield per plant were revealed for the genotype EEB450 (35.22g) followed by EEB401 (35.11g), and EEB336 (31.05g) in the control condition and EEB114 (27.78g) followed EEB318 (24.95g) for drought-stressed condition. A significant positive correlation between yield per plant and row type, and the number of grain per spike was observed in both control and drought conditions. The EEB81, EEB382, EEB90, EEB83, EEB116, EEB418, EEB298, EEB265, EEB318, EEB114, EEB204, EEB152, EEB433, EEB166, EEB129, EEB254, EEB346 were identified as highly drought tolerant cultivars based upon drought susceptible index (DSI). A total ten simple sequence markers viz. BMAC0577, BMAG808, WMS6, EBMAC624, Bmag125, Bmag006, Scssr25691, Bmac0113, GMS027, Bmag337 were evaluated in 39 barley cultivars for molecular characterization. All of the SSRs were polymorphic across the 39 genotypes. A total of 31 alleles were detected and the number of alleles per marker ranged from 2 to 4 with an average of 3.1 alleles per locus. The most polymorphic microsatellite markers were BMAG808, EBMAC624 and Bmag006 detecting 4 alleles, followed by Scssr25691, Bmac0113, GMS027, Bmag337 and BMAC0577 with 3 alleles. The highest PIC value (0.7) was recorded for BMAG808 and GMS027, Bmag337 and Bmac0113 both recorded second highest (0.65) and lowest by WMS6 (0.42). In population genetic structure analysis, population I consisted 19 genotypes, Population II comprised of total 15 genotypes, and Population III comprised of total 5 genotypes. The results obtained from the above two experiments suggest that the genotypes EEB 450, EEB 336, and EEB 129 should be considered as potential source of genetic materials and must be taken distinctly further drought stress breeding programs in barley.

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SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATION

AEZ	:	Agro Ecological Zone
ANOVA	:	Analysis of Variance
BBS	:	Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics
cm	:	Centimeter
CRD	:	Completely Block Design
CV	:	Coefficient of Variation
DAS	:	Days After Sowing
DAP	:	Di-Ammonium Phosphate
d.f.	:	Degree of Freedom
e.g.	:	For Example
etc.	:	And the rest
<i>et al.</i>	:	And others people
EEB	:	Eastern European Barley
FAOSTAT	:	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FAO	:	Food and Agriculture Organization
g	:	Gram
GA	:	Genetic Advance
GAM	:	Genetic Advance Over Mean
GCV	:	Genotypic Coefficient of Variation
PCV	:	Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation
GE	:	Genotype by Environment interaction
GGE	:	Genotype and Genotype by Environment interaction
i.e.	:	That is
K	:	Potassium
kg	:	Kilogram
MoP	:	Muriate of potash
MS	:	Mean Sum of Square
MSe	:	Error Mean Square
MSg	:	Genotype Mean square
N	:	Nitrogen
OM	:	Organic Matter
P	:	Phosphorus

PAB	:	Pure and Applied Biology
PBI	:	Plant Breeding Institute
PCA	:	Principal Component Analysis
p ^H	:	Potential for Hydrogen
ppm	:	Parts Per Million
RBD	:	Randomized Block Design
RCBD	:	Randomized Complete Block Design
rg	:	Genotypic correlation
RSS	:	Residual sum of squares
S	:	Sulphur
SE	:	Standard Error
SPAD	:	Soil Plant Analyses Development
SNP	:	Single-nucleotide polymorphism
Std. dev.	:	Standard deviation
STAR	:	Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research
USDA	:	United States Department of Agriculture
Zn	:	Zinc
°C	:	Degree Celsius

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Barley (*Hordeum* spp.) is a self-pollinating diploid species ($2n=2x=14$) with a genome size of 4.79 billion letters of genetic code, which is approximately twice as large as the genome of a human being (Mascher *et al.*, 2017). It is a member of the Poaceae family and comes in three different types: 2-row type barley (*H. disticum*), 4-row type barley (*H. vulgare*), and 6-row type barley (*H. hexastichum*). Barley is one of the main important cereal crops cultivated worldwide in a wide range of environments from temperate to sub-tropical, arid to semi-arid (Kaur *et al.*, 2022). Ranking fourth in world cereal production after maize, rice, and wheat, it is mainly used for feed (55–60%), brewing malts (30–40%), and the remaining percent for food purposes (Ullrich, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2014). In terms of utilization, barley is largely consumed as a staple food and used for preparing the popular traditional drink (Araya *et al.* 2021).

Barley is one of the world's oldest cereal crops, is rich in a variety of bioactive phytochemicals with potentially health-promoting effects (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). The major components of barley kernels consist of approximately 70% starch, 10-20% protein, 5-10% β -glucan, 2-3% free lipids, and 1-2.5% minerals (w/w) (Sullivan *et al.*, 2013; Zhang *et al.*, 2016) The consumption of whole-grain barley, barley β -glucan, and barley extracts has been linked to a decreased risk for several chronic diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, metabolic syndrome, and some forms of cancer for many years (Cavallero *et al.*, 2002; Casiraghi *et al.*, 2006; Choi *et al.*, 2010). It is a source of three life essential components: carbohydrates (74%), proteins (11.5%) and fiber (3.9%) along with fats (1.3%) and minerals (1.5%). Barley is mainly used for animal and poultry feeding, also for malt and some uses in the pharmaceutical industry (Biel and Jacyno, 2013). Barley also contains eight essential amino acids (Vasan *et al.*, 2014).

In Bangladesh, barley is cultivated on 453.10 acres of land where the total production is 172.42 MT (BBS, 2021-22). It ranks twelfth in terms of top agricultural commodities worldwide and fourth for the most produced cereal crop after maize (FAOSTAT, 2022). The global production volume of barley amounted to about 147.05 MT in the 2021/2022 crop year (Statista 2023). The global production of barley is anticipated to reach 149.47 MT in the year 2022 (USDA, 2023).

Barley is a fast growing, cool season, annual grain crop, that could be used as forage as well as, cover crop to improve soil fertility (Ghanbari *et al.*, 2012). Winter is the growing season

for barley. Additionally, it can be grown in both the winter and spring. Most spring barley in the world is grown in farms. Spring barley is planted in Bangladesh during the second rabi season. There was a dearth of barley types that had been developed for low-moisture stress. Farmers are thus compelled to cultivate genotypes with low yields.

Drought is one of the most limiting factors especially in warm dry areas yielding crops (Qadir, 2018) that affects the growth and development of plants under water deficit conditions. Recently Bangladesh has been experienced a consequence of high climate variability (Prodhan *et al.*, 2020). North western region, namely, the Barind tract, is one of the largest drought-affected areas of Bangladesh (Islam *et al.*, 2019). It is one of the most common abiotic stresses that affects growth and development of plants (Pour-Siahbidi *et al.*, 2013). Loss of yield is the main concern of plant breeders, and hence emphasizes on yield performance under stress conditions (Naghavi *et al.*, 2013). It affects morphological, physiological, biochemical and molecular processes in plants resulting in growth inhibition. The extent of these changes is dependent on the time, stage and severity of environmental stress (Cao *et al.*, 2011).

The most devastating environmental constraint is drought that causing much more yield loss than any other abiotic stress (Farooq *et al.*, 2009; Kadam *et al.*, 2014). It occurs virtually in all climatic regions, and the drought-prone areas accounted for 16.2–41.2% of arable land worldwide (Wang *et al.*, 2014; Kebede *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, it has been predicted that the drought frequency and severity will increase in presently dry regions due to climate change (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014). It affects almost all stages of growth and development during plant life cycle, particularly dramatic decline in photosynthesis, floral abnormalities, spikelet/kernel sterility, grain yield and quality losses (Kadam *et al.*, 2014). Meanwhile, world population is expected to increase from 7.7 billion currently to 9.7 billion in 2050 (United Nations: Department of Economic and Social Affairs - Population Division, 2019), which will seriously bring challenge the global food security. To overcome the increasing requirement of agricultural production in the future climate scenarios, the most effective and economic approach is to breed cultivars with high drought tolerance. However, due to limited availability of resistance sources, very little progress in breeding drought-tolerant crops has been made.

Studying genetic variability in crops is important for improving the crops and enhancing the production. Genetic variability is the occurrence of differences among varieties due to differences in their genetic composition and/or the environment in which they are raised

(Tehulie, 2022). Heritability is a measure of the value of selection for particular characters and an index of their transmissibility. It plays a predictive role in breeding, expressing the reliability of phenotype as a guide to its breeding value. The expected response to selection is also called genetic advance (GA). High genetic advance coupled with high heritability estimates the most effective condition for selection. Genetic improvement of crop is largely depending on the scale of genetic variability and the degree to which desired traits are inherited (Dinsa *et al.*, 2018).

Plant breeders explore genetic variations and select different tolerant genotypes under environmental stress conditions (Haddadin, 2015). Drought-tolerant genotypes of barley are selected through agronomic traits such as grain yield and its related parameters (Hossain *et al.*, 2012; Niazi-Fard *et al.*, 2012). Plants of drought-tolerant genotypes that show optimum performance and productivity have been tested in drought and normal irrigation conditions (Niazi-Fard *et al.*, 2012; Haddadin, 2015). It can be recommended to be used when planning on the availability of parents in breeding programs for drought tolerance (Khokhar *et al.*, 2012; Haddadin, 2015). Therefore, yield and its components can be analyzed comparatively under stressed and unstressed conditions, thereby predicting which genotypes are more tolerant to different types of stress (Plaut, 2003).

Genetic diversity is an important factor in any successful hybridization program. It is the process that analyzes the variation among genotypes by a specific method or a combination of methods. Thus, the presence of genetic diversity and the relationship among various yield and yield-related traits and their heritability is essential in identifying possible genotypes for forthcoming crop variety (Dinsa *et al.*, 2018).

Multivariate analysis technique in studying the divergence between genotypes and the degree of association between the traits has become increasingly important. Hence different authors reported the application of cluster and principal component analysis in barley (Derbew, 2020; Dido *et al.*, 2020). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a tool to identify the similarities and dissimilarities pattern in the data. It is an effective tool in identifying the prototype of high dimension data where we cannot have luxury of graphical presentation. It facilitate in reducing the dimensions of the data after identifying the pattern without much loss of information. PCA have many alternative uses among which assigning the weights while computing an index is one. It is based on the development of eigen values and mutually independent eigen vectors (principal components) ranked in descending order of variance size or declining information content (Jalata *et al.*, 2020).

Plant susceptibility to stress is determined by the genetic factors encoding morphological and physiological (Sallam *et al.*, 2019). Understanding the role of physiological and agronomic attributes during drought recovery in determining barley's variable drought stress tolerance (Ferioun *et al.*, 2023; Hasanuzzaman *et al.*, 2022).

Breeders have traditionally attempted to figure out genetic connection with potential of variety (Meszaros *et al.*, 2007), since these factors are crucial to breeding, genetic resource exploitation, and conservation. Morphological markers may employ to assess genetic diversity and a viable substitute for morphological criteria since DNA markers are environmental-independent (Pirseyyedi *et al.*, 2006). Simple sequence repeats (SSRs) markers based on the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) have high polymorphism, co-dominant inheritance, highly reproducibility, locus specificity, and random genome distribution (Russell *et al.*, 1997), thus suitable markers are effective for assessing genetic diversity, genetic relationship, and phylogenetic development. Using SSRs technique as powerful tool for genetic studies in barley breeding for drought (water) stress have been frequently confirmed in several investigations (Fantahun *et al.*, 2023; Jabbari *et al.*, 2022; Mariey *et al.*, 2022; Lakew *et al.*, 2012; Vahideh *et al.*, 2015; Hellal *et al.*, 2018 and Heiba *et al.*, 2019), identified potential markers in selection in barley drought tolerant breeding programs. So, the research hypothesis might be the identification of potential drought tolerance genotypes through genetic analysis in a diverse collections of barley applying morpho-physiological and molecular approaches.

Therefore, the present study should be conducted under the following specific objectives.

1. To screen the 123 European barley genotypes based on morpho-physiological traits under control and drought stress conditions.
2. To study the genetic variability, correlation, and regression analysis for 13 morpho-physiological traits under control and drought stress conditions.
3. To identify the drought-tolerant and susceptible genotypes through the drought tolerance selection indices.
4. To study population structure in barley using SSR molecular markers.
5. To identify drought tolerant and susceptible diverse parents through phenotypic and molecular diversity analysis

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Barley is an important cereal crop throughout the world. It is eaten in various forms by more than thousand million human beings in the world. Its straw is used as the feed for large population of cattle. It is the fourth staple food crop following rice, wheat and maize. It contains about 8-15% protein and is specially important for bakery, making baby food and bread making. For this, the present study has aimed about the variability, heritability, correlation analysis, genetic diversity and principal component and using SSR marker to study population structure, molecular genetic diversity in a larger collection of barley germplasm. The chapter contains the review of literature related to the work on effect of drought stress in barley genotypes. The work carried out by various scientists on drought tolerance has been reviewed.

2.1. Mean comparisons of different morpho-physiological traits studied in barley:

Fekadu *et al.* (2022) examined that thirty barley genotypes were tested in nine environments in a randomised full block design with three replications to determine genotype-by-environment interaction and stability and adaptation of high-yielding genotypes. Environment (54.61%), genotype (10.69%), and $G \times E$ interaction (34.70%) explained the variances. IPCA1 (45.48%), IPCA2 (24.65%), and IPCA3 (13.02%) explained 70.13% of the $G \times E$ interaction sum of squares. The current investigation suggested 3514-A, 24,990, and 17,148 for breeding line identification and variety development.

Angassa and Mohammed (2022) studied that in 2019, southern Ethiopia examined 64 landrace barley accession and 3 released varieties for eight quantitative features. Each block had three standard tests in an enhanced block design experiment. Except for days to 75% maturity and plant height. Grain yield is 20.72–57.33 quintals ha⁻¹. Chefo produced the most grain (released variety). However, 43 of the farmer's varieties had grain yields higher than the two enhanced types. The study revealed farmers' variety accessions' hidden yield-boosting potential by using conserved germplasm.

Elbasyoni *et al.* (2022) studied that 426 barley lines under deficiency (DI) and full irrigation (FI) in 2019 and 2020. NDF, CH, CAN, GFD, PH, and Yield were measured under DI and FI. 24 significant indicators were barley genes. Most of these genes affected plant drought

responses. Nine important indicators were previously reported, whereas 27 were novel. This study identified markers that could predict DI and FI-optimal barley accessions.

Usubaliev *et al.* (2020) studied about five agronomic traits of 29 barley accessions that were evaluated in different agro-environmental conditions. Accessions represented cultivars from Kyrgyzstan, Ukraine, and the Nordic and Baltic countries as well as landraces from northeastern and eastern Russia. The field experiments were carried out in two countries (Latvia and Kyrgyzstan) in order to select the suitable genotypes or cultivars as a source for Kyrgyz barley breeding programs. Among the accessions studied, we found material that can be used in Kyrgyz breeding as potential sources of earliness, spike length and TKW. Among the cultivars, „Cecilia“ from Sweden showed an attractive agronomic performance, and had constant behaviour under Kyrgyz climatic conditions during two years of trials. Other cultivars like “Saana”, “Sencis” and “Mette” can also be included in future breeding due to their earliness, plant height, spike length and number of kernels.

Rodrigues *et al.* (2020) conducted a breeding process focused on selection for grain yield, disease resistance and malting quality. The objective of this work was to quantify the genetic gain in barley grain yield from 1968 and 2008 in Brazil and to identify the physiological characteristics associated with the increase of grain yield. Field experiments with five 2-row barley cultivars were tested from 2011 to 2013 in the absence of biotic and abiotic stresses and with mechanical restriction to lodging. The ANOVA showed no genetic gain until 1980 with average grain yield of 4.632 kg/ha. After 1980, there was a productivity increase of 59.9 kg/ha/year. The main component associated with grain yield was the number of grains, due to the higher number of spikes associated to a greater contribution of the tillers in the modern cultivars.

Yadav *et al.* (2019) evaluated forty-nine exotic and indigenous genotypes along with four check varieties of barley for yield and its contributing traits. Analysis of variance revealed significant differences among the genotypes for all the traits viz. days to 50% flowering, days to maturity, plant height (cm), flag leaf area (cm²), peduncle length (cm), ear length (cm), productive tillers/ plant, 1000 seed weight (g), biological yield/ plant, grain yield/ plant and harvest index (%) and exhibited high amount of variability among all the genotypes. The mean plant height was 73.21 cm with a range of 51.85-89.85 cm. They observed mean grain yield/ plant 10.03 g with a range of 7.74-11.54 g.

Sayd *et al.* (2019) carried out a study with 69 barley genotypes from 2012 to 2014, under irrigation in the Cerrado. Six agronomic characteristics were assessed: grain yield, plumpness kernel, thousand seeds weight, plant height, degree of plant lodging and days to heading. Analysis of variance was performed and significant effects were observed for genotypes, years and the G x E interaction. The Colombian accession MCU363PI402112 8 stood out for its agronomic characteristics. Genotype selection based on the phenotypic evaluations was possible due to their good experimental accuracy and precision. Precocious genotypes with high grain yields and homogeneous grain sizes were selected. Due to the environmental influence on the grain yield, additional studies concerning the components of yield in this environment are necessary to facilitate the selection of more productive genotypes.

Hagenblad *et al.* (2019) conducted an experiment with morphologically and genetically characterized 57 landraces collected during the twenty first century and conserved in gene banks. The majority of accessions were of the six-row type. Accessions from the easternmost islands were genetically distinct from those from the central and western islands. Accessions from the western islands often had a mixed genetically composition, suggesting more recent exchange of plant material with the central islands.

Hajiagha *et al.* (2019) evaluated both morphological and physiological traits followed by classification of 18 barley inbred lines based on RCBD design with four replications. Results of descriptive statistics revealed vast range of variation for most of studied traits. Among the studied traits, seed yield with standard deviation of 614.06 possessed maximum divergent, hectoliter weight and grain yield had the lowest and the highest coefficients of variation values of 0.58 and 8.88, respectively. Univariate analysis of variance depicted remarkable genetic variation among studied genotypes based on morphological and physiological traits. They postulated that line number 3 with high peduncle length (7.18 cm), 1000 kernel weight (42.2 gr), yield (5172.5 kgh-1), dry matter percentage (31.3 %), fresh weight (0.463 gr) and also another moderate characteristics could considerable as promising one for arid and semi-arid region after regional field trials.

Al-Sayaydeh *et al.* (2019) worked with the agronomic performance of 10 Jordanian barley landraces and three local cultivars were evaluated in two locations for two growing seasons. Clear significant variations for all studied traits were observed among the selected genotypes, environments, and their interactions, local cultivar Rum and Baladi landrace showed the best yield performance, while Herawi and Nabawi landraces produced the lowest yield across all environments.

2.2. Variability, Genetic Advance and Heritability analysis:

Verma *et al.* (2022) studied that two hundred ten barley germplasm lines (144 exotic and 66 indigenous) and six standard check varieties (HBL 113 (Vimal), HBL 713 (Him Palam Jau 1), HBL 804 (Him Palam Jau 2), BHS 400 (Pusa Sheetal), BHS 352 (Himadri), and VLB 118 (VLJau 118)) were evaluated for yield and yield-related traits. This group of experimental barley genotypes showed strong PCV and GCV (>20%) for grain yield/plant, number of effective tillers/plant, biological yield/plant, and number of grains/spike, showing high selection response. For barley grain yield improvement, number of grains/spike, biological yield/plant, and grain yield/plant had strong heritability and genetic progress as a percent of mean.

Gupta *et al.* (2022) examined that 28 F1 s were developed by crossing 8 commercial varieties, germplasm, or local lines as per diallel mating design (excluding reciprocals) and laid out in randomised block design with parents and three replications during rabi 2019-20 to study genetic variability parameters, correlation, and path analysis. All characters had enough genetic variety. Variability estimates showed substantial phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation for biological and seed yield per plant. 1000 grain weight had excellent heritability and genetic progress, indicating additive gene action and good selection potential. Seed yield per plant was positively correlated with biological yield, spike length, tillers per plant, grains per spike, 1000 grain weight, plant height, days to maturity, and harvest index. Path analysis showed that factors including biological yield per plant, harvest index, 1000 grain weight, number of grains per spike, and peduncle length affected barley seed yield and could be selected to improve it. Biological yield per plant and harvest index were useful selection factors that may be used in barley breeding programmes to boost seed production.

Avanish and Singh (2021) examined that barley yield and contributing characters were analysed for genetic variability, heritability, correlation coefficient, and path analysis. Seed yield, biological yield, number of tillers, harvest index, number of seeds per spike, 100-seed weight, ear length, and plant height had higher genotypic and phenotypic coefficients. All characters had strong heritability and genetic progress. Biological yield per plant, harvest index, number of tillers per plant, number of grains per spike, and 100-seed weight are the most important yield contributing features.

Dyulgerov & Dyulgerova (2020) showed that twenty barley types were arranged in a complete block design with four replications. Studying grain yield variability, heredity, and genetic advance. All attributes, including grain yield, differed between kinds. Grain yield had 10.10% heritability and spike length 94.60%. Spike length and 1000-grain weight had high heritability and genetic progress as percent of mean. These features also showed minimal genotypic and phenotypic variances. Selection might easily increase these features. Veslets yielded 5.27 t/ha and Izgrev 5.09 t/ha. PA86-49-95 (6.43 t/ha), Bojin (6.01), and Express (5.90) outperformed the checks in grain yield. Thus, breeding winter feed barley with these cultivars may increase grain production.

Dido *et al.* (2020) evaluated that the genetic variability, direct and indirect effects of some metric characters on grain yield of 585 barley landraces and 10 cultivars under augmented complete block design, the current study was carried out in 2018 and 2019 at Sinana Agricultural Research Center (on-station) and Goba (on-farm), South-east Ethiopia. The mean, range, components of variation, broad sense heritability, genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), and genetic progress were evaluated for yield and yield linked characters using the data on twelve quantitative characters. The studied barley accessions showed significant variance for all features, according to the results. Plant height, number of viable tillers per plant, spike length, number of seeds per spike, and weight of 1000 seeds showed strong heritability whereas grain yield per plant showed moderately high heredity along with high genetic progress. The development of high yielding barley varieties in the future crop improvement programme can be based on those quantitative characteristics that have a significant and favourable direct effect on grain yield/plant.

Shiferaw *et al.* (2020) assessed the genetic variability and to assess the associations among morpho-agronomic characters, three hundred and twenty Ethiopian barley genotypes were evaluated in 2017 main-season at Holetta Agricultural Research Centre using 20 × 16 Alpha Lattice design. The analysis of variance showed that there were significant differences among the genotypes in all traits except for days to emergence, indicating the presence of genotypic variation among the studied genotypes. Grain yield, biomass yield and kernels per spike had high phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of 12 variation. The estimates of broad sense heritability and genetic advance were high for days to heading and maturity and thousand kernels weight. Therefore, there is a high possibility of developing new varieties from these genotypes.

Matin *et al.* (2019) was carried out a study to investigate the correlation coefficient, path analysis and genetic variability among some barley varieties for nine characters in a Randomize Block Design (RBD) with three replications in three environments of Bangladesh. High genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) was obtained from grain/ spike (29.89 %), yield/ plant (28.72%) and effective tiller/plant (21.86 %) and spike length (13.56 %). The characters with high GCV indicated high potential for selection. The highest heritability (Hb) was observed for 1000 seed weight (95.09) followed by yield/ plant (93.98), grain/ spike (92.09) and spike length (69.93), days to heading (72.65) but the lowest Hb was identified for effective tiller/plant (22.41) followed by the plant height (34.21). Those traits with higher heritability may be considered for selection. Grain/ spike had the highest positive direct effect (5.65) on yield followed by 1000 seed weight (4.65), spike length (1.26), yield/ plant (0.66), days to heading (0.55) and days to maturity (0.34). These parameters were identified as direct selection. Direct negative effect on yield was shown by plant height (-0.32) and effective tiller/plant (-0.74). This was an indication of indirect selection.

Ali *et al.* (2019) showed the heritability estimation of the grain yield per plant was moderate heritability estimate (0.50). This indicated that this trait can be improved under investigated environments. We identified some promising stable DHs lines that might be used in barley breeding programs in Egypt. Some of these DHs performed better than both parents and the local check cultivar.

2.3. Correlation and regression analysis

Fantahun *et al.* (2023) examined that a panel of 320 barley genotypes was tested for phenotypic variability to identify candidate lines for improvement programmes and use. Six-rowed lines performed best across all conditions based on spike row number. The two-rowed spike type-predominate at Arsi Negelle and the six-rowed form at Holetta, according to two years of data. Grain and biomass yield had a low but significant connection ($r = 0.38^{***}$). 1000 kernel weight correlated negatively with spike seed count (-0.72^{***}). According to current studies, biomass and grain yield are positively correlated, attracting farmers as feed and food crops. Combining farmers' varieties with the improved barley gene pool, which is mostly from overseas sources, may narrow the disparity.

Firoozabadi *et al.* (2022) studied that 20 barley genotypes (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) were evaluated during two cropping seasons 2016–2017 and 2017–2018 under terminal drought stress conditions (irrigation cut at 50% heading) using a randomised complete block design

with three replications to investigate morpho-physiological traits and their relationship with grain yield in barley and determine the best selection criteria under terminal drought stress. The experiment measured days to heading, days to maturity, number of fertile tillers, plant height, peduncle length, weight, spike length, number of grains per spike, 1000-kernel weight, remobilization, remobilization efficiency, biological yield, harvest index, and grain yield. Remobilization, harvest index, biological yield, and peduncle weight affected grain yield most under drought stress, according to correlation, regression, and path analysis. These features can be employed in barley breeding to boost grain yield under terminal drought stress. Under stress, genotypes 4, 11, and 16 with the highest remobilization, harvest index, biological yield, and peduncle weight yielded more grain.

Matsuoka *et al.* (2022) examined that 594 persons without diabetes, hypertension, or dyslipidemia were chosen from 236 Japanese participants. We examined faeces, physical exams, and diet questionnaires. Median barley consumption grouped subjects. We then ranked 50 genera by abundance. Multiple regression analysis, adjusted for disease and diet, examined the link between barley consumption and characteristic microorganisms in all subjects. We examined 20 selected genera' networks and clustering. Bifidobacterium, Butyricoccus, Collinsella, Ruminococcus 2, and Dialister were distinctive candidate bacteria of the barley-consuming group ($P < 0.05$). After controlling for disease and diet, barley consumption and Bifidobacterium and Butyricoccus persisted. Barley consumption was also linked to Bifidobacterium and Butyricoccus by network and cluster analyses.

Wang *et al.* (2022) examined compared texture analyzer results to farinograph and extensograph to see if texture analyzer could assess highland barley flour (HBF) dough sheet processing quality. The farinograph, extensograph, texture analyzer, glutenin macropolymer (GMP), free sulfhydryl (-SH), secondary protein structure, and microstructure of HBF dough sheet were examined. Regression and Pearson correlation coefficients determined correlations between these parameters. Better gluten index reconstituted flours had higher farinograph quality numbers (FQN) and higher maximal resistance to extension (R_m). Higher gluten index HBF dough sheets had more GMP and less free -SH, a better organised protein secondary structure, a more compact gluten network, and a stronger TS. TS linked positively with FQN and R_m . GMP, SH, protein secondary structure, and gluten network were also substantially associated. Texture analyzer might assess HBF dough sheet processing quality. Flour gluten index can also indicate HBF dough sheet processing quality.

Zarei *et al.* (2021) revealed that due to water resource strain, especially in agriculture, field water management must evaluate efficient water consumption reduction measures. This study studied and prioritised the efficiency of 7 climatic elements on barley's water demand (PETB during growth) utilising the random forest method (RF), Bayesian multiple linear regression (BR), and cross-correlation function (CCF). This research can help PETB management control effective climate variables. This article uses the 1968–2017 climatic data series of 8 sites in Iran with two replicates for each climate condition. The linear regression of simulated PETB using AquaCrop model and predicted PETB using the RF and BR models had no difference with perfect reliable in 0.05 significant levels (T-Statistics varies from 0.010–0.103 and 0.000–0.842 in BR and RF models, respectively), and the R-square (R²) between simulated and predicted PETB were significant in 0.01 levels at all stations (R² varies from 0.843–0.996 and 0.930–0.999 in BR and RF models, respectively). The results showed that the wind speed had the greatest impact on the PETB (at 62.5% of stations) and that the RF, BR, and CCF approaches had the lowest impact.

Ramazani and Abdipour (2019) revealed that 10 cultivars were tested in three field tests in randomised block design with three replicates throughout the 2013–2014 growing season to discover the most critical factors affecting barley grain production. Each experiment assessed 10 yield component qualities. After a combined analysis of variance, simple correlation coefficients, factor analysis, stepwise analysis, route analysis, and cluster analysis were performed on combined means. Grain yield was positively correlated with grain filling period, biological yield, harvest index, seed/spike, seed/m², 1000-seed weight, and spikes/m². Factor analysis grouped 11 variables into five factors. Grain yield and filling affected factor 1. Spikes/m² and seeds impacted factor 2. Factor 3 affected hardening and maturity. Seed/spike, spikes/m², and 1000-seed weight affected Factor 4. Biological yield and plant height substantially influenced fifth factor. Stepwise regression analysis for grain yield as independent variable included biological yield and harvest index in four phases with R-square = 0.98. Both variables' regression coefficients were positive and significant at 1%. Biological yield has the greatest beneficial direct effect on grain yield, according to path coefficient analysis. Harvest index through biological yield had the greatest beneficial indirect effect on grain yield.

Taherian *et al.* (2017) examined that in 2012–2013, the Agricultural and Natural Research Station of Neishabour, Iran, planted 16 hardly cultivars and promising lines in a randomised full block design with three replications in optimum, salinity stress, and end-of-season

drought stress settings. Abiotic tolerance index (ATI), stress susceptibility percentage index (SSPI), relative drought index (RDI), drought response index (DRI), drought resistance index (DI), yield stability index (YSI), yield index (YI), tolerance (TOL), stress susceptibility index (SSI), stress tolerance index (STI), harmonic mean (HM), geometric mean productivity (GMP), and mean productivity (MP) were calculated from grain yield under non-stress. The present study found that only STI could distinguish high-yield cultivars under salt stress and non-stress. When stress was moderate, MP, YI, GMP, STI, and DI identified tolerant genotypes better (drought stress). Stress type and severity affected genotype ranking. Breeders should select selection indices based on target environment stress.

2.4. Diversity (cluster) analysis

Angassa *et al.* (2022) examined that 64 landrace barley accession and 3 released variety for eight quantitative attributes in 2019. The experiment used augmented block design with three standard tests per block. Principal component analysis yielded two principal components (PC1 and PC2) with eigenvalues from 1.74 to 4.30 and variability of 21.80% and 53.77%. Two genotype clusters (I and II) emerged. The first cluster I has 44 (65.67%) genotypes and the second cluster II has 23 (34.33%), including two enhanced varieties. The study revealed farmers' variety accessions' hidden yield-boosting potential by using conserved germplasm.

Rahman *et al.* (2020) examined the cluster analysis in regional flood frequency analysis. A total of 88 sites in New South Wales, Australia are adopted. Quantile regression technique (QRT) is integrated with the PCA to estimate the flood quantiles. A total of eight catchment characteristics are selected as predictor variables. A leave-one-out validation is applied to determine the efficiency of the developed statistical models using an ensemble of evaluation diagnostics. It is found that the PCA with QRT model does not perform well, whereas cluster/group formed with smaller sized catchments performs better (with a median relative error values ranging from 22% to 37%) than other clusters/groups. No linkage is found between the degree of heterogeneity in the clusters/groups and precision of flood quantile prediction by the multiple linear regression technique.

Dido *et al.* (2020) assessed the diversity of barley landraces collected from various altitudes and regions of Ethiopia. A total of 585 barley landraces and 10 checks were evaluated using augmented randomized complete block design consisting of six blocks. Data on 13 quantitative characters were subjected to calculation of descriptive statistics, ANOVA and multivariate analysis, Unweighted Pair Group Method Analysis (UPGMA) cluster analysis

and principal component analysis). There were significant differences (ANOVA, $P < 0.01$) among landraces for plant height, 1000-seed weight, number of seeds per spike, days to heading and days to maturity. All the genotypes were grouped into five clusters where 74.02% of the accessions (433) fall in cluster I, IV and V. Early matured accessions were grouped in cluster I, while late matured, high yielding and tall accessions were clustered in cluster IV. The highest intra-cluster distance was 23.12 for cluster III whereas the highest inter-cluster distance was 57.37 between cluster IV and V. The information generated complements the robust barley breeding program of competitive, stable and climate resilient varieties of end users' preferences in different agro-ecologies of Ethiopia.

Ramazani and Abdipour (2019) studied that 10 cultivars were tested in three field tests in randomised block design with three replicates throughout the 2013–2014 growing season to discover the most critical factors affecting barley grain production. Each experiment assessed 10 yield component qualities. After a combined analysis of variance, simple correlation coefficients, factor analysis, stepwise analysis, route analysis, and cluster analysis were performed on combined means. Ward's technique groups 10 cultivars into three. Cluster 1 cultivars had the largest plant height, seed/spike, and 1000-seed weight. Cluster 2 included lines with increased grain production, biological yield, and seeds/m². Cluster 3 contained control cultivars Sina and Nosrat. GGE biplot study suggests Sina, with its higher yield and relative stability, is the best cultivar.

Enyew *et al.* (2019) showed collections of 48 barley landrace accessions which were not studied yet and four standard checks to estimate the magnitude of genetic diversity among the genotypes and to identify the major morphological traits contributing for the observed variations. The experiment was laid in Augmented Randomized Complete Block Design in six blocks at Adet in 2016/17 cropping season. The traits used for analysis were days to 50% heading, days to maturity, plant height, total number of tillers/plant, effective number of tillers/plant, number of spikes/plant, spike length, average number of grains/plant, biomass yield/ha, thousand grain weight/gm, grain yield tones/ha and harvest index tones/ha. The 52 genotypes were grouped into six clusters where 65.39% of the genotypes (34) fall in cluster I, III and IV. Early matured genotypes were grouped in cluster III, late matured in cluster VI and high yielding and tall genotypes in cluster IV. The highest inter cluster distance was 57.00 between cluster V and IV. The result ensures the existence of high genetic divergence among the studied genotypes.

2.5. Principal component analysis (PCA) and Biplot analysis

Alemayehu *et al.* (2022) studied that a three-replication randomised complete block method, we assessed six enhanced malt barley cultivars. The 2019 and 2020 growing seasons were used for the study, which was carried out in the Lay Gayint district. The combined study revealed highly significant variations in all traits among types, years, and their interactions. From the cultivar Holker, the maximum yield (31.54 qt/ha) was attained. The examination of the correlation coefficients revealed a considerable and very strong positive link between grain yield and effective tiller count, spike length, and thousand seed weight, with a medium positive correlation between seed per spike. In the main component analysis, PC1, features with a stronger impact on yield were dominant. In the research locations and other agro-ecologies with a comparable makeup, a variation of Holker might be suggested. Due to a lack of new technologies, farmers lost several quintals of output; however, by utilising better production technology, the average yield increased.

Modarresi *et al.* (2022) examined that a randomised full block design with 27 genotypes in four replications to assess spring barley genotype genetic diversity based on phenological and morphological parameters. The first three principal components in principal component analysis explained 52.88 percent of the variation. Second and third components were 17.23% and 9.15%. Booting date (0.884), quantity of grains per spike (0.855), flowering date (0.776), and flag leaf width (0.883) had high coefficients in the first component. In the second component, plant height (0.885), shooting date (0.880), and flag leaf length (0.873) showed significant positive coefficients, while 1000-grain weight (-0.387) and plant weight (-0.377) had large negative coefficients. Third is leaf count. The third component had strong correlations for cluster emergence date (0.586), milk stage (0.739), and plant grain number (0.570). Third is maturity.

Derbew *et al.* (2020) conducted a study with twenty genotypes to estimate the extent of genetic variation and relationships among barley genotypes based on quantitative traits using multivariate analysis and, to identify the set of morpho-agronomic traits which could be further utilized in breeding programs. Using Eigen value greater than one as a measure for significance of a principal component (PC), three PCs extracted about 77% of the total variance of eight quantitative traits. Of these, the first two PCs explained about 60% of the gross variance while about 37% of the total variation accounted for by the first PC alone. In this study one should concentrate on early maturing genotypes with short grain filling period and head length having many spikelets spike⁻¹ which leads higher yield.

Dido *et al.* (2020) assessed the first three principal components contributed 51.76% of the total variations observed among the genotypes. Principal component one (PC1) alone had contributed 22.56% of the total variations mainly due to plant height, 1000-seed weight, grain yield and peduncle length in their respective order. Principal component two (PC2) contributed 18.94% of the total variations mainly through spike density, number of kernels per spike, spike weight and days to maturity in their descending order. Principal component three (PC3) had contributed 10.94% of the total variations through total number of tillers per plant, number of seed-bearing tillers, days to 90% maturity and days to 50% heading. Altitude of the original landrace collection sites also significantly impacted the various quantitative characteristics studied. Regional differentiations were also evident among the landrace collections.

Enyew *et al.* (2019) did experiment with huge collections of barley landrace genotypes in Ethiopian are not studied for the magnitude of genetic distances from each other. The 52 genotypes were grouped into six clusters where Principal component one (PC1) alone had contributed 49.96% of the total variations mainly due to grain yield, biomass yield, thousand grain weight and plant height in their respective order. Principal component two (PC2) contributed 15.98% of the total variations mainly through total number of tillers per plant, number of effective tillers per plant and number of spikes per plant in their descending order. Principal component three (PC3) had contributed 8.25% of the total variations through days to maturity, days to 50% heading and number of grains per plant. The result ensures the existence of high genetic divergence among the studied genotypes.

Hagenblad *et al.* (2019) reported that principal component analysis of all accessions separated two-row from six-row accessions. PCA of only the six-row accessions visualized the high level of variation among landraces. Seven principal components 21 (PCs) accounted for 75.46% of the total variance among the 20 variable morphological characters. Spike length, plant height, triplets per spike and stem pigmentation were the main contributors to the first PC, which explained 19.79% of total variation. An additional 14.38% of the variation, accounted for by the second PC, was due to contributions from awn length and spike shape. The third principal component, which explained 11.45% of the variation, had high loadings from auricle and awn pigmentation. With the exception of the two accessions from Lanzarote the morphological diversity showed little evidence of distinguishing between accessions from different islands along the first two PCs.

Kendal *et al.* (2019) carried out with four replications in a random design at seven environments in years 2012-13 and 2013- 14. The superior and stable genotypes were identified with GGE biplot and AMMI (Additive main effects and multiplicative interaction) models. The AMMI analysis showed that the major treatment sum of squares was affected by environments (80.6%), GE (14.0%) and genotypes (5.4%), respectively. On the other hand, the first two principal component axes (PCA 1 and PCA 2) contributed to the complete interaction with 88.1%, whereas, PCA 3 and PCA 4 axes only with 12.0%. The GGE biplot indicated that G4 is adaptable for all environments, while Altikat, G2 and G3 showed specific adaptation to E1, E3 and E5, G6, G7 and G8 to E6, respectively. According to both techniques, G2, G3, G6, G7, G8 and Altikat were the best genotypes with high yield, whereas G4 was the best with high yield, and stable and general adaptation. The results of biplot indicated that G4 was recommended for release and it was released as HEVSEL in 2017. On the other hand; G7 and G6 were protected as genetic material to use as parent in breeding programs for yield stability and quality respectively.

Yadav *et al.* (2018) conducted an experiment about principal component analysis revealed the quantitative traits, viz. grain yield, plant height and earliness, and qualitative traits, viz. grain color, overall phenotypic performance, lemma awn/hood and lemma awn barbs, to be the principal discriminatory characteristics of the Nepalese naked barley landrace collection. The Shannon–Weaver diversity index (H') ranged from 0.32 to 0.99 with a mean value of 0.73, inferring tremendous diversity in the collection for the qualitative traits.

2.6 Drought Tolerance Index (DSI)

Saremi *et al.* (2022) observed that in order to evaluate drought tolerance of 121 genotypes, lines, and barley cultivars and identify tolerant and susceptible genotypes based on grain yield and drought tolerance indices, an experiment was conducted in rainfed and irrigated conditions at Maragheh rainfed agricultural research station during the cropping years 1394-94 and 1394-95 using a randomised complete block design with two replications. Number of spikes, number of seeds, weight of 1,000 seeds, days to heading, days to maturity, and grain production were evaluated. The correlation between drought tolerance indices and grain yield in rainfed and irrigated conditions revealed that tolerance index (STI), mean productivity (MP), harmonic mean (HM), and geometric mean productivity (GMP) were significantly positively correlated with grain yield traits in both environmental conditions. Therefore, they were suitable for identifying high-yielding cultivars in both rainfed and irrigated conditions. In both situations, the number of viable spikes and the weight of 1000 seeds had a strong

connection with the STI, GMP, MP, and HM indices. In an examination of the principal components based on the drought tolerance index and grain yield under water conditions, the three components accounted for 81% of the initial data's variety. In rainfed conditions, the three factors accounted for around 88% of the overall variety. In this study, genotypes 10 (71557), 100 (Tokak / Demir-2) and 38 (72480) had greater grain production potential than other genotypes in both rainfed and irrigated situations.

Saed-Moucheshi *et al.* (2022) studied that with regards to the importance of drought stress and genotype screening under stress conditions, the current study was conducted to evaluate barley varieties in response to drought stress and find the tolerant ones, along with the determination of the influential ratio of each yield component on grain yield under both conditions. Accordingly, 25 barley varieties were evaluated under two water regimes including 100% (normal condition) and 50% (drought stress) of field capacity. According to the results of correlation of tolerance indices with grain yield, stress tolerance index (STI), harmonic mean productivity (HMP), and mean productivity (MP) which showed high correlations with grain yield under both conditions can be introduced as proper indices for screening tolerance genotypes of barley.

Bakhshi *et al.* (2022) examined that in 2019–2020 and 2020–2021, fifty barley landraces and six check varieties (Nosrat, Yousef, Nimroz, Goharan, Mehr, and Khatam) were tested under well-watered and drought circumstances. GT and GYT (genotype by yield*trait) biplots evaluated the data. The GYT biplot, called GYSI (Genotype by yield*stress index) in this work, also used drought stress tolerant and susceptibility indices including TOL, SSI, YSI, HM, GMP, MP, and STI. ATC view and SI ranking of GYT data found 27 genotypes under well-watered and drought stress that were above average with positive SI values. Likewise, 25 above average drought-tolerant genotypes were discovered based on GYSI technique. The results identified superior genotypes using plant height, YSI, and grain yield. Our investigation found 12 genotypes with high yield and drought tolerance. GT, GYT, and GYSI methods accurately selected high-yielding and drought-tolerant genotypes in locally adapted Iranian barley landraces.

Arazmjoo & Nikkhah Chamanabad (2022) showed that 19 promising barley lines and Goharan were tested under normal and terminal drought stress to identify drought-tolerant lines. The South Khorasan Agricultural and Natural Resources Research and Education Centre conducted the experiment in a randomised complete block design with three replications across two cropping years, 2019–2021. Drought stress affected the first-year

lines' days to maturity, grain filling duration, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield. The drought sensitivity and tolerance indices showed that YI, HM, STI, and GMP indices can be used to choose barley cultivars and lines in terminal drought stress locations, whereas MP, STI, GMP, and HM indices are recommended in other places. Lines 20, 11, and 14 were the most terminal drought-tolerant in this experiment. Stability indices and grain yield of the studied lines showed that grain yield had a positive and significant correlation with the variance of genotype and environment interaction I and regression coefficient (b) and a negative and significant correlation with the Kang (KR) and Thennarasu (NP(2,3)) statistics. Most stability statistics showed that lines 20, 14, and 8 were high-yielding and stable for cultivation under normal and terminal drought stress.

Yadav *et al.* (2022) examined that Drought, one of the most prevalent abiotic stresses, can lower agricultural productivity by 70%, making sustainable food production difficult. In arid and semi-arid regions, either reduction in water supply in soil or excessive transpiration can create drought experience in crops. Drought stress reduces barley grain yield by 49–87%. Drought affects all climates and 16.2–41.2% of arable land worldwide. Agronomists and plant breeders still face drought. By 2025, 1.8 billion people would be without water and 65% will be water-stressed. Climate change negatively impacts crop growth and output. Drought stress reduces agriculture productivity and production, hence vital crops must be improved. DWRUB 64, BH 946, RD 103, and RD 2592 were the most desirable parents since majority of the investigated traits were drought-tolerant. Among the F1 crossings, BH 946 × PL 426, BH 946 × RD 103, RD 2592 × PL 426, PL 426 × RD 2052, PL 426 × RD 103, and RD 2592 × RD 2035 were preferred for majority of the examined characteristics. In F2 crosses, RD 2592 × PL 426, DWRUB 64 × DWRB 137, PL 426 × RD 103, PL 426 × RD 2508, and RD 103 × The hybrids RD 2592 × PL 426 and PL 426 × RD 103 were more favourable because they had good drought tolerance for most attributes across generations.

Hasanuzzaman *et al.* (2022) observed that Plant drought adaptation may depend on quick recovery. We developed a set of simple and relevant physiological proxies to predict plant drought responses and evaluate the importance of physiological parameters such root length, stomata density, and residual transpiration in barley drought tolerance and recovery. Eighty barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) genotypes were droughted until 10% soil moisture, then rewatered. Visually scoring plants after dryness and two weeks after rewatering. SPAD values, chlorophyll fluorescence Fv/Fm ratio, stomatal density (SD), and residual transpiration were measured (RT). Quantifying root growth trends in paper rolls treated with

15% (w/v) polyethylene glycol (PEG) 8000 germinated the same genotypes. Genotypes' drought tolerance and recovery scores were substantially associated. Drought tolerance and recovery were strongly connected with SPAD value, Fv/Fm ratio, and root length. Both indices substantially linked with irrigated plant SD and RT in an unexpected way. We identified a positive correlation between drought tolerance and the ability to thrive in saline soils (a "physiological drought"). Drought-tolerant genotypes have better salinity tolerance, suggesting same processes. Drought-tolerant irrigated plants had less SD and more RT. Lower SD and greater RT under ideal conditions may be markers for barley drought resistance.

Ahakpas *et al.* (2020) studied that most barley farming areas in Iran are cold, arid, or semi-arid, hence high-yielding cultivars that can adapt to different climates and drought are needed. 108 barley genotypes were examined for effective morphological features on grain yield and drought tolerance. In 2015–2016, Dryland Agricultural Research Institute (DARI) (Maragheh station) conducted an alpha lattice experiment with two replications in rainfed and irrigation settings. Rainfed and additional irrigation circumstances differed in all traits. Under rainfed conditions, thousand kernel weight, NDVI in booting stage, stem width, and main spike length affected grain yield. Under supplementary irrigation conditions, thousand kernel weight, NDVI in milk development stage, and main spike length were most relevant. MP, GMP, STI, YI, and SSPI drought tolerance indices correlated best with grain yield in both situations. These indices found 25 drought-tolerant genotypes.

Sharifi-Alhosseini & Taherian (2018) revealed that twenty barley varieties and promising lines were examined in a randomised full block design with three replication under two irrigation circumstances (normal and water lack after 50% ear emergence). The experiment took two years at Torogh research station. Farm preparation, culture and sowing were conducted as usual protocol for experiment. Under stress, irrigation was terminated after 50% ear emergence, but under normal conditions 3-4 irrigation were applied according to crop water need. Stress tolerance indices were constructed using two-year means: MP, GMP, STI, SSI, TOL, YI, YSI, RDI. Biplot correlation equations may explain grain yield and derived indices, where GMP, MP, and STI were best under both situations. The hybrids RD 2592 × PL 426 and PL 426 × RD 103 were more favourable because they had good drought tolerance for most attributes across generations.

Taherian *et al.* (2017) showed that crop development and performance can be affected by abiotic stress. Drought and salinity limit crop output worldwide. This study examined many

selection indices to determine the best indices/cultivars for each environment under varied environmental conditions. Sixteen cultivars and promising lines of barely were planted in a randomised full block design with three replications in three different settings (optimal, salt stress, and end-of-season drought stress) in 2012-2013 at the Agricultural and Natural Research Station of Neishabour, Iran. On the basis of grain yield under non-stress, thirteen selection indices were calculated: abiotic tolerance index (ATI), stress susceptibility percentage index (SSPI), relative drought index (RDI), drought response index (DRI), drought resistance index (DI), yield stability index (YSI), yield index (YI), tolerance (TOL), stress susceptibility index (SSI), stress tolerance index (STI), harmonic mean (HM), geometric mean productivity (GMP), and mean productivity (MP). STI was the only index that could distinguish high-yield cultivars in both salinity stress and non-stressed conditions, according to this study. MP, YI, GMP, STI, and DI were better at finding tolerant genotypes under mild stress (drought stress). Genotype ranking also depended on stress type and severity.

2.7 Molecular characterization of barley genotypes using SSR markers

Abebe *et al.* (2023) studied that breeders use genetic variability to select barley accessions. Given the germplasm's heterogeneity, Ethiopia's gene bank does not archive genetic information about barley landraces. Hence, 20 barley accessions comprising 194 plants were studied for genetic diversity. Accessions come from 10 Ethiopian regions at various heights. 15 SSR markers tested the accessions (SSRs). Barley plants' genetic diversity was shown by the SSR markers' 57 alleles, ranging from two (GBM1042) to seven (Bmac0040). Ethiopian barley accessions from mid- and low-altitudes had higher allelic diversity than high-altitude accessions. The biggest molecular variance was within accessions (64.39%) and altitude classes (64.04%). Geographic and altitude-based genetic structure study found two subpopulations. Altitude influences barley genetic diversity, as shown by individual assignment by collection altitude. This study reveals that each barley line among the accessions should be considered a possible genetic material source and treated separately during germplasm collection and use.

Ahmed *et al.* (2021) studied that Fertile Crescent barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L. subsp. *vulgare*) was one of the first domesticated crops. Germplasm conservation and breeding programmes benefit from primary gene pool and landrace genetic diversity studies. Eighty-two barley genotypes—22 Iranian improved cultivars and 60 landrace accessions from different regions

of Iran—were used for genetic diversity analysis using three gene targeted markers, start codon targeted (SCoT) polymorphism, conserved DNA-derived polymorphism (CDDP), and CAAT box-derived polymorphism (CBDP) in comparison with sequence-related amplified polymorphism (SRAP) markers. 40 primers (10 from each marker) revealed barley genotype genetic polymorphism. SRAP markers had more polymorphic bands (67) than SCoT, CDDP, and CBDP markers. SCoT, CDDP, CBDP, and SRAP averaged 0.33, 0.37, 0.37, and 0.31 PIC values. SRAP and CBDP markers have higher MI than SCoT and CDDP. CDDP, CBDP, and SRAP markers clustered barley genotypes into three groups, while SCoT markers split them into four. Similarity matrices from each marker type correlated positively. Cluster analysis and STRUCTURE analysis using combined data sorted barley genotypes into three groupings that strongly matched their origins. Genotypes from west and north-west Iran clustered apart from those from north-east and centre Iran. This is the first complete report of gene-targeted molecular marker genetic diversity analysis in barley. These markers were effective for barley genetic diversity study and genomic diversity and germplasm conservation.

El-Awady *et al.* (2012) examined that KSA, which is losing biodiversity due to landrace replacement, knows nothing about barley landrace genetic diversity and morphological variability. Approach: RAPD and SSR were used to estimate intra- and inter-cultivar polymorphism in six barley KSA landraces from different geographical regions to determine genetic linkages and produce cultivar-specific molecular fingerprints. The long-term goal was to use these fingerprints to uncover molecular markers that co-segregate and isolate gene(s) that govern essential features for breeding programmes (marker assisted selection). Results: A clear and reproducible band profile of 13 RAPD and 7 SSR primers was produced from 20 and 10 primers, respectively. 54.6 percent of 111 RAPD bands were polymorphic. 5-15 alleles per primer averaged 8.54. ISSR found 53 alleles, 16 of which (30.2%) were polymorphic. 5-10 alleles per SSR primer averaged 7.57. RAPD markers had a mean PIC of 0.45 and SSR markers 0.37. SSR detects barley landrace genetic diversity better than RAPD. RAPD and SSR results match, and SSR results are more accurate for the geographical distribution of the six barley landraces. This work may improve barley data for KSA national barley programmes.

2.8 Population structure of barley genotypes

Degu *et al.* (2023) examined that Ethiopia's fifth-most-important food crop is barley. Barley genetics and population structure investigations are limited to gene bank collections. So, this study examines the selection, consumption, economic worth, genetic diversity, and population structure of farm-collected barley from the Gumer district of the Gurage Zone, which has been neglected. Semi-structured interviews and questionnaires collected barley use data in the research region. Population structure research showed Gumer barley landraces diverged from Japan and the US. US barley was the farthest from Gumer barley in principal component analysis. The markers' allele frequencies ranged from 0.10 to 0.50, averaging 0.28. The samples had substantial genetic diversity based on Nei's gene diversity (0.38) and polymorphism information content (0.30). Accessions were not clustered geographically. Because ethnic groups influenced Ethiopian barley selection and use, significant genetic variation necessitates further barley diversity research.

Gungor *et al.* (2022) recognizing that crop plant genetic structure and variety improves quantitative attributes. To assess population structure and genetic diversity, 54 barley cultivars issued from 1963 to the present by Turkish and Bulgarian institutes were screened with 18 iPBS and four SCoT markers. The results showed 530 polymorphic bands out of 560 total (438 and 92 amplified bands for iPBS and SCoT markers, respectively). Polymorphic band number averaged 24.09. The average polymorphism information content (PIC) value was 0.48 for iPBS and SCoT markers. 0.50 was the highest PIC. The iPBS2271 marker had the most effective number of alleles, Shannon's information index, and Nei's genetic diversity at 1.61, 0.52 and 0.35, respectively. The SCoT-71 marker had the highest values at 1.55, 0.32 and 0.48. Structure analysis of 530 amplified bands in 54 barley cultivars revealed a value of $k=5$ for the subpopulations. Average anticipated heterozygosity and fixation indices were 0.234 and 0.322. Martı and Zahir barley varieties had 75% genetic closeness, whereas Özdemir and Karatay 94 and Tosunpaşa and Konevi had 73%. Bayrak and Avcı-2002 have the maximum genetic diversity at 19.9%. Hence, barley cultivars released in Turkey and Bulgaria varied, and genetic diversity and statistical index analysis showed that iPBS and SCoT markers are powerful markers for genetic diversity study.

Marzougui (2021) examined that barley breeding operations need genetic dissimilarity and population structure data to conserve genetic diversity and generate new cultivars. SSR-type molecular markers were used to analyse Tunisian barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) genetic variation. 11 SSR markers had 30 alleles. The 16 barley accessions had 2 to 4 alleles per

locus, averaging 2.7, and the average polymorphic information content (PIC) was 0.54. STRUCTURE programme detected 4 subpopulations with allele frequencies from 0.0119 to 0.0597 and fixation indices (F_{st}) from 0.29 to 0.43. Higher allelic frequencies differentiate subpopulation members. Barley collection genetic diversity analysis will aid cultivar development and genetic resource usage.

Kashyap *et al.* (2020) studied that *Ustilago hordei*'s genome was mined for microsatellite distribution and genetic variation. Using simple sequence repeats, 59 fungal isolates from two Indian agro-ecological zones were studied to determine *U. hordei*'s genetic structure and variation (SSRs). Bioinformatic methods revealed 100,239 and 137,442 microsatellites from 20.13 and 26.94 Mb of assembled genomic sequences of *U. hordei* isolates Uh364 and Uh4857-4. Penta- and tri-nucleotides were the most common in both genomes. 15 polymorphic microsatellites with conservancies in both genomes were chosen to study *U. hordei* population genetics. With band sizes from 180 to 850 bp, microsatellite markers averaged two alleles. Polymorphic information content (PIC) was 0.095–0.37. UPGMA clustering and population structure analysis ($K = 2$) divided 59 isolates into two groups with 65% genetic similarity. The population has moderate gene flow ($N_m = 1.009$). AMOVA showed 87% genetic variation within groups and 13% between populations. Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis showed LD with epidemic population structure in both population groups ($SIA = 0.181$). In conclusion, the newly created neutral SSR markers are highly polymorphic within *U. hordei* and will help disclose evolutionary history, population dynamics in India, and CS of barley management techniques.

2.9 Genetic diversity assessment based on SSR in barley

Dido *et al.* (2022) studied that evaluation and characterization of genetic resources at in situ and ex situ GenBanks affects association mapping, genetic selection, breeding, and conservation. This study used 49 SSR markers to assess the genetic diversity, population structure, and connection of 384 Ethiopian barley varieties from several barley growing locations. These 49 SSR markers amplified 478 alleles, averaging 9.755 per locus, and 97.07% of the loci were polymorphic. Nei's genetic diversity index (h) was 0.654 and Shannon's was 0.647, showing modest genetic variety in barley genotypes. Population-level mean polymorphic loci (PPL) was 98.37%, $h = 0.388$, and $I = 0.568$. The Jimma population had the lowest genetic diversity, while the Arsi population had the most (PPL = 100%, $h = 0.439$, $I = 0.624$). AMOVA indicated significant genetic differentiation within and across populations ($P < 0.001$), with 84.21% and 15.79% of variation occurring within and within

populations, respectively. Genetic variation study found 0.053 gene differentiation and 4.467 gene flow between groups. STRUCTURE, neighbour-joining tree, and main coordinate analysis clustered 384 barley genotypes into seven genetic groupings that correlated with geographic distribution. The highest variation was within populations ($P < 0.001$). The findings will help create conservation measures like in situ and ex situ genetic protection.

Ghomi *et al.* (2022) studied that 14 phenologic and agronomic variables and 50 SSR markers covering barley's seven chromosomes were used to examine 120 barley genotypes' genetic diversity. Multiple regressions in two circumstances examined the correlations between these marker loci and the characteristics. In Gonbad-e-Kavous University's Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Resources experimental field, the field experiment was conducted before and after the region's ideal planting date. Both planting dates were randomised complete block designs with two replications. SSR data clustered barley genotypes into six categories. Only spike length had a single relevant marker. Stepwise regression showed significant relationships between characteristics and 60 SSR marker alleles under cold stress. 63 SSR marker alleles correlated significantly with the characteristics under normal settings. Among the 50 SSR markers, the Bmag0211 marker with the highest coefficient of determination (R^2) in regression analyses of grain yield, 1000-kernel weight under non-stress conditions, grain width and days to maturity under cold stress conditions, and HVBM5A marker associated with spike length, 1000-kernel weight, and days to flowering under cold stress conditions should be given special attention. These markers may be innovative and more trustworthy than others. After further testing, the informative markers may be appropriate for barley marker-assisted breeding.

Jabbari *et al.* (2022) examined that drought impacts agricultural productivity and phenological phases. Phenological stages can significantly impact crop output and quality. In this study, 14 AFLP primer combinations and 32 SSR loci were used to determine barley cultivars' molecular profiles. Phenotypic data demonstrated high cultivar diversity. Two barley subgroups were analysed. Linkage disequilibrium study showed that r^2 values for all marker pairs average 0.0178. Mixed linear model showed that 137 loci were associated with nine attributes under normal and drought stress circumstances. Marker-assisted selection in barley drought-resistant breeding efforts may use the markers.

Jan *et al.* (2022) showed that Western-Himalayan India grows barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). 105 barley genotypes—38 two-rowed and 67 six-rowed—were phenotyped for 10 significant quantitative features. 14 unlinked SSR markers characterised 96 barley genotypes (7 random

and 7 genic SSR markers). SSR marker data showed 67 alleles (range 2 to 8) at 4.78 alleles/locus. Genetic SSR markers are slightly less varied (4.71 alleles/locus) than random genomic SSR markers (4.85 alleles/locus) when analysed individually. The most polymorphic/informative barley allelic diversity markers were two random (XBmac156 and XBmag378) and one genic (XGbm1221) SSR markers detecting 7–8 alleles. Genotypic data clustered 96 genotypes into broad, sub, and sub-sub clusters. Three sub-clusters of genotypes had no trait-specific association. Genotypic data analysis showed moderate genetic diversity in 96 barley genotypes. The present study's various and promising genotypes for multiple attributes may help future barley breeding projects worldwide.

Mariey *et al.* (2022) observed that in semiarid and arid regions, water constraint and climate change threaten agriculture development. Ten SSR primers yielded 26 alleles, averaging 2.6 per locus. Each SSR marker's Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) ranged from 0.33 (Bmag 0387) to 0.47 (Bmac 0167), averaging 0.34. Cluster analysis split the eight barley genotypes into two distinct groupings based on water stress tolerance. Egypt's breeding initiatives used genetic information on eight water stress-tolerant barley varieties.

Sayd *et al.* (2022) observed that this study used molecular markers and quantitative agronomic parameters to analyse and compare 29 barley genotypes under irrigation in the Brazilian Cerrado. RAPD, ISSR, and SSR molecular markers were employed. In two irrigated environments in the Brazilian Cerrado, quantitative agronomic features were assessed for estimated grain production, grain size, thousand seed weight, plant height, lodging degree, and days to heading. Marker polymorphisms for RAPD, ISSR, and SSR were 91, 51.46, and 85%, respectively. RAPD, ISSR, and SSR markers are complimentary for barley genotype identification. For more thorough genetic variability investigations, supplementary analyses of molecular markers are needed due to the low correlations between molecular marker distances and agronomic trait distances. The genotypes' agronomic properties vary between environments. Because of their genetic heterogeneity, the selected genotypes can form the Brazilian Cerrado's working collection of irrigated barley.

Tomka *et al.* (2021) studied that cereals are strategic food and nutrition. Food and brewing industries use thousands of barley varieties to make malt. We employed SSR markers to distinguish barley genotypes in this investigation. 4 pure and 1 compound markers tested barley. STMS showed substantial polymorphism. 24 variants had 27 alleles, 5.4 per locus. DI and PIC averaged 0.767 and 0.756. SSR marker Bmag 0222 (7 alleles) showed the most polymorphism and one heterozygous variety. Hierarchic cluster analysis using UPGMA

algorithm developed dendrogram from discovered alleles. Genotypes were clustered into three to examine genetic links among barley cultivars.

Abdul-Razzak Tahir *et al.* (2021) showed that Barley is an ancient cereal crop grown worldwide. 25 microsatellite (SSR) loci examined genetic diversity in 16 barley (*Hordeum* spp) genotypes. All seven barley chromosomes have 94 alleles. 76 were polymorphic, averaging 3.04 alleles/primer. Allele frequencies assessed major allele frequency, gene diversity, and PIC with mean values of 0.543, 0.571, and 0.513, respectively. Principal component analysis showed considerable barley genotype genetic variability. ATACO, Canela, Local Abiad Sulaimani, and Amal2 were considerably divergent. Hierarchical cluster analysis using the UPGMA method divided genotypes into 7 genetically distant groups. Both analyses parallel to primary coordinate analysis show that Quinn, Zambaka, Al-khair, and Arta/3/Avar genotypes are closely connected due to continuous breeding efforts. These values show that SSR markers can distinguish barley genetics and breeding.

Nyiraguirwa *et al.* (2021) examined that barley is the fourth-most-cultivated cereal crop. Demand for higher-yielding, nutritious, and better-adapted agricultural varieties has encouraged genebank variety use. Thus, barley genetic diversity must be assessed to determine lineage and use novel alleles in breeding programmes. We used 14 polymorphic Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers to analyse genetic diversity, genetic connection, and population structure of 113 barley lines from 14 countries, mostly Africa. This collection has substantial genetic variation, with 5.36 average alleles per locus, 0.57 PIC, and 0.61 genetic diversity. AMOVA found 74% genetic variation within nations and 26% between countries. STRUCTURE analysis, neighbor-joining clustering, and principal components analysis identified three main subpopulations based on geographic origin. Growing circumstances, migration between and within countries may have contributed to the genetic diversity of North African barley germplasm. This study conserves and uses barley germplasm.

Kumar *et al.* (2021) studied that Linkage disequilibrium (LD)-based association mapping (AM) was performed on 48 barley accessions (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) from ICARDA in India using polymorphic SSR markers for eight agro-morphological variables. CMLM model validated MLM (Q+K) marker trait association mapping. Twelve marker traits correlations were significant at $p < 0.001$. ABC252 on 2H and Bmag273 on 7H were unique associations with DH, TGW, and SL. This study provides SSR markers for barley QTL/marker assisted selection of various attributes.

Brbaklić *et al.* (2021) studied that finding new crop-improving alleles requires determining breeding material's genetic diversity and population structure. This work used microsatellites, pedigree, and phenotypic data to analyse genetic diversity and population structure of a 40-year-old barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) breeding collection. 90 barley genotypes with 338 polymorphism alleles were phenotyped during three growth seasons. Genetic diversity changed during breeding. Population structure divided breeding material into three groups. Principal coordinate analysis grouped genotypes by growth behaviour and row type. on chromosomes 1 and 2 have beneficial allele effects that can be utilised to generate drought-resistant barley variants. This study found new alleles (qLWS-4a, qSLS-4, qLNS-7b, qSCS-7, and qLNS-7a) for pyramiding elite alleles for molecular breeding and marker assisted selection to improve barley salinity tolerance.

Kumar *et al.* (2020) observed that this study used 51 polymorphic SSR markers to analyse the genetic diversity and population structure of 48 barley accessions from ICARDA to choose unique parents for breeding. The selected barley SSR markers showed substantial polymorphism with a mean polymorphic information content of 0.491. Only two significant clusters showed a fine genetic base. All accessions were clustered 100%. Most (78%) of molecular variance was between populations, while 22% was between individuals within groups. This distance matrix created a neighbour-joining (NJ) tree with two large clusters. Cluster 1 had all hulled barley and cluster 2 all hulless. Cluster 2 has three subclusters. Like the NJ tree, principal coordinates analysis clustered hulled and hulless barley accessions. This study found genetic diversity in the 48 investigated accessions. India and other countries can breed barley using the appropriate genetic resources.

Mohammadi *et al.* (2020) showed that natural and mass selection during barley domestication and cultivation favoured desirable features. A set of 77 and 72 EST-SSR and gSSR markers dispersed on seven barley chromosomes were used to analyse population structure and genetic linkages among 144 barley landraces and breeding materials from diverse nations. 77 EST-SSRs and 72g SSR sites amplified 262 and 429 alleles, respectively. 185 private/group-specific alleles were found in landraces compared to 14 in "cultivar and advanced breeding lines," suggesting the possibility of introgressing preferred alleles from landraces into breeding materials. Iranian landraces had higher genetic diversity than foreign and breeding materials. Iranian, exotic, and breeding materials had 37, 15, and 14 private/group-specific alleles. Model- and distance-based clustering and main coordinate analysis separated landraces and breeding materials into three groups for 144 barley genotypes. Population

structure, domestication history, and eco-geography affected allele distribution. The high allelic richness in the examined barley genotype provides insights into the available diversity and facilitates the establishment of core groups based on maximising allelic diversity for barley breeding operations.

Mariey *et al.* (2020) evaluated 15 Egyptian barley cultivars and their genetic diversity for water stress resistance using simple sequence repeats (SSR) across two seasons. Egyptian barley Giza 126, Giza 131, and Giza 2000 were tolerant cultivars with the highest mean values for all morphological and physiological parameters. Fingerprinting ten SSR primers produced twenty alleles, ranging from one to four per locus with a mean of 2.0. The average PIC value of each SSR marker was 0.227, ranging from 0.23 (HvM67) to 0.58 (EBmac 624). Un-weighted Pair-Group Method with Arithmetic (UPGMA) cluster analysis of similarity data grouped all fifteen Egyptian cultivars into two major groups based on their water stress tolerance: the first group included all water stress tolerant cultivars and moderately tolerant in two closely related clusters, while the other group included all sensitive genotypes and moderate cultivars in two clusters. SSR markers are professional and detective tools for assessing genetic diversity and relatedness and distinguishing Egyptian barley cultivars for water stress tolerance for breeding programmes.

Yadav *et al.* (2020) observed that SSR markers analysed genetic diversity in released varieties and registered germplasm of Indian barley. Twenty-five SSR markers from all seven barley chromosomes were utilised to evaluate genetic variation in 88 germplasm lines. These SSR markers had an average PIC of 0.40 and amplified 3.4 alleles, ranging from 2 to 5. Germplasm accessions averaged 0.45 genetic diversity, ranging from 0.05 to 0.91. Barley germplasm accessions were different. Cluster analysis showed that most variations from one centre clustered together, suggesting a restricted genetic substrate for varietal development.

Elakhdar *et al.* (2018) examined that a barley core collection can be extensively investigated to find loci/genes for quantitative and qualitative trait improvement. 261 polymorphic SSR alleles examined all genotypes. The average locus had 4 alleles, PIC was 0.49, and genetic diversity ranged from 0.03 to 0.82. Three genotype subpopulations matched their origins. At molecular levels, population genetic variation was 51% higher than between populations ($F_{ST} = 0.491$ when $P < 0.10$). Due to being taken from diverse places with distinct ear-types, subpopulations-II had the largest polymorphism variance. A neighbor-joining tree and main components analysis clustered the 153 barley genotypes into three subpopulations. These results showed genetic variety among Egyptian barley genotypes, suggesting association

analysis, classical mapping population development, and parental line selection in breeding programmes. Thus, Egypt needs exotic genotypes to generate new barley varieties.

Shakhatreh *et al.* (2016) showed that cultivated barley comes from wild barley, *Hordeum spontaneum*. Wild barley develops under many environmental and climatic circumstances throughout the Fertile Crescent in the Near East. Jordan wild barley may have drought-tolerant genes that could boost cultivated versions. Using Simple Sequence Repeats, 103 wild barley genotypes from different parts of Jordan and 29 farmed barley genotypes were evaluated for genetic diversity and allelic variation (SSR). The *spontaneum* genotypes were classified into six populations by longitude, latitude, altitude, and rainfall zone of their collection sites and farmed in one population. 11 SSR markers with known sequences and chromosomal positions evaluated all barley genotypes. 237 alleles from 11 microsatellite markers averaged 21.5 per locus. *Spontaneum* genotypes had 209 alleles, averaging 19 per locus, while cultivated genotypes had 95, averaging 8.6 per locus. In addition, *spontaneum* had 52 alleles (22%) and cultivated barley 22 (9%). The mean total gene diversity (H_t) was 0.86, ranging from 0.72 to 0.94, indicating considerable genetic diversity. H averaged 0.79. Morphological traits such awn length, plant height, days to maturity, peduncle length, extrusion, and tillering number revealed larger variation within populations than between populations, supporting the molecular conclusion. Ecological geography clustered populations.

CHAPTER III

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the experimental field of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur during the rabi seasons from December to April, 2021-22. The main purposes of the study were to assess variability, heritability, diversity, principal component analysis, and through SSR marker: population structure, Nei's similarity index, genetic diversity . To achieve this aim, the materials and methods of this study are presented in this chapter under the following sub headings.

3.1 Location

The experimental site was situated under the Dinajpur Sadar upazila and located at East longitude at an altitude of 37.5 m above from the mean sea level. The land belongs to the agro-ecological region of the Old Himalayan Piedmont plain (AEZ-1).

3.2 Climate

The experimental site belongs to the Rabi season (October-February). During the growth period of this crop the atmospheric temperature was decreased as the rabi season proceed with occasional gusty winds.

3.3 Soil

The experimental field was a medium high land belonging to the non-calcarious dark gray floodplain soil under the agro-ecological zone (AEZ-1) of Old Himalayan piedmont plain. The soil is sandy loam under the order Inceptisol. The soil test (SRDI, Dinajpur) revealed that the soil contained OM 0.89%, total nitrogen 0.04%, potassium 0.26 and magnesium 0.66 meq/100 g soil. The other mineral matter was phosphorus 55.85, sulphur 9.93 and zinc 1.43 µg/ gm soil. The soil pH condition was 4.7. So, it denoted the acidic condition of soil.

3.4 Experimental design and layout

The experiment was conducted in a strip-plot design with two replications. Here, two treatments viz. control and drought stress were assigned in block and genotypes were assigned randomly in blocks. The row-to-row distance was 25 cm and the plant-to-plant distance was 15 cm. The inter block distance was 50 cm.

3.5 Plant Materials

In this research work, 123 barley lines were used. The barley genotypes collected from Germplasm Centre, Plant Breeding Institute (PBI), University of Sydney, Australia and Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Bangladesh were used in the present investigation. These genotypes and their origin are presented in Table1. is shown in next page.

3.6 Land preparation

The land was first ploughed by two ploughing with a tractor mounted disc plough during first year. During second period, the land was ploughed by a power tiller. After a few days the land was further ploughed and cross ploughed with the country plough followed by laddering to get a good puddle condition. Weeds and stubbles were removed from the field prior to the sowing of seed. Manures and fertilizers were applied as per the recommended dose.

3.7 Sowing of seeds

During the first sowing date, the seeds of the barley genotypes were sown on 15th December, 2021 in the experimental seed beds.

Figure 1: Sowing of seeds

Table 1: Plant genetic materials with their name and origin used in this experiment (Contd.)

Sl. No.	Genotype	Variety	Origin	Sl. No.	Genotype	Variety	Origin
1	EEB011	Calotte	Russia	31	EEB117	Pi 94821	Ukraine
2	EEB017	Bark	Russia	32	EEB119	Pi 94823	Ukraine
3	EEB018	Chernishevka	Russia	33	EEB122	Pi 94824	Ukraine
4	EEB023	Dioszegi 625 sorapa	Russia	34	EEB129	Pi 101441	Ukraine
5	EEB028	Dvoran	Hungary	35	EEB131	Krasnoyarsk goldcoin	Hungary
6	EEB032	Exedra	Czech republic	36	EEB134	Pi 184050	Russia
7	EEB035	Fleche	Former soviet Union	37	EEB135	Pi 184061	Yugoslavia
8	EEB038	Golozernyj 1	Ukraine	38	EEB136	Pi 184063	Yugoslavia
9	EEB040	Iris	Russia	39	EEB140	Pi 184069	Yugoslavia
10	EEB041	Hatvani	Russia	40	EEB144	Groavac-buskat	Yugoslavia
11	EEB042	Hungary r2382	Hungary	41	EEB145	Vladivostock 1	Yugoslavia
12	EEB043	Iljsineckij 43	Hungary	42	EEB147	Mesterhazi	Russia
13	EEB047	Kite	Russia	43	EEB150	Pereztegi	Hungary
14	EEB050	Kurof	Russia	44	EEB152	31259a	Hungary
15	EEB053	Louasgpatonai universal	Russia	45	EEB161	Ex ussr barley	Former soviet Union
16	EEB060	Nutans 244	Hungary	46	EEB163	Greek g-63994	Russia
17	EEB069	Rikotense 45	Ukraine	47	EEB166	Mfb 104	Greece
18	EEB078	Smooth awn	Russia	48	EEB168	U 463	Hungary
19	EEB081	Tak hanna	Yugoslavia	49	EEB169	Orbit	Hungary
20	EEB082	Taplani	Hungary	50	EEB173	Pervenec	Czech republic
21	EEB087	Uervonetz	Hungary	51	EEB203	Perelom	Ukraine
22	EEB088	Vyatskiy 1163	Russia	52	EEB204	Afrasiab	Former soviet Union
23	EEB090	Yuznyj	Russia	53	EEB208	Krasnoufimskij 95	Former soviet Union
24	EEB091	Zero	Russia	54	EEB212	Mamluk	Former soviet Union
25	EEB092	Pi 249934	Russia	55	EEB227	Icb-100140	Former soviet Union
26	EEB107	Karpathos	Greece	56	EEB251	Krim nackt zweizeilig	Former soviet Union
27	EEB111	Doneckij 4	Greece	57	EEB254	Dina	Ukraine
28	EEB112	Har'kovskij 84	Former soviet Union	58	EEB255	Hor 1368	Russia
29	EEB114	Ciho 2632	Former soviet Union	59	EEB265	Martonvasari korai Tovasz	Russia
30	EEB116	Pi 94787	Russia	60	EEB266	Kubanec	Hungary

Table 1: Plant genetic materials with their name and origin used in this experiment

Sl. No.	Genotype	Variety	Origin	Sl. No.	Genotype	Variety	Origin
61	EEB267	Juznyj	Russia	92	EEB371	Kombainiesis	Former soviet Union
62	EEB290	Detenicky bohatyr	Ukraine	93	EEB375	Mfb 104	Former soviet Union
63	EEB292	Exportni hanacky	Czech republic	94	EEB376	Slovensky 802	Hungary
64	EEB295	Horicky	Czech republic	95	EEB377	Vairogs	Czech republic
65	EEB296	Kasticky	Czech republic	96	EEB380	Svit	Latvia
66	EEB297	Nitransky exportni	Czech republic	97	EEB382	Chervonetz	Slovakia
67	EEB298	Novodvorsky hanacky	Czech republic	98	EEB384	Martonvasari mk-175	Russia
68	EEB301	Zborovicky kargyn	Czech republic	99	EEB385	Gintariniaj	Hungary
69	EEB308	Radosinsky sladar	Czech republic	100	EEB394	Diamant	Lithuania
70	EEB309	Pi 467629	Slovakia	101	EEB400	Hana	Czech republic
71	EEB312	PI 440418	Russia	102	EEB401	Hor 8676	Czech republic
72	EEB313	Beta	Former soviet Union	103	EEB407	Zhodinskij 5	Czech republic
73	EEB318	Perun	Hungary	104	EEB408	Nutans 115	Belarus
74	EEB325	Icb 119304	Czech republic	105	EEB409	Auksinjai	Armenia
75	EEB335	Ig 24943	Czech republic	106	EEB417	Akcent	Lithuania
76	EEB336	Ig 26734	Russia	107	EEB418	Athenais	Czech republic
77	EEB337	Ig 26735	Georgia	108	EEB427	No. 14 (stamn)	Greece
78	EEB343	Ig 28518	Georgia	110	EEB431	Hanna	Bulgaria
79	EEB344	Ig 35200	Slovakia	111	EEB433	Bohemian	Czech republic
80	EEB345	Ig 36206	Georgia	112	EEB434	Imperial	Czech republic
81	EEB346	Ig 36207	Slovakia	113	EEB436	Dobrovicky starocesky	Hungary
82	EEB347	Ig 36595	Slovakia	114	EEB438	Michalovicky nahy	Czech republic
83	EEB352	Ig 112502	Hungary	115	EEB439	118kr nahy	Czech republic
84	EEB353	Ig 112452	Georgia	116	EEB440	Dvoran	Czech republic
85	EEB354	Ig 125712	Georgia	117	EEB443	Jarek	Slovakia
86	EEB355	Ig 125713	Georgia	118	EEB444	Malvaz	Czech republic
87	EEB358	Ig 125716	Georgia	119	EEB450	Atlas	Czech republic
88	EEB362	Ig 125717	Georgia	120	BARI 5	BARI barley 5	Bangladesh
89	EEB363	Ig 125740	Georgia	121	BARI 7	BARI barley 7	Bangladesh
90	EEB366	Ig 125810	Armenia	122	BARI 8	BARI barley 8	Bangladesh
91	EEB370	Ciho 5541	Greece	123	BARI 9	BARI barley 9	Bangladesh

3.8 Fertilizer application

The following fertilizer, manure and other materials doses were applied in the field.

Types of Fertilizer	Recommended dose ha ⁻¹
DAP	156 kg
MoP	156 kg
Boron	104 kg
Monovit(sulphur)	10 kg
Furadan	10 kg

Here, 1/2 doses of nitrogen (N) & full doses of phosphorus (P), potassium (K), Sulphur (S) and zinc (Zn) was applied as basal during final land preparation & remaining ½ doses of the nitrogen was top dressed in two equal splits at 30-35 days after sowing (DAS) and 55-60 DAS.

3.9 Intercultural operation

After sowing care were taken against birds up to 15 days. For protecting the field from animal, netting was given. Some important intercultural operations were accomplished during the cropping period for the better growth and development of the plants.

3.9.1 Gap filling

The gap fillings were made where it was necessary.

3.9.2 Weeding

Weeding was done to break the soil crust. It was also done to keep the plots free from weeds, easy aeration of soil and to incorporate the nitrogen fertilizer into the soil for reducing the loss of fertilizer through de-nitrification and leaching which ultimately ensured better growth and development of plants.

3.9.3 Irrigation

Three irrigations were given at the experimental plot. First irrigation was given lightly at 10 DAS for crown root initiation. Second irrigation was given at the hard drought stage of the control field only and adequate measures were taken to keep the pest and disease infestation to 29 a minimum level at 25 to 30 days after sowing. Third irrigation was given at panicle emergence at 65-75 days after sowing on the control field only. During irrigation, precautions were taken to remove the stagnancy of water.

3.9.4 Harvesting

The maturity of crops was determined when 80% of the barley seeds became physiologically mature. It should be harvested the right time to prevent from over ripening to avoid breaking of spikes. The crop was harvested and the yields of grain were recorded after thoroughly drying in sun.

3.9.5 Processing

Barley grain has a property of absorbing moisture from the atmosphere so the crop was stored in dry place after harvesting. Then the spikes were taken in an oven for proper drying. From oven the spikes were taken for threshing. Grains were collected to record the grain yield plant-1.

3.10. Collection of data

The data on different yield and yield contributing characters were recorded considering each plant of the plots. Among the characters studied days to 50% flowering was recorded at different times from the plots. Here, three plants from each row were tagged after germination and the data were recorded on the following characters:

- i) Days to flowering
- ii) Plant height (cm)
- iii) Tiller number per plant
- iv) Canopy temperature
- v) Chlorophyll content
- vi) Number of grains per spike
- vii) Thousand grain weight (kg)
- viii) biological weight (g)
- ix) Days to maturity
- x) Growth habit
- xi) Number of spike per plant
- xii) Row type
- xiii) Proline content
- xiv) Relative water content
- xv) Excessive water loss
- xvi) Yield per plant (g)

3.11. Procedure of recording data on morpho-physiological traits

A brief outline of the data recording procedure is given below:

i) Days to flowering:

Days to 50% flowering were calculated by counting the number of days from the date of sowing till the emergence of 50% spike (eye estimation).

ii) Plant height (cm):

Plant height was measured from the base of the plant to the top of the spikes with the help of measuring scale and was expressed as centimeter (cm).

iii) Tiller number per plant:

For recording the number of effective tiller per plant, the tiller which emerges the spikes that were counted from the individual plant at the reproductive growth stage.

iv) Canopy temperature (°C): Canopy temperature was measured with a hand-held infrared thermometer. It was recorded during noon under the bright sun and less wind within 2 hours from started recording data.

v) Chlorophyll content: This trait was measured in fully expanded sunlight flag leaves by using self-calibrating Minolta chlorophyll meter (Model: SPAD-505, Minolta Co. Ltd., Japan) and expressed as SPAD (Soil Plant Analyses Development) unit.

vi) Number of grains per spike:

Number of grains in every spike of the individual plants are counted and averaged to measure number of grains per spike.

vii) Thousand grain weight (g):

After collecting number of thousand seeds from each genotype, thousand seed weight was weighted with an electric balance.

viii) Biological weight (g):

Biological weight of individual plant was counted.

ix) Days to maturity: Days to physiological maturity were calculated by counting the number of days from the date of sowing till 90% peduncle and spike become completely yellow.

x) Growth habit: Growth habit was measured using the following scale:

1. Spreading type
2. Semi-spreading type
3. Intermediate type
4. Semi-erect type
5. Erect type

xi) Row Type: Row type data was by the decoration of spiket.

Figure 2: Showing row type

xii) Estimation of proline content

To estimate proline from each landrace, fresh green leaves (0.1 g/sample) will be collected from the plot basis and will be carried in 70% ethanol to the Genetics and Plant Breeding Laboratory, HSTU, Dinajpur. The leaves will be grounded to powder and then homogenized with 10 ml of 3% (w/v) sulpho salicylic acid and will be passed through a Whatman 2 filter paper. A reagent, 2 ml ninhydrin and 2 ml glacial acetic acid will be added to 2v ml filtrated extract. The mixture will then be incubated at 100°C in a water bath for one hour. The reaction mixture will be placed on rice and excreted with 4 ml toluene. Absorption of chromospheres will be read at 250 nm using Perkin's lambda 900 uv/vis spectrophotometer. Toluene will be used as blank. The proline concentration will

be calculated using L - proline corresponding to aroma content as suggested by Bates *et al.* (1973).

The proline content on fresh weight basis as-

$$\mu \text{ moles per g tissue} = \mu\text{g proline/ml} \times \text{ml toluene}/115.5 \times 1/\text{g sample}$$

Figure 3: Estimation of proline content in laboratory

xiii) Relative water content (RWC): At the middle of plant canopy, five fully developed leaf samples will be taken from each of the selected plants from each plot, when drought appeared. After excision each sample will be carefully taken to laboratory in polythene bag and fresh weight will be recorded immediately. The leaf samples will be kept in water for overnight to record turgid leaf weight. On next day the samples will be oven dried at 70° C for six hours.

The relative water content will be measured using the following formula:

$$\text{RWC} = \frac{\text{Fresh weight} - \text{Dry weight}}{\text{Turgid weight} - \text{Dry weight}}$$

xiv) Excised leaf water loss (ELWL): Three fully developed leaves will be excised from selected plants and carefully will be packed in polythene bags. The samples will be brought into laboratory avoiding any water loss. Immediately at laboratory fresh weight of leaves will be recorded and samples will be left on laboratory benches for six hours. After six hours the weight of wilted leaves will be recorded and samples will then be dried in oven at 70° C.

The ELWL will be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{ELWL} = \frac{\text{Fresh weight} - \text{Wilted weight}}{\text{Dry weight}}$$

xv) Yield per plant (g): It was recorded as weight of clean dry seeds of each genotype harvested after full maturity and was expressed as grams.

3.12 Statistical analysis

The data obtained for different characters were recorded first on MS excel sheet. Afterwards, the data were analyzed using the software package R of version 4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022), and Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) of version 2.0.1 (STAR 2014). Analysis of variance and the post-hoc tests were performed in package agricolae (Mendiburu and Simon 2015) in R. The simple correlation co-efficient and regression was conducted in R. Finally, the mean data of 123 EEB lines was used in cluster analysis, principal component and biplot analysis in STAR software (STAR 2014).

3.12.1. Analysis of variance

The analysis of variance was computed using the software package R version 4.2.2. For the experiment of RCBD method, the structure of ANOVA was as follows:

The structure of ANOVA (two factor)

Source of variation	d.f.	M.S.S.	Expected values of M.S.S.
Replication (r)	r-1	M1	-
Genotypes (g)	g-1	M2	$\sigma^2_e + r. \sigma^2_g$
Treatment (t)	t-1	M3	$\sigma^2_e + r. \sigma^2_y$
Genotype \times treatment	(r-1) (gy-1)	M4	$\sigma^2_e + r. \sigma^2_{gy}$
Error	(r-1) (g-1)	M5	σ^2_e
Total	(rg-1)	M1 + M2 + M3+ M4+ M5	-

The structure of ANOVA (one factor)

Source of variation	d.f.	M.S.S.	Expected values of M.S.S.
Replication (r)	r-1	Mr	-
Genotypes (g)	g-1	Mg	$\sigma^2_e + r. \sigma^2_g$
Error	(r-1) (g-1)	Me	σ^2_e
Total	(rg-1)	Mr + Mg + Me	-

Where, r = number of replications

g = number of genotypes

t = treatment

3.12.2 Estimation of genotypic and phenotypic variances

Genotypic and phenotypic variances were estimated based on method whether the genotype, location and environment factors are defined as random or fixed reported by Dagnelie (1975).

$$\text{Genotypic variance } (\sigma^2_g) = (\text{MSg}-\text{MSe})/r$$

Where,

MSg = Mean sum of squares for genotypes;

MS_e = Mean sum of squares for error

r = Number of replications; and

$$\text{Phenotypic variance } (\sigma^2_p) = \sigma^2_g + \sigma^2_e$$

Where,

σ^2_g = Genotypic variance

σ^2_e = Environmental variance/Error mean square

3.12.3 Estimation of heritability

Heritability in broad sense (h^2_b) was estimated following the formula of Johnson *et al.* (1955).

$$h^2_b (\%) = \frac{\sigma^2_g}{\sigma^2_p} \times 100$$

Where,

σ^2_g = Genotypic variance; and

σ^2_p = Phenotypic variance.

3.12.4 Estimation of genetic advance

Estimation of genetic advance was done following formula given by Johnson *et al.* (1955) and Allard (1960).

$$\text{Genetic advance (GA)} = h^2_b \cdot K \cdot \sigma_p$$

Where,

h^2_b = Heritability in broad sense;

K = Selection intensity which is equal to 2.06 at 5% level; and

σ_p = Phenotypic standard deviation

3.12.5 Estimation of genetic advance in percentage of mean, GA (%)

Genetic advance in percent of mean was calculated by the formula of Comstock and Robinson (1952) as follows

$$GA\% = \frac{GA}{x}$$

Where,

GA = Genetic advance; and

x = Population mean

3.12.6 Estimation of correlation co-efficient

Simple correlation co-efficient (r) among 11 important barley characters were estimated with the following formula (Miller *et al.* 1958 and Singh and Chaudhary, 1985).

$$r = \frac{\sum xy - \frac{\sum x \sum y}{N}}{\sqrt{(\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{N})(\sum y^2 - \frac{(\sum y)^2}{N})}}$$

Where,

Σ = Summation;

x and y = Two variables correlated; and

N = Number of observations

3.12.7. Estimation of regression coefficient

Simple linear regression coefficient among characters were estimated with following formula

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where:

Y = is the dependent variable (yield per plant)

X = is the independent (explanatory) variable (other characters except yield per plant)

a = is the intercept

b = is the slope

The formula for intercept “a” and the slope “b” can be calculated per below.

$$a = \frac{(\sum y)(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)(\sum xy)}{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2}$$
$$b = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2}$$

3.12.8 Diversity analysis

Diversity or Cluster analysis was performed by D² analysis (originally proposed outlined by Mahalanobis, 1928 and 1936, and extended by Rao, 1952) which helps to divide the genotypes based on the data set into more or less homogeneous groups. D² statistic is potential tool for identification of parents which are genetically diversified and used in hybridization programme complete linkage method. Cluster diagram gives a brief idea of the pattern of diversity among the genotypes and the relationship between different genotypes included in a cluster.

3.12.9 Principal component analysis and biplot analysis

The PCA is the process of computing the principal components and using them to perform a change of basis. The principal components were computed from the correlation matrix obtained from the sum of squares product matrix of the characters and genotype score obtained from the first component and the succeeding component with latent roots greater than unity. The latent roots are called Eigen values. The component has the property of accounting for maximum variances. The PCA displays most of the original variability in a smaller number of dimensions, since it finds linear combination of a set of varieties that maximize the variation contained within them. Contributions of the different characters towards divergence are discussed from the latent vectors of the first two principal components. A PCA biplot shows both PC scores of samples and loadings of variables. It is a two-dimensional chart using the relative value of the traits. Genotype × trait biplot was constructed from a two-way matrix of twelve traits and 57 genotypes using STAR software (STAR 2014).

3.12.10. Drought susceptibility index (DSI)

Drought susceptibility index (DSI) was calculated for grain yield and other attributes over stress (Drought stress - water stress conditions) and non-stress environment (Normal - fully irrigated conditions) by using the formula as suggested by Fisher and Maurer (1978).

$$DSI = [1 - Y_D / Y_P] / D$$

Where;

Y_D = mean of the genotype in stress environment (drought).

Y_P = mean of the genotype under non-stress environment.

$D = 1 - [\text{mean } Y_D \text{ of all genotypes} / \text{mean } Y_P \text{ of all genotypes}]$.

The DSI value was used to characterize the relative tolerance of genotypes based on minimization of yield losses compared to normal environmental conditions.

3.13 Experiment-2. Molecular characterization and diversity analysis in barley using SSR markers

3.13.1 Genomic DNA Isolation

2-4 pieces of young leaves were collected in Eppendorf tube and were dried for 6-7 days in silica gel. The samples were grinded using mortar and pestle. 800 μ l of warmed (65°C) CTAB buffer was added to each tube and was vortexed thoroughly. Samples were incubated in water bath at 65°C for 45 minutes and at every 10 minutes they were mixed gently by inversion (400 μ l of 2% β - Mercaptoethanol was added to 200 ml of extraction buffer prior to warming). The tubes were taken out of the water bath and left at room temperature for 5 minutes. 600 μ l chloroform Isoamyl alcohol was added (24:1). The samples were mixed by gently inversion for about 2 minutes (100 times) until two layers' mix. Then the samples were centrifuged for 4000 rpm at room temperature for 20 mins. The aqua phase was removed with wide bore pipette. The aqua phase was transferred to clean 1.5 ml tube then 2/3 volume of Ethanol was added and mixed gently to precipitate the nucleic acids. At this stage the samples were stored in 4°C for overnight. After that the samples were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 20 minutes and the supernatant was discarded. Then the DNA was dried so that there was no ethanol. 500 μ l of washing buffer was added in each tube and the DNA was washed gently inversion. Again, the samples were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 20 mins, then the supernatant was removed and the tubes were left on bench for drying. 100 μ l double distilled water was added, the samples were left for dissolving. Finally, the samples were stored in 4°C for short term.

3.13.2 DNA Quantification

The Quality of the extracted DNA samples were also checked prior to PCR amplification through Quantification using a Thermo Scientific Nano DropTM 1000 Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).

3.13.3 PCR Amplification and Electrophoresis Separation

PCR amplifications were performed in 10 μ L tube using a Veriti Thermal Cycler (Appliedbiosystems, USA). 2 μ L of template DNA, and 8 μ L (0.5 μ L of Forward primer, 0.5 μ L of Reverse primer, 2 μ L of nuclease free water and 5 μ L of G2 Green Master Mix) of reaction mixture was added in each tube. The PCR amplification was as follows: one cycle of 94°C for 5 min; 35 cycles of 95°C for 0.5 min, 53 to 58°C (depending on the specific primers) for 0.5 min and extension for 0.5 min; and a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. Reaction products were mixed with one fifth volume of loading buffer (100 mM/L EDTA pH 8.0, 10 mM/L Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 5% Ficoll 400; 0.05% bromophenol, 0.05% xylene cyanol) and 2 μ L were loaded vertically, for electrophoresis 8% denaturing polyacrylamide gels in 1 \times TBE (90mM/L Tris borate pH 8.3, 2 mM/L EDTA) at 50 mA for 2 to 3 h (Wang *et al.* 2007). Gels were then silver stained and photographed using x-ray viewer.

Figure 4 Amplification of polymerase chain reaction

Figure 5 Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

3.13.4 Microsatellite/Simple Sequences Repeat (SSR) Markers

A total of 10 microsatellite (SSR) markers primer pairs (sigma Aldrich, Germany) covering all 10 chromosomes were selected for the genetic diversity analysis of the 39 Eastern European barley genotypes of as showed in the Table 2. These SSR primers with a distinct chromo some number were used for final Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification. The original sources, repeat motifs, primer sequences, expected length and chromosomal position and other relevant information to these markers is published on the Grain Genes website (<http://www.wheat.pw.usda.gov>). The chromosomal location, annealing temperature and primer sequences to SSR markers are shown in Table2.

Table 2. SSR Markers used for diversity analysis of barley

SSR Loci	Forward primer(5'–3')	Reverse primer (5'–3')	Annealing temperature (degree centigrade)
BMAC0577	TCATACAGAAGCCCACACAG	TGCATGTTTATTCTAGACAGG	53
BMAG808	TCATAGACTACGACGAAGATG	TCATAGACTACGACGAAGATG	54
WMS6F	CGTATCACCTCCTAGCTAAACTAG	AGCCTTATCATGACCCTACCTT	59
EBMAC624	AAAAGCATTCAACTTCATAAGA	CAACGCCATCACGTAATA	55
Bmag125	AATTAGCGAGAACAAAATCAC	AGATAACGATGCACCACC	55
Bmag006	TTAAACCCCCCTCTAG	TGCAGTTACTATCGCTGATTTAG	58
Scssr25691	ACGAGCTGATATCCCACGAG	TCCGAGCTTCTTATCTTTGG	54
Bmac0113	TCAAAGCCGGTCTAATGCT	GTGCAAAGAAAATGCACAGATAG	55
GMS027	CTTTTTCTTTGACGATGCACC	TGAGTTTGTGAGAACTGGATGG	54
Bmag337	ACAAAGAGGGAGTAGTACGC	GACCCATGATATATGAAGATCA	55

3.13.5 Molecular Statistical Analysis

Polymorphism information content (PIC) will be calculated using the following formula:

$$PIC= 1-\sum (P_i)^2$$

Note P_i depicts the proportion of samples carrying the i th allele.

Model-based clustering program STRUCTURE V2.3.4 (Pritchard *et al.* 2000) was employed to deduce the population structure of all the 36 accessions. Number of populations (K) was determined with a burn-in period of 10,000 and Markov Chain Monte Carlo of 100,000. Five independent runs were performed for each K varying from 1 to 10. In this model, several subpopulations (K) were assumed to be present, each of which was characterized by a set of allele frequencies for each locus. Individuals in the sample were assigned to subpopulations or jointly to two or more subpopulations if their genotypes were admixed. The model choice criterion to detect the most likely value of K was ΔK , an ad hoc quantity related to the second-order change in the log probability of data ($\ln P[D]$) with respect to the number of clusters inferred by Structure (Evanno *et al.* 2005). An individual was assigned to a subpopulation group if >80% of its genome fraction value was derived from that group. Most probable K -value was defined based on DK method (Evanno *et al.* 2005) by running the Structure Harvester software (Earl and von Holdt 2012). Every band was considered as a single locus. All the scorable Loci were considered for generation of bivariate 1-0 data matrix and for estimation of genetic diversity dendrogram was constructed using the software Metabo Analyst (Online Version) (Chong and Xia, 2018).

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment was conducted during the rabi season from December to April 2021-22. From this experiment, the outcome of the results and discussion of this research were obtained to analyze the variances, mean comparison, variability, heritability, genetic advance, correlation of phenotypic and genotypic condition, regression analysis, diversity analysis and principal component analysis morphologically and molecularly, population structure, Nei's similarity index of 123 barley genotypes that were collected from different European countries.

4.1 Analysis of variance among different morpho-physiological characters in barley

The analysis of variance for 13 morpho-physiological contributing characters of 123 barley genotypes were recorded and presented in table 3, table 4, and table 5 respectively. Analysis of variances showed highly significant differences among the varieties for all the characters including yield in both field and stressed environments (Table 4 and 5). Analysis of variance was also calculated combinedly with field and stressed environment (Table 3). The interaction effects between genotype x environment were also found significant for all the characters. In table 3, the sources of variation included genotype, replication, treatment, genotype-treatment interaction, error and CV%. The trends of variations among the genotypes were more or less similar in both environments, which could be observed by the CV values (Table 4 and 5). The analysis of variances revealed a highly significant difference among the genotypes for all traits viz. days to flowering (FL), plant height (cm) (PH), canopy temperature (CT), chlorophyll content (CC), number of grains per spike (GSP), thousand-grain weight (g) (TGW), days to maturity (DM), growth habit (GH), row type (RT), number of spike per plant (SP), Biological weight (BWT), tiller number per plant (NTP), yield per plant (g) (YP). The genotypes studied all were significant at 0.1% level of probability.

Angassa & Mohammad (2022) studied that the analysis of variance was performed for plant height, thousand-grain weight, number of grains per spike, number of spike per plant, days to maturity. Karkee *et al.* (2020) reported that the analysis of variance was performed for days to flowering and maturity, plant height, number of grains per spike, and 1000 kernel weight.

In table 4 and 5, it is shown that in the case of Treatment, all the traits show an identical difference at 0.1%, 1% level and 5% of significance. The same results have been found in the case of genotype-treatment interactions. This indicated that there were significant differences revealed among the treatments and also with genotypes.

Table 3. Analysis of variance of 13 important characters of barley genotypes under combined (drought stressed + control) conditions

Characters	Source of variation with Mean sum square					
	Replication (1 d.f.)	Genotype (122 d.f.)	Treatment (1 d.f.)	Genotype x Treatment (122 d.f.)	Error (245 d.f.)	Co- efficient of Variation (%)
Days to flowering	9.5 ^{NS}	149.6***	9700.4***	15.8***	7.0	3.66
Days to maturity	7.3 ^{NS}	147.8***	10198.4***	18.0***	7.1	2.39
Plant height (cm)	0.5 ^{NS}	355.7***	8704.4***	95.5***	1.8	1.64
Row Type	0.01 ^{NS}	9.81***	0.01 ^{NS}	0.01 ^{NS}	0.01	1.35
Growth Habit	0.34 ^{NS}	3.43***	78.88***	0.66***	0.18	13.28
Canopy Temperature(°C)	1.56 ^{NS}	5.29***	317.17***	7.09***	0.77	1.03
Chlorophyll Content	1.1 ^{NS}	26.4***	4932.1***	22.4***	1.2	2.49
Number of tiller/Plant	2.47 ^{NS}	107.49***	2298.85***	86.46***	2.11	7.69
Number of spike/Plant	2.61 ^{NS}	68.89***	770.83***	52.94***	3.37	14.19
Number of grain/ spike	0.63 ^{NS}	1569.11***	2658.75***	232.58***	3.20	6.03
Biological weight(g)	1.8 ^{NS}	409.9***	6592.9***	316.3***	8.8	10.02
Thousand grain weight(kg)	0.2 ^{NS}	223.2***	9952.9***	79.1***	9.3	8.45
Yield/Plant(g)	0.4 ^{NS}	185.1***	6338.3***	45.4***	0.6	7.43

Here, ***, ** and * indicates significance at 0.1%, 1% and 5% levels of probability, respectively. NS- not significant, df- indicates degrees of freedom

Table 4. Analysis of variance of 13 important characters of barley genotypes under control condition

Characters	Source of variation with mean sum square			
	Replication (1 d.f.)	Genotype (122 d.f.)	Error (122 d.f.)	Co-efficient of Variation (%)
Days to flowering	7.93 ^{NS}	80.38***	13.67	4.81
Days to maturity	6.83 ^{NS}	82.70***	13.78	3.19
Plant height (cm)	0.55 ^{NS}	237.13***	0.32	0.66
Row Type	0.01 ^{NS}	4.90***	0.01	9.05
Growth Habit	2.3***	2.29***	0.19	11.95
Canopy Temperature(°C)	10.73***	6.42***	0.33	0.68
Chlorophyll Content	8.04**	25.85***	1.13	2.28
Number of tiller/Plant	0.14 ^{NS}	99.13***	0.80	4.26
Number of spike/Plant	2.51 ^{NS}	68.98***	4.0	14.09
Number of grain/ spike	0.13 ^{NS}	786.79***	0.51	2.23
Biological weight(g)	7.49 ^{NS}	353.70***	13.25	10.92
Thousand grain weight(kg)	9.38 ^{NS}	170.76***	15.91	9.81
Yield/Plant(g)	0.02 ^{NS}	156.78***	0.44	4.80

Here, ***, ** and * indicates significance at 0.1%, 1% and 5% levels of probability, respectively. NS- not significant, df- indicates degrees of freedom

Table 5. Analysis of variance of 13 important characters of barley genotypes under drought stressed condition

Characters	Source of variation with mean sum square			
	Replication (1 d.f.)	Genotype (122 d.f.)	Error (245 d.f.)	Co-efficient of Variation (%)
Days to flowering	1.47 ^{NS}	84.55***	0.51	0.94
Days to maturity	1.47 ^{NS}	83.07***	0.51	0.62
Plant height (cm)	0.1 ^{NS}	214.08***	3.27	2.18
Row Type	0.01 ^{NS}	4.91***	0.00	2.75
Growth Habit	0.8*	1.79***	0.15	10.14
Canopy Temperature(°C)	2.28 ^{NS}	5.96***	1.12	1.25
Chlorophyll Content	1.91 ^{NS}	22.97***	1.14	2.26
Number of tiller/Plant	3.41 ^{NS}	94.82***	3.42	9.88
Number of spike/Plant	0.49 ^{NS}	52.85***	2.77	12.15
Number of grain/ spike	1.38 ^{NS}	1014.90***	5.90	7.76
Biological weight(g)	0.67 ^{NS}	372.49***	4.45	6.59
Thousand grain weight(kg)	10.61*	131.48***	2.68	3.93
Yield/Plant(g)	1.03 ^{NS}	73.67***	0.71	12.75

Here, ***, ** and * indicates significance at 0.1%, 1% and 5% levels of probability, respectively. NS- not significant, df- indicates degrees of freedom

4.2 Treatment comparisons of 123 barley genotypes on 13 morpho-physiological characters

The differences between the control condition and drought-stressed condition on different yield-related parameters were shown in box plots (Figure 6). Here, X-axis indicated two treatments i.e. control condition and drought stress condition against Y axis that was indicated in different characters.

In, Figure 6. plant height (PH) was higher in the control treatment condition than the of drought-stressed condition. Also, days to flowering (FL), growth habit (GH) and tiller number per plant (TP), were contained comparatively higher values in control conditions than drought stressed. This indicated that the time required for flowering, growth habit, total tiller number, and height most of the plant in optimum temperature were higher than drought stress (Figure 6). Days to flowering also considered as a decisive stage for improving yield and yield components (Cuesta-Marcos *et al.*, 2009; Pasam *et al.*, 2012). Fine adjustment of flowering date is important for understanding other developmental traits such as plant height, tillering and grain number (Alquadah *et al.*, 2016). Chlorophyll content (CC), days to maturity (DM), number of grains per spike (GSP), number of spike per plant (SP) were also contributed comparatively higher values in control temperature than drought stress condition (Figure 6.). But canopy temperature (CT) was higher in drought stressed condition than that of optimum condition. Some characteristics like leaf chlorophyll content and canopy temperature depression may be correlated with field performance, especially under drought stress (Jin *et al.*, 2012; Wu *et al.*, 2015). This indicated that high canopy temperature, low chlorophyll content, shorter life cycle and lower number of grains per spike were presented in drought stressed condition than control treatment condition (Figure 6.). Biological weight (BWT), thousand grain weight (TGW) and yield per plant (YP) were shown comparatively lower values in drought stress condition than control condition. This also revealed that biological weight, thousand-grain weight and total yield per plant were lower drought stress condition than control condition (Figure 10). Row type (RT) in both condition are same for their arrangement of spike. After all, control temperature condition was contributed higher performance than drought-stressed condition of 123 common genotypes in barley based on different yield contributing characters. Firoozabadi *et al.* (2022) also found the similar results.

a) PH

b) DF

c) GH

d) TP

Figure 6: Box plots showing the treatment comparison between control and drought stressed condition for plant height (PH), days to flowering (DH), growth habit (GH), tiller number per plant (TP) (Continued)

e) CHLC

f) SP

g) DM

h) GSP

Figure 6: Box plots showing the treatment comparison between control and drought stressed condition for chlorophyll content (CHLC), number of spike per plant (SP), days to maturity (DM) and number of grains per spike (GSP) (Continued)

i) TGW

j) RT

k) CT

l) BWT

m) YD

Figure 6: Box plots showing the treatment comparison between control and drought stressed condition for thousand grain weight (TGW), Row type (RT), canopy temperature (CT), biological weight (BWT), Yield per plant (YD)

4.3 Mean performances of 57 barley genotypes for morpho-physiological characters

The results of the mean comparison among the 123 barley genotypes of two treatment condition (control and drought) for different characters were presented below in table 3 to 5.

4.3.1 Days to flowering

In control treatment condition, the mean ranges of days to flowering were 54.0- 94.0 for control condition and 46.00-83.00 for drought stressed condition. The grand mean of this character was 74.09 for control and 68.06 for drought stressed condition. For control condition, the maximum days to flowering revealed for the genotype EEB82 (94.0) and EEB135 (91.0) followed by EEB166 (90.0) and EEB384 (88.0). The minimum number were revealed for the genotype EEB450 (59.5) followed by EEB313 (65.5). In case of drought stressed condition, the maximum days to flowering revealed for the genotype EEB83 (82.5) followed by EEB166 (80.5) and EEB255 (79.0). The minimum number were revealed for the genotype EEB119 (60.78) followed by EEB251 (61.0). Poudyal *et al.* (2019) observed the mean of days to flowering was 79 days. The days to flowering for normal sown condition was about 83 days and it was significantly higher than days to flowering for late sown condition (60 days).

4.3.2 Canopy temperature

Canopy temperature is an important physiological character. It helps to identify heat tolerant genotypes of barley. Lower canopy temperature in drought-stressed crop plants indicates the best capacity of absorbing soil moisture and maintaining the water requirement by various plant adaptive traits. In control treatment condition, the mean values of canopy temperature having a range 80.03-92.97 with mean value 84.43. The highest canopy temperature was exhibited in the genotype EEB382 (92.87). The lowest canopy temperature revealed for the genotype EEB166 (81.15) for control temperature condition. In case of drought stressed condition, the mean values of canopy temperature having a range 82.1-92.67 with mean value 86.04. The highest canopy temperature was exhibited in the genotype EEB169 (92.05). The lowest canopy temperature revealed for the genotype EEB150 (82.63) for drought stressed condition.

Kumar *et al.* (2018) showed that canopy temperature (19.6-43.4 and 17.1-46.8 °C), at the time of anthesis and 15 days after anthesis, respectively, showed significant variation among

the genotypes for all the characters studied. Hence, this physiological trait could be considered as suitable selection criteria for the development of high yielding barley varieties.

4.3.3 Chlorophyll content

Chlorophyll plays a vital role for photosynthesis. Photosynthesis rate depends on chlorophyll content (CC). The higher chlorophyll content, the more amounts of food storage and it will supply more energy. In control treatment condition, the mean values of chlorophyll content giving a range 37.73- 59.30 with mean value 46.56. The maximum chlorophyll content was revealed for the genotype EEB384 (58.6) and the minimum chlorophyll content exhibited in genotype EEB423 (39.25). In drought stressed condition, the mean values of chlorophyll content giving a range 32.26-52.30 with mean value 40.23. The maximum chlorophyll content was revealed for the genotype EEB166 (50.42) and the minimum chlorophyll content exhibited in genotype EEB443 (32.7). Sid`ko *et al.* (2016) showed that the high efficiency of chlorophyll photosynthetic potential in combination with traditional spectrophotometric measurements to assess chlorophyll content of crops.

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (Contd.)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Flowering		Canopy Temperature		Cholophyll Content	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
1	BARI5	63j-m	50A	80.22D	89.67a-f	41.45g-m	43.13c-u
2	BARI7	65i-m	53.5z	85.35c-t	85.57d-n	44.05x-l	43.9b-q
3	BARI8	57m	46B	85.15d-w	83.42k-n	38.75m	40.28h-J
4	BARI9	58.5lm	50A	86.72b-h	84.13h-n	40.25k-m	42.15d-x
5	EEB11	74b-l	65r-u	84.27h-y	85.03d-n	44.83u-k	47.18a-c
6	EEB17	82.5a-g	71j-n	83.6n-B	83.12mn	43.62y-l	33.83N-P
7	EEB18	80.5a-i	68.5m-q	85.33c-u	84.98e-n	43.98x-l	42.05d-y
8	EEB23	79.5a-j	68.5m-q	83.38o-C	86.52b-n	42.85d-m	37.28y-P
9	EEB28	76b-k	69m-p	83.18o-C	84.9f-n	45.33o-j	42.42c-w
10	EEB32	71.5b-m	65.5q-u	83.53n-C	87.55a-m	44.17w-k	37.02B-P
11	EEB35	74b-l	65r-u	83.48n-C	85.15d-n	48.15g-a	41.35d-C
12	EEB38	75b-m	65.5q-u	84.08i-j	83.92i-n	48.15g-a	40.3h-I
13	EEB40	76b-l	65.5q-u	83.1p-C	83.4k-n	52.3b-h	39.67m-L
14	EEB41	80.5b-k	67.5o-s	86.32b-m	86.85b-n	46.35i-f	35.93g-P
15	EEB42	73.5a-i	78.5b-e	84.38h-y	88.72a-h	41.22h-m	36.26E-P
16	EEB43	75b-m	65r-u	85.35c-t	87.68a-m	48.58f-x	39.23q-L
17	EEB47	77.5b-l	66.5p-t	83.45n-C	85.9d-n	46.07m-g	40.58g-H
18	EEB50	76a-j	66.5p-t	82.72v-D	84.65g-n	45.98n-h	33.48OP
19	EEB53	76.5b-k	68n-r	85.23c-v	86.6b-n	48.3g-z	44.53b-l
20	EEB60	81.5b-j	72.5h-l	84.22h-y	86.03d-n	45.28p-j	45.7a-f
21	EEB69	85.5a-i	72.5h-l	84.12h-y	85.83g-n	42.83d-m	38.17v-O
22	EEB79	87a-e	72.5h-l	84.6g-y	86.15b-n	45.18q-j	44.85b-i
23	EEB81	75ab	73g-k	83.08p-C	85.48d-n	47.03j-e	44.1b-p
24	EEB82	94b-l	67.5o-s	87.33b-e	87.42d-n	46.98j-e	40.33h-I
25	EEB83	77a	82.5a	84.28h-y	85.95c-n	44.85t-k	42.3d-w
26	EEB87	82.5b-j	68.5m-q	87.37b-e	85.63d-n	48.38g-y	46.18a-d
27	EEB88	75.5a-g	73.5f-j	85.28c-v	84.95a-n	55.65a-c	41.43d-C
28	EEB90	68b-k	68.5m-q	85.57b-q	86.92d-n	45.17q-j	38.9r-L
29	EEB91	76f-m	64.5s-v	84j-A	86.38d-n	44.52v-a	44.7b-k
30	EEB92	82b-k	69.5i-p	84.45h-y	85.48e-n	54.85a-d	42.48c-w
31	EEB107	79a-h	76.5c-f	82.37x-C	84.78b-n	51.73b-j	40.05i-K
32	EEB111	81.5a-j	67.5o-s	82.7v-D	86.1b-n	45.6n-i	39.62n-L
33	EEB112	75.5a-i	67.5o-s	83.17o-C	85.6d-n	49.77e-s	41.82d-B
34	EEB114	76.5b-k	66.5p-t	83.82k-A	86.9g-n	45.93n-h	38.17v-O
35	EEB116	77.5b-j	66.5p-t	84.65f-y	86.92d-n	45.33o-j	37.87w-O
36	EEB117	77.5a-j	66.5p-t	82.3x-D	86.35d-n	47.4j-e	40.67g-G
37	EEB119	76.5a-j	59.5xy	84.43r-C	86.15b-n	46.72i-e	43.28c-T
38	EEB122	76.5b-j	68.5m-q	83.77s-C	88.07b-n	49.65e-t	41.03e-E
39	EEB129	79b-j	67.5o-s	83.08n-B	87b-n	46.72i-e	39.72l-L

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (Contd.)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Flowering		Canopy Temperature		Chlorophyll Content	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
40	EEB131	74.5a-j	69.5I-p	84.85h-y	88.63c-n	47.83h-b	35.67I-P
41	EEB134	73.5b-l	68.5m-q	84.3x-D	87.13a-l	46.12m-g	40.95f-F
42	EEB135	91b-m	65.5q-u	82.27n-C	86.52b-n	50.13d-o	39.18q-L
43	EEB136	72.5ab	74f-j	82.93y-D	88.12a-i	43.28b-m	38.5t-N
44	EEB140	76b-m	64.5s-v	82.88o-C	85.05b-n	51.73b-j	39.9j-K
45	EEB142	75b-k	67.5o-s	83.62z-D	85.13b-n	52.33b-h	35.43K-P
46	EEB145	74.5b-l	68.5m-q	84.44B-D	86.18a-k	48.3g-z	41.48d-C
47	EEB148	77b-l	69.5I-p	82.4o-C	83.28d-n	48.4f-y	37.3y-P
48	EEB150	70b-j	73g-k	83.45k-A	82.63d-n	48.65f-x	41.42d-C
49	EEB152	82.5c-m	64.5s-v	82.18CD	84c-n	45.75n-i	40.6g-H
50	EEB161	68.5a-g	72.5h-l	83.23A-D	86.65l-n	45.2q-j	43.08c-u
51	EEB163	85.5f-m	65.5q-u	81.48x-D	85.55n	45.23q-j	45.03b-h
52	EEB166	90a-e	80.5ab	81.15u-D	87.5h-n	50.08d-p	50.42a
53	EEB168	78ab	76d-g	83.15s-C	87.5b-n	46.58i-e	40.35h-I
54	EEB169	79a-j	68.5m-q	83.92o-C	92.05d-n	45.22q-j	43.37c-s
55	EEB173	81a-j	78.5b-e	80.95j-A	91.11a-m	49.13e-v	41.98d-z
56	EEB203	84a-i	68.5m-q	81.45o-C	85.35a-m	41.1i-m	40.98e-F
57	EEB204	78.5a-f	68.5m-q	82.25n-B	87.78a	51.62b-k	43.55c-r
58	EEB208	75a-j	67.5o-s	82.74h-y	84.73ab	45.4n-j	39.87k-K
59	EEB212	81b-l	72.5h-l	82.87b-r	86.34d-n	49.93e-r	41.53d-C
60	EEB227	82a-i	68.5m-q	83.33o-C	85.68a-m	49.77e-s	40.87f-F
61	EEB251	88.5a-h	59.5xy	84g-y	87.77g-n	44.78u-k	39.82l-K
62	EEB254	86.5ab	74.5f-i	83.38h-y	87b-n	49.97e-q	41.77d-B
63	EEB255	80.5a-c	79b-d	83.62q-C	88.48d-n	48.53f-x	36.87C-P
64	EEB265	68.5a-i	72.5h-l	84.5x-D	88.7a-m	46.9k-e	39r-L
65	EEB266	82.5f-m	61w-y	85.5t-D	87.25b-m	52.27b-i	44.53b-l
66	EEB267	71a-g	78.5b-e	83.23x-D	86a-j	45.72n-i	48.48ab
67	EEB290	79.5b-m	64.5s-v	84.6o-C	88.93a-i	47.17j-e	41.05e-E
68	EEB292	76a-j	73.5f-j	84.2w-D	87.03b-n	45.3p-j	44.48b-m
69	EEB295	76b-k	69.5I-p	83.01h-y	86.58d-n	43.1b-m	39.9j-K
70	EEB296	84.5b-k	69.5I-p	82.48o-C	87.02a-g	44.03x-l	35.65I-P
71	EEB297	80a-f	73.5f-j	82.77w-D	85.48b-n	47.68h-c	37B-p
72	EEB298	86a-i	58.5y	82.35h-y	86.57b-n	44.22w-k	35.8H-P
73	EEB301	82.5a-d	78.5b-e	83.38b-k	85.79b-n	53.77b-e	35.45J-P
74	EEB308	76.5a-g	68.5m-q	83.2b-p	87.8d-n	47.47i-e	38.75r-M
75	EEB309	78b-j	68.5m-q	84.13f-y	84.92b-n	43.9x-l	45.68a-f
76	EEB312	82a-j	65.5q-u	83.42n-C	84.95d-n	50.93c-l	39.02r-L
77	EEB313	65.5a-h	75.5e-h	82.55b-f	84.22a-m	48.96e-w	40.9f-F
78	EEB318	78h-m	58.5y	84.13n-C	85.95e-n	50.82d-m	37.85w-O

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (Contd.)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Flowering		Canopy Temperature		Chlorophyll Content	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
79	EEB325	68a-j	69.5i-p	86.42o-C	84.22e-n	52.88b-g	37B-P
80	EEB335	73f-m	60xy	85.68h-y	85.78g-n	49.88e-r	40.75g-G
81	EEB336	68b-m	64.5s-v	84.72b-k	86.85d-n	44.75u-k	38.18v-O
82	EEB337	78.5f-m	61w-y	83.47b-p	84.2g-n	43.38a-m	38.53s-N
83	EEB343	69a-j	69m-p	87.22f-y	83.42d-n	46.82k-m	37.98w-O
84	EEB344	81e-m	60.5w-y	83.45n-C	87.02b-n	46.8i-e	39.6n-L
85	EEB345	80.5a-i	71j-n	87.25b-f	85.1g-n	45.57n-i	44.42b-n
86	EEB346	79a-i	71.5i-m	86.03n-C	84.25k-n	51.1c-l	41.15e-C
87	EEB347	69.5a-j	70k-o	86.37b-f	85.35b-n	47.9h-b	38.7s-M
88	EEB352	78d-m	60xy	86.32b-m	85.28d-n	47.63h-d	40.63g-H
89	EEB353	68a-j	66.5p-t	88.03b-l	89.82g-n	41.53g-m	38.1w-O
90	EEB354	67f-m	59.5xy	87.51b-m	88.63d-n	41.35g-m	38.6s-N
91	EEB355	76.5g-m	59.5xy	87.71b	86.25d-n	45.95n-h	38.43u-N
92	EEB358	76b-j	73g-k	84.48b-d	84.7a-d	48.37g-y	37.05A-P
93	EEB362	77b-k	74.5f-i	84.13b-d	90.9a-i	55.95ab	37.13z-P
94	EEB363	68.5b-j	73g-k	87.42h-y	88.18c-n	44.48v-k	34.9L-P
95	EEB366	83f-m	61.5v-y	87.43h-y	83.52g-n	45.3p-j	35.95G-P
96	EEB370	75.5a-g	78.5b-e	82.39b-e	84.79a-c	45.05s-k	36.88C-P
97	EEB371	70.5b-k	69m-p	87.18b-e	86.1a-k	49.52e-u	45.81a-e
98	EEB375	80.5b-m	62.5u-x	84.21x-D	86.25k-n	50.2d-n	50.38a
99	EEB376	73.5a-i	61.5v-y	83.42b-g	86.1g-n	47.87h-b	45.35b-g
100	EEB377	72b-m	65.5q-u	84.43h-y	85.18t-n	42.77e-m	37.88w-O
101	EEB380	70.5b-m	65.5q-u	86.62b-i	83.97c-n	41.62f-m	36.18F-P
102	EEB382	74b-l	68.5m-q	92.87a	83.68d-n	53.2b-f	38.12w-O
103	EEB384	88ab	78.5b-e	84.13h-y	84.62d-n	58.6a	38.34u-N
104	EEB385	75b-l	67.5o-s	85.11d-w	84.2h-n	41.38g-m	44.22b-o
105	EEB394	86a-d	71.5i-m	85.55b-q	84.73k-n	46.77i-e	36.48D-P
106	EEB400	73.5b-m	74f-j	87.82bc	85.73g-n	42.88c-m	38.52t-N
107	EEB401	83.5a-g	61.5v-y	85.68b-p	83.77g-n	45.23q-j	38.42u-N
108	EEB407	82a-h	72.5h-l	85.33c-s	84.16g-n	45.8n-i	42.97c-v
109	EEB408	75b-l	59.5xy	83.63n-B	85.43d-n	43.18b-m	40.47h-I
110	EEB409	74b-l	61.5v-y	84.83e-x	85.65d-n	40.75j-m	41.63d-C
111	EEB417	74.5b-l	63.5t-w	86.55b-j	85.3d-n	44.17w-k	42.05d-Y
112	EEB418	87.5ab	79.5a-c	86.57b-j	84.63g-n	42.92c-m	41.87d-A
113	EEB423	77.5a-j	74f-j	86.42b-k	89.7a-e	39.25lm	35.33K-P
114	EEB431	74.5b-l	68n-r	85.31c-v	86.7b-n	43.53z-m	37.32x-P
115	EEB433	74.5b-l	67o-s	84.85e-x	84.73g-n	45.92n-h	37.7w-O
116	EEB434	76.5b-j	67o-s	85.72b-o	84.67g-n	44.87t-k	38.92r-L
117	EEB436	79a-j	67o-s	83.72m-B	84.6g-n	45.13r-j	42.17d-w

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (Contd.)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Flowering		Canopy Temperature		Chloophyll Content	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
118	EEB438	87ab	78b-e	86.6b-j	83.67k-n	43.31b-m	44.73b-j
119	EEB439	77b-j	68n-r	85.12d-w	86.92b-n	44.45v-k	39.4o-l
120	EEB440	77.5a-j	69m-p	84.57h-y	86.83b-n	46.97j-e	38.23v-o
121	EEB443	79.5a-j	73g-k	85.35c-t	84.52g-n	41.62f-m	32.7P
122	EEB444	83.5a-g	78b-e	85.52b-r	86.21c-n	44.63v-k	33.93m-P
123	EEB450	59.5k-m	50A	84.03i-A	86.87b-n	44.18w-k	39.3p-L
	Mean	74.09	68.06	84.43	86.04	46.56	40.23
	Range	57.0-94.0	46.00-83.00	80.03-92.97	82.1-92.67	37.73-59.30	32.26-51.30
	SE(±)	2.61	0.5	0.41	0.75	0.75	0.76

4.3.4. Days to maturity

In control treatment condition, the mean values of days to maturity having a range 92-133 with mean value 115.99. The maximum days required for maturity was exhibited in the genotype EEB83 (133). The minimum days required for maturity was revealed for the genotype EEB450 (98.5). In drought stressed condition, the mean values of days to maturity having a range 85.0-122.0 with mean value 106.89. The maximum days required for maturity was exhibited in the genotype EEB83 (121.5), EEB255 (119.5) etc. The minimum days required for maturity was revealed for the genotype EEB 450 (89.0) etc.

Adhikari *et al.* (2018) observed that days to 90% maturity from days to sowing ranged from 125.3 to 133 days. Early maturing types can be selected as an early type variety or can be used as parent to develop early maturing cultivars.

4.3.5 Number of grains per spike

In control treatment condition, the number of grains per spike revealed the ranges of mean were 10.00 -94.00 with mean value 31.96. The maximum number of grains per spike were revealed for the genotype EEB 450 (93.67) followed by EEB114 (90.67) and the minimum number of grains per spike were revealed for the genotype EEB136 (11.5) followed by EEB168 (12.25), EEB265 (12.33). In drought stressed condition, the number of grains per spike revealed the ranges of mean were 2.00- 84.00 with mean value 22.5. The maximum number of grains per spike were revealed for the genotype EEB129 (86.0) followed by EEB069 (27.78) etc. and the minimum number of grains per spike were revealed for the genotype EEB163 (4.83), EEB255 (5.67) followed by EEB165 (5.83) etc.

Ahmadizadeh *et al.* (2013) reported that the range of number of grains per spike had between 49.73 (line 14) to 29.63 (line 15) in barely genotypes. Total means of number of grain per spike was 41.11 in 20 lines studied.

4.3.6 Tiller number per plant

In control treatment condition, the tiller number per plant were exhibited the ranges of mean 7.67-44.00 with mean value 21.04. Maximum tiller number per plant were EEB382 (43.5) followed by EEB117 (40.5). The minimum tiller number per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB129 (11.17), EEB140 (12.92), EEB255 (13.5) etc. In drought stressed condition, the tiller number per plant were exhibited the ranges of mean 1.67- 33.67 with mean value 16.72. Maximum tiller number per plant were EEB112 (33.67) followed by

EEB382 (32.00). The minimum tiller number per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB140(4.0), EEB301 (4) followed by EEB431 (5) etc.

Vinesh *et al.* (2018) observed the high mean number of tillers per unit area and low variance for number of tillers could be used in selecting varieties with consistently high yield at varying environments.

4.3.7 Plant height

In control treatment condition, the mean ranges of plant height were 52.33- 109.67 cm with a mean value of 85.45 cm. The maximum plant height was exhibited in genotype EEB431 (109) followed by EEB433 (105.17). The minimum number of genotypes were exhibited in genotypes EEB203 (52.92) etc. In drought stressed condition, the mean ranges of plant height were 34- 97.67 cm with a mean value of 77.06cm. The maximum plant height was exhibited in genotype EEB18 (96.33) followed by EEB375 (95.17) and the minimum number of genotypes were exhibited in genotypes EEB83 (37).

Mirosavljević *et al.* (2015) found the highest average plant height in genotype G12 and the lowest average plant height in genotype G17.

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Maturity		No. of grain per spike		No. of Tillers per Plant		Growth Habit	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
1.	BARI5	102m-p	89x	94a	90ab	18.83A-J	15.67m-J	5a	4a
2.	BARI7	104l-p	92.5w	82e	78cd	18.83A-J	11.17z-O	5a	4a
3.	BARI8	96p	85y	86d	93.67a	18.5B-L	10.83A-P	5a	4a
4.	BARI9	97.5op	89x	88cd	86a-c	11.5W-Z	12.83t-N	5a	4a
5.	EEB11	113c-o	104n-q	21.5J-Q	23.67h-q	19.83y-I	24.5c-k	5a	4a
6.	EEB17	121.5a-j	110h-k	22.5H-O	23.33h-q	12.83R-Y	24d-m	4a-c	3a-c
7.	EEB18	119.5a-l	107.5j-m	43.5j	73de	12.92R-Y	14p-L	3b-e	2b-e
8.	EEB23	118.5a-m	107.5j-m	27.5s-B	24.67h-o	24o-x	21f-t	4a-c	4a
9.	EEB28	115b-n	108j-l	28.83p-x	27.33h-j	20x-H	16l-I	4a-c	3a-c
10.	EEB32	109.5f-p	104.5m-q	34.17k-m	24.17h-p	25.5k-t	8.17I-P	5a	4a
11.	EEB35	113c-o	104n-q	30.67n-s	26.5h-k	29.5e-k	13t-M	4a-c	4a
12.	EEB38	111d-p	104.5m-q	28.83p-x	24.67h-o	20.5w-F	11.17z-O	5a	3a-c
13.	EEB40	114c-o	104.5m-q	29.67o-u	25.83h-l	23.5q-z	12.33u-O	4a-c	4a
14.	EEB41	115b-n	106.5l-o	27.17t-B	22.5h-r	40.17ab	16.3k-I	4a-c	3a-c
15.	EEB42	119.5a-l	117.5b-d	27t-C	21.5h-s	24.83m-v	6.17L-P	4a-c	3a-c
16.	EEB43	112.5d-p	104n-q	29.17o-v	28.83h	29e-l	15o-K	4.5ab	4a
17.	EEB47	114c-o	105.5l-p	25.67x-H	21.33h-s	27g-q	12.83t-N	4.5ab	4a
18.	EEB50	116.5a-m	105.5l-p	27.67s-A	20.5h-u	22.83r-A	13.33s-N	4a-c	4a
19.	EEB53	115b-n	107k-n	32.33m-o	29.17h	31.5ef	20.17g-w	3b-e	3a-c
20.	EEB60	115.5b-m	111.5g-i	18.5Q-U	13.75o-A	28.17f-n	32.83bc	4a-c	2b-e
21.	EEB69	120.5a-l	111.5g-i	60g	0CD	20.33w-G	25.33c-i	4a-c	2b-e
22.	EEB79	124.5a-h	111.5g-i	17.25S-V	15.83k-A	15.92I-U	29.25b-f	2d-f	2b-e
23.	EEB81	126a-f	112f-h	2.5Z	19.17h-v	M-Y	25c-j	3b-e	2b-e
24.	EEB82	114c-o	106.5l-o	25.5y-H	14.5m-A	23.83o-y	22.33f-p	4a-c	2b-e
25.	EEB83	133a	121.5a	14.5V-X	6w-D	13.08Q-Y	20g-w	1f	1.5c-e
26.	EEB87	116b-m	107.5j-m	20.17M-T	19.67h-u	26i-s	23.67d-n	3b-e	2b-e
27.	EEB88	121.5a-j	112.5e-h	22I-P	25.5h-m	19.83y-I	15.5n-J	3b-e	2b-e
28.	EEB90	114.5b-n	107.5j-m	31m-r	22.67h-q	14.83J-X	11.83w-O	5a	4a
29.	EEB91	107i-p	103.5o-r	87d	73de	14.83J-X	13.83q-M	5a	4a
30.	EEB92	115b-n	108.5i-l	19.5O-T	14.17n-A	15.83I-V	7.08K-P	4a-c	3a-c
31.	EEB107	121a-j	115.5c-e	31m-r	15I-A	12.667S-Y	17.17i-G	4a-c	2b-e
32.	EEB111	118a-e	106.5l-o	30n-t	23.17h-q	20.5w-F	25.83c-h	3b-e	3.5ab
33.	EEB112	120.5a-k	106.5l-o	26.67u-E	24.33h-p	36.83bc	41.33a	2d-f	3a-c
34.	EEB114	114.5b-n	105.5l-p	90.67bc	89a-c	17.67C-N	16.33k-I	4a-c	3.5ab
35.	EEB116	115.5b-n	105.5l-p	37k	28.33hi	17.33D-O	21f-t	4a-c	4a
36.	EEB117	116.5ab	105.5l-p	29.67o-u	17.33i-v	40.5ab	8I-P	3b-e	4a
37.	EEB119	116.5a-c	98.5tu	29.17o-v	23.17h-q	14M-Y	14.67o-K	3b-e	3a-c
38.	EEB122	115.5a-d	107.5j-m	20.83K-R	25.5h-m	16.17H-U	29.33b-f	5a	3a-c
39.	EEB129	115.5a-d	106.5l-o	82e	86a-c	11.17X-Z	10.17C-P	4a-c	3a-c

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Maturity		No. of grain per spike		No. of Tillers per Plant		Growth Habit	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
40.	EEB131	118a-e	108.5i-l	18R-U	5.67y-D	14.67K-Y	20.42g-v	3b-e	2b-e
41.	EEB134	113.5a-f	107.5j-m	21.67J-Q	22h-s	18.67B-K	31b-e	4a-c	4a
42.	EEB135	112.5a-f	104.5m-q	19.67N-T	25.33h-m	20.17w-H	21.83f-r	5a	4a
43.	EEB136	131a-g	113o-r	11.5X	14.83I-A	18.5B-L	11.5x-O	2d-f	3a-c
44.	EEB140	111.5a-g	103.5l-o	51i	86a-c	12.92R-Y	5.5M-P	5a	4a
45.	EEB142	115a-h	106.5j-m	28.67p-y	22.67h-q	28.67e-m	7.33J-P	5a	4a
46.	EEB145	114a-i	107.5i-l	86d	41g	22.92r-z	8.5H-P	5a	3a-c
47.	EEB148	113.5a-i	108.5f-h	28.83333p-x	11s-C	23.33q-z	24.17d-l	4.5ab	3a-c
48.	EEB150	116a-j	112o-r	30.5n-s	18.33h-v	26.5h-s	24d-m	4.5ab	4a
49.	EEB152	109.5a-j	103.5g-i	78f	83a-d	16.33G-T	11.33y-O	4.5ab	4a
50.	EEB161	121.5a-j	111.5m-q	26.83333t-D	16.25k-y	20.67w-F	17.42i-F	2.5c-f	2b-e
51.	EEB163	107.5a-j	104.5ab	87.5cd	4.83A-D	19.67z-I	18.5h-C	4.5ab	3a-c
52.	EEB166	124.5a-j	119.5d-f	17.5S-V	13q-B	29.17e-k	20.67g-u	2.5c-f	1de
53.	EEB168	129.5a-k	115j-m	12.25W-X	15.75k-A	32.25d-e	9.67F-P	1.5ef	1de
54.	EEB169	117a-k	107.5b-d	15.33U-W	24.83h-n	11.67W-Z	34.83ab	1.5ef	2b-e
55.	EEB173	118a-k	117.5j-m	25.17z-I	22h-s	29.67e-j	27.75b-g	2d-f	1de
56.	EEB203	120a-k	107.5j-m	13.5WX	55f	12.17U-Y	17.17i-G	3b-e	1de
57.	EEB204	123a-l	107.5l-o	3.5YZ	8.25v-D	17.5D-O	19.83g-x	2d-f	2b-e
58.	EEB208	117.5a-l	106.5g-i	23.67D-K	88a-c	23.17q-z	24d-m	3b-e	2b-e
59.	EEB212	114a-l	111.5j-m	17.5S-V	21.28h-s	28.67e-m	10.08D-P	2.5c-f	2b-e
60.	EEB227	120a-l	107.5tu	56.5h	65ef	11.67W-Z	17.67h-F	3b-e	2b-e
61.	EEB251	121a-l	98.5e-g	24.5A-J	18.5h-v	15.83I-V	14.67o-K	3b-e	3a-c
62.	EEB254	127.5a-l	113.5b-d	M-T	20.5h-u	11.83V-Z	2.5P	1f	1de
63.	EEB255	125.5a-l	118g-i	13.33WX	5.83x-D	13.5O-Y	22.33f-p	2.5c-f	2b-e
64.	EEB265	119.5a-l	111.5s-u	12.33WX	5z-D	18.83A-J	19.33h-z	3b-e	2.5a-d
65.	EEB266	107.5a-m	100b-d	27.17t-B	28.33hi	17.17D-P	13.33s-N	3b-e	3.5ab
66.	EEB267	121.5a-m	117.5o-r	25.83w-G	10.17t-C	13.17P-Y	12.33u-O	3.5a-d	2b-e
67.	EEB290	110a-m	103.5e-h	28.08r-z	21h-t	25.67j-t	13.67q-M	5a	4a
68.	EEB292	118.5a-m	112.5i-l	25.5y-H	23.33h-q	18C-M	18.5h-C	4a-c	3a-c
69.	EEB295	115a-m	108.5i-l	28.5p-y	25h-n	20.83v-E	15.5n-J	3.5a-d	3a-c
70.	EEB296	115a-m	108.5e-h	30.67n-s	21.67h-s	28.5e-m	23.67d-n	4a-c	3.5ab
71.	EEB297	123.5a-m	112.5vw	22.83G-N	20h-u	17.83C-N	12.17v-O	3.5a-d	2b-e
72.	EEB298	119a-m	94.5j-m	27.83r-z	11.5r-B	12.5T-Y	8.33H-P	4.5ab	3a-c
73.	EEB301	125a-m	107.5j-m	28.67p-y	14.83I-A	17D-Q	4.25OP	2.5c-f	1.5c-e
74.	EEB308	121.5a-m	107.5j-m	31m-r	26.17h-k	28.17f-n	17.5h-K	3b-e	2.5a-d
75.	EEB309	115.5a-m	107.5m-q	30.5n-s	24h-q	17.5D-O	18.5h-C	2.5c-f	2b-e
76.	EEB312	117a-m	104.5m-q	31.33m-q	18.83h-v	25I-u	17.67h-F	3.5a-d	1.5c-e
77.	EEB313	121a-m	104.5uv	27.08t-B	24.25h-p	21.67t-C	12w-O	2.5c-f	2b-e
78.	EEB318	104.5a-m	97.5i-l	25.83w-G	22.67h-q	20.67w-F	24.5c-k	4a-c	1.5c-e

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Maturity		No. of grain per spike		No. of Tillers per Plant		Growth Habit	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
79.	EEB325	117a-m	108.5tu	31.5m-q	22.17h-r	18.83A-J	21.67f-s	2d-f	2.5a-d
80.	EEB335	107a-m	99o-r	45.67j	22.83h-q	11.67W-Z	16l-I	2.5c-f	3.5ab
81.	EEB336	112a-m	103.5s-u	54hi	90ab	16.67F-S	12w-O	4.5ab	3.5ab
82.	EEB337	107a-m	100j-l	19P-T	18.83h-v	25.67j-t	25.83c-h	5a	4a
83.	EEB343	117.5b-m	108s-u	26.5u-E	23.67h-q	18.5B-L	22f-q	4.5ab	a
84.	EEB344	108b-m	99.5h-k	31.67m-p	17.17j-v	16.67F-S	21.17f-t	5a	3.5ab
85.	EEB345	120b-m	110g-j	24.5A-J	24.83h-n	12.17U-Y	22.83e-o	4.5ab	2b-e
86.	EEB346	119.5b-m	110.5h-k	22I-P	19.33h-u	21u-D	10.33B-P	2.5c-f	1.5c-e
87.	EEB347	118b-m	110tu	31.67m-p	25.5h-m	17.5D-O	13.17t-N	2.5c-f	1.5c-e
88.	EEB352	108.5b-m	99l-p	26.67u-E	25h-n	15.83I-V	14.83o-K	3b-e	4a
89.	EEB353	117.5b-n	105.5tu	31.58m-p	23.33h-q	22.5s-B	21.83f-r	4.5ab	3a-c
90.	EEB354	107b-n	98.5tu	26.17v-F	13.5p-A	26.67h-r	10.83A-P	4a-c	3.5ab
91.	EEB355	106b-n	98.5f-h	30.5n-s	16.83j-x	26i-s	8.17I-P	4.5ab	3.5ab
92.	EEB358	115.5b-n	112e-g	35.67KI	19.5h-u	27.83f-o	9.83E-P	4.5ab	3a-c
93.	EEB362	115b-n	113.5f-h	13.5WX	16k-z	15.5J-W	4OP	3.5a-d	3a-c
94.	EEB363	116b-n	112r-u	26.5u-E	16.5j-y	25.67j-t	22f-q	2.5c-f	2.5a-d
95.	EEB366	107.5c-o	100.5b-d	23.67D-K	17.33i-v	19.67z-I	25.83c-h	3.5a-d	3.5ab
96.	EEB370	122c-o	117.5j-l	5.75Y	19.92h-u	35.83cd	31.58b-d	4a-c	3a-c
97.	EEB371	114.5c-o	108q-t	33I-n	22.83h-q	30.17e-h	14.5o-L	1.5ef	2.5a-d
98.	EEB375	109.5c-o	101.5r-u	30.67n-s	16.58j-y	14.5L-Y	18.17h-E	4.5ab	3.5ab
99.	EEB376	120c-o	100.5m-q	23.67D-K	17.5i-v	15.33J-W	8.83G-P	4.5ab	3a-c
100.	EEB377	112.5c-o	104.5m-q	28r-z	21h-t	27.17g-q	13.17t-N	3.5a-d	4a
101.	EEB380	109.5c-o	104.5m-q	32.33m-o	21.5h-s	24.83m-v	14p-L	4.5ab	3.5ab
102.	EEB382	113c-o	107.5j-m	25.17z-I	18.5h-v	43.5a	17i-G	4.5ab	2b-e
103.	EEB384	127c-o	117.5b-d	28.33q-z	13.33p-A	31e-g	20.17g-w	3.5a-d	2.5a-d
104.	EEB385	114c-o	106.5l-o	27.66667s-A	20.17Hh-u	26.17h-s	14.83o-K	3.5a-d	2.5a-d
105.	EEB394	125c-o	110.5g-j	23.83C-K	13.33p-A	27.67f-p	21.67f-s	4a-c	1.5c-e
106.	EEB400	112.5d-p	113e-h	13.5WX	2.27B-D	7.83Z	15o-K	2d-f	0.5e
107.	EEB401	122.5d-p	100.5r-u	62g	82b-d	14.67K-Y	16.17k-I	5a	3.5ab
108.	EEB407	121d-p	111.5g-i	17T-V	16.92j-w	13.92N-Y	9.92E-P	3b-e	2.5a-d
109.	EEB408	114e-p	98.5tu	22.17I-P	15.67k-A	19.67z-I	16.67j-H	3b-e	3.5ab
110.	EEB409	113f-p	100.5r-u	20.33L-S	18.17h-v	26i-s	18.33H-D	4a-c	2.5a-d
111.	EEB417	113.5f-p	102.5p-s	60.67g	54.5f	14.5L-Y	17.33i-F	4a-c	2b-e
112.	EEB418	126.5f-p	118.5a-c	17.5S-V	9.5u-C	27.83f-o	16l-I	2d-f	1.5c-e
113.	EEB423	116.5g-p	113e-h	25.5y-H	19.5h-u	30e-i	9.67F-P	4a-c	2.5a-d
114.	EEB431	113.5h-p	107k-n	29p-w	18.17h-v	23.67p-z	5N-P	4.5ab	3a-c
115.	EEB433	113.5i-p	106l-o	26.17v-F	17.17j-v	24.17n-w	9.83E-P	4.5ab	2.5a-d
116.	EEB434	115.5i-p	106l-o	26.17v-F	19.33h-u	12.33T-Y	6.17L-P	5a	3.5ab
117.	EEB436	118i-p	106l-o	23.83C-K	13.67o-A	16.83E-R	17.67h-F	4a-c	3.5ab

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Days to Maturity		No. of grain per spike		No. of Tillers per Plant		Growth Habit	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
118.	EEB438	125.5i-p	117b-d	23.5E-L	6.08w-D	10.67YZ	13.08t-N	1f	1de
119.	EEB439	116i-p	107k-n	24.33B-J	14.17n-A	21u-D	19.67g-y	2d-f	2b-e
120.	EEB440	116.5i-p	108j-l	21.83J-P	23.5h-q	23.83o-y	15.67m-J	3b-e	2.5a-d
121.	EEB443	118.5j-p	112f-h	23F-M	16.5j-y	24.83m-v	18.67h-B	2.5c-f	1.5c-e
122.	EEB444	122.5k-p	117b-d	27.08t-B	16.67j-y	37.5bc	13.5r-M	2d-f	1de
123.	EEB450	98.5n-p	89x	93.67ab	88a-c	16.67F-S	18.83h-A	5a	4a
	Mean	115.99	106.89	31.96	22.5	21.04	16.72	3.6	2.8
	Range	92-133	85.0-122.0	10.00-94.00	2.00-84.00	7.67-44.00	1.67-43.67	1.0-5.00	0.00-4.00
	SE(±)	2.63	0.5	0.5	1.7	0.63	1.31	0.3	0.27

4.3.8. Thousand grain weight

In control treatment condition, the mean ranges of thousand grain weight were 11.34-67.30 with mean value 40.66. The maximum number of thousand grain weight were revealed for the genotype EEB107 (57.73) followed by EEB111 (57.43) and the minimum number of thousand grain weight were exhibited in the genotype EEB81 (12.37) followed by EEB83 (14.45). In drought stressed condition, the mean ranges of thousand grain weight were 0.8-50.87 with mean value 31.67. The maximum number of thousand grain weight were revealed for the genotype EEB337 (50.35) followed by EEB1376 (46.72) and the minimum number of thousand grain weight were exhibited in the genotype EEB81 (1.87) followed by EEB418 (7.62).

Mirosavljević *et al.* (2015) found the highest thousand grain weight in genotypes G4, G10 and G19 while the lowest thousand grain weight was found in G18.

4.3.9. Biological weight

In control treatment condition, the mean ranges of biological weight were 9.67-118.33 with mean value 33.33. The maximum number of biological weight were revealed for the genotype EEB318 (73) followed by EEB41 (58.83) and the minimum number of biological weight were exhibited in the genotype EEB92 (12.67) followed by EEB136 (14.50). In drought stressed condition, the mean ranges of biological weight were 2-70.0 with mean value 26.01. The maximum number of biological weight were revealed for the genotype EEB17 (69.5) followed by EEB119 (60.83) and the minimum number of biological weight were exhibited in the genotype EEB423 (6.65) followed by EEB136 (7.17).

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Plant height		Thousand Grain weight		Biological Weight	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
1	BARI5	91.5r-w	82h-w	40.71a-s	33.56k-G	23.83y-Q	25.83v-K
2	BARI7	94.5m-q	68.83G-P	34.74e-w	23.52K-R	25.67v-Q	20D-Q
3	BARI8	85.17H-L	75.5u-I	33.28i-w	21.57N-S	38.5d-z	31.75n-z
4	BARI9	84.67J-L	77.67p-E	41.76a-r	32.77p-G	29.83p-O	14.5N-X
5	EEB11	91.33s-x	83g-u	48.33a-l	34.35j-F	28s-P	35.83l-t
6	EEB17	77.83W-Z	81.17j-w	41.03a-s	28.08E-O	20.67C-Q	69.5a
7	EEB18	93.67o-s	96.33a	23.03s-y	32.59p-G	23.58y-Q	49.67d-f
8	EEB23	90.5t-z	87.5b-k	43.5a-q	38.61d-s	45c-r	20D-Q
9	EEB28	84.67J-L	83.33f-u	41.26o-C	29.37y-M	47.83c-m	9.17T-Z
10	EEB32	83.33L-P	77.5p-E	40.08n-C	28.12D-O	36.17d-D	32.67m-x
11	EEB35	85.5G-L	81.17j-w	43.3n-C	39.32x-L	48.5c-k	32.83m-x
12	EEB38	87D-J	91.17a-g	44.9i-z	37.47u-K	21.67A-Q	8.5V-Z
13	EEB40	78W-Z	67.33I-R	39.93p-C	26.56f-C	26.83v-Q	20.17D-Q
14	EEB41	89.67v-C	76.33s-H	40.05a-s	29.77f-A	58.83bc	12.5P-X
15	EEB42	87.83A-G	77.33p-F	41.33a-r	30.72r-I	21.83A-Q	25.83v-K
16	EEB43	80.33R-W	79.83k-A	46.3a-p	35.96c-r	45.5c-q	26.17u-J
17	EEB47	90v-B	80.67j-x	52n-C	36.25k-G	52.5cd	14.83N-X
18	EEB50	93.5o-s	87.5b-k	38.25c-t	31.77S-V	18.33H-Q	39.5g-O
19	EEB53	90.67t-z	80.17j-z	48.51a-l	39.18z-N	48c-l	42.58f-l
20	EEB60	80R-W	73.92w-K	46.48a-p	33.64X	33.67i-J	56b-e
21	EEB69	90.33u-A	80.17j-z	36.42d-v	16p-G	40d-y	49.83d-f
22	EEB79	79.17R-X	80.67j-x	39.24c-t	28.98J-R	16.25M-Q	28r-H
23	EEB81	78.5U-Z	77.33p-F	12.37y	1.87w-L	21.5B-Q	28.5q-G
24	EEB82	67.83333	59.67R-U	42.74a-q	32.68p-H	43.33c-u	8.5V-Z
25	EEB83	58.5	37W	14.45xy	23.95b-k	20.75C-Q	35.67l-u
26	EEB87	93o-t	85d-q	37.65c-u	30.22d-v	47.5c-m	15.5M-X
27	EEB88	84.33K-L	75.5u-I	38.85c-t	32.13m-G	30.83n-O	37j-s
28	EEB90	87.5B-H	90.17a-h	46.79a-o	40.88H-R	32.5j-M	39g-p
29	EEB91	80.67Q-V	71.33B-P	45.08a-p	37.75b-l	40.5d-w	8.67V-Z
30	EEB92	84.33K-L	77.33p-F	38.17c-t	33.05a-c	12.67PQ	22.5z-O
31	EEB107	94.83I-p	77.33p-F	57.73a-s	25.03F-P	16.83K-Q	36.67k-s
32	EEB111	92.83p-u	81.5i-w	57.43a-j	40.58j-F	46.5c-o	32.67m-x
33	EEB112	78.17V-Z	66.67J-R	54.62a-s	46.09l-G	44.93c-r	46.67d-i
34	EEB114	96.67h-m	92.17a-e	54.61d-v	27.77u-K	40.83d-w	36.83k-s
35	EEB116	97.17g-l	86c-o	53.5a-p	34.4a-f	33d-w	30.5o-V
36	EEB117	97.5f-k	77.83o-D	53.08a-k	33.31l-G	118a	33m-x
37	EEB119	81.5N-S	86.83c-l	52.83a-q	30.86u-K	25.17v-Q	60.83ab
38	EEB122	95.5j-o	86.83c-l	52.77a-f	43.12a-f	34.67f-H	37.42i-r
39	EEB129	100.5c-e	86.83c-l	52.71a-q	24.67l-R	34.17g-l	2.5YZ

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Plant height		Thousand Grain weight		Biological Weight	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
40	EEB131	88.67y-E	78.67I-B	51.99a-m	10.85VW	34h-I	8.08V-Z
41	EEB134	90.33u-A	86.83c-l	51.78a-r	35.20h-E	24x-Q	50.33c-f
42	EEB135	90.67t-z	80.33j-y	51.64a-o	35.55g-D	39d-z	9.5S-Z
43	EEB136	60	76.08t-H	51.45c-v	21.21O-T	14.50-Q	7.17W-Z
44	EEB140	99.17d-h	87.17b-k	51.31a-p	33.14m-G	19.2F-Q	25.17w-L
45	EEB142	96.67h-m	91.33a-f	51.22a-e	35.68g-C	46.83c-n	19.17F-R
46	EEB145	101.17cd	80.5j-y	50.85c-t	22.03M-S	51.17c-e	28.83q-E
47	EEB148	93.33o-s	87b-k	50.65a-r	36.13f-B	30p-O	18.5H-T
48	EEB150	87.167C-J	82.33h-v	49.95a-o	34.43j-F	41.5d-v	17.17J-V
49	EEB152	98.83d-i	93.67a-c	49.91f-w	34.31j-F	34.5f-H	25.5v-K
50	EEB161	90v-B	70.5B-P	49.48a-i	28.72B-M	28.83r-P	34.17l-w
51	EEB163	89.17w-D	76.67r-G	49.43a-i	34.69j-F	32I-M	23y-M
52	EEB166	89.42w-D	72z-N	48.89a-s	19.55Q-U	50.67c-f	29.83p-C
53	EEB168	83.17L-Q	67.67I-R	47.98f-w	31.95q-l	50.5c-g	56.08b-d
54	EEB169	89.67v-C	74.17v-J	47.53b-s	31.25s-j	17.33J-Q	24.5x-M
55	EEB173	75.25	66J-R	47.44a-s	26.45G-Q	50.25c-h	35.83l-t
56	EEB203	52.91667	65.67L-R	47.27p-y	29.54x-L	14.83N-Q	22A-P
57	EEB204	61.66667	70.5B-P	46.85xy	40.96b-k	19.5E-Q	42.83f-l
58	EEB208	56.75	69.67D-P	46.58d-v	28.55C-O	26.83v-Q	32.23m-y
59	EEB212	77.83W-Z	69G-P	46.43n-y	35.09i-F	34.3f-H	59.83bc
60	EEB227	86.33E-K	88.17a-j	46.22a-d	32.86n-G	24.83w-Q	48.17d-g
61	EEB251	85H-L	69.5E-P	45.74r-y	30.7u-k	19.33F-Q	27.5s-I
62	EEB254	78.5U-Z	63.5P-S	45.32q-y	14.12T-W	18.5G-Q	29.5p-D
63	EEB255	64.16667	65.83K-R	45.3a-q	32.55p-G	20.33C-Q	34.83l-v
64	EEB265	85.67F-L	67.5I-R	45a-q	36.54e-y	30.83n-O	18.75H-S
65	EEB266	87.33C-I	84.33e-s	44.79a-d	42.59b-h	35.17e-F	26.17u-J
66	EEB267	94n-r	72.33y-M	44.4h-w	36.37f-z	26.33v-Q	14N-X
67	EEB290	94.33m-q	83g-u	44.26a-r	29.35y-M	38d-A	12.5P-X
68	EEB292	81.67M-R	68.17H-Q	43.73j-x	19.79Q-U	26.33v-Q	22.83y-N
69	EEB295	95.17k-p	69.17F-P	43.56a-q	32.87n-G	33i-K	18.5H-T
70	EEB296	88.67y-E	71.33B-P	43.47a-k	33.08m-G	44.17c-t	13.17O-X
71	EEB297	97.83f-j	68.83G-P	43.26j-x	27.71F-P	38.5d-z	10.25R-Z
72	EEB298	81P-U	76.83q-G	43.2a-r	23.03L-S	17.75I-Q	20.5C-Q
73	EEB301	98e-j	67.17J-R	42.97r-y	20.05Q-U	35.83e-E	14.5N-X
74	EEB308	96.5i-n	76.67r-G	42.23c-v	24.33j-R	48.67-k	21B-Q
75	EEB309	98.75d-i	81.61i-w	42.15n-y	35.85f-C	24.5w-Q	38h-q
76	EEB312	97.83f-j	71.33B-P	41.96d-v	37.72d-v	47.67-m	33.83l-x
77	EEB313	99.5c-g	64N-S	41.94m-y	32.41p-H	28.08s-P	11.75Q-Y
78	EEB318	75.16667	66.33J-R	41.75a-q	32.08q-l	73b	46.17f-k

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Plant height		Thousand Grain weight		Biological Weight	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
79	EEB325	81.17O-T	87b-k	41.6c-t	31.16t-j	31.67l-M	46.5e-j
80	EEB335	88.67y-E	93.67a-c	41.59a-i	40.23b-n	33.5i-J	16.5K-W
81	EEB336	87.5B-H	93.5a-c	41.48a-s	33.66k-G	27.23u-Q	26v-K
82	EEB337	78.83T-Y	78.67I-B	41.14ab	50.35a	30.330-O	27.5s-I
83	EEB343	84.17K-M	88b-k	40.97a-r	30.68v-K	27.67u-P	27t-I
84	EEB344	84.83I-L	89.5a-i	40.77c-t	38.12d-u	35.33e-F	15.83L-X
85	EEB345	88.17z-F	86.33c-n	40.63m-y	39.23c-q	32.32k-M	47d-h
86	EEB346	95.5j-o	80j-A	40.51a-f	40.88b-k	34.83e-G	15.83L-X
87	EEB347	81.33N-T	67.83I-R	40.46a-s	33.77k-G	31.67l-M	23y-N
88	EEB352	84.17K-M	78.33n-C	40.46a-j	40.21b-o	25.17v-Q	16.67J-W
89	EEB353	93o-t	81.17j-w	40.30a-s	38.82c-r	23.5z-Q	19.17F-R
90	EEB354	90.67t-z	76.33s-H	40.29a-e	40.43b-m	27.83t-P	8.72U-Z
91	EEB355	92q-v	77.83o-D	39.58a-i	38.48d-t	26.5v-Q	7.5W-Z
92	EEB358	99d-i	91.33a-f	39.24a-q	30.25w-L	48.83c-j	16.67J-W
93	EEB362	71.5	51.5UV	38.45a	31.32s-j	24x-Q	1Z
94	EEB363	83.67L-O	59.83R-T	38.39a-r	18.89r-u	32.83i-L	9.83R-Z
95	EEB366	77X-1	83.83f-t	37.62a-d	43.88a-e	26.5v-Q	28.67q-F
96	EEB370	60.75	50.5V	37.29k-x	29.08z-m	34.95e-G	30.42O-B
97	EEB371	88.83x-E	93.17a-d	36.85c-v	28.92A-M	23.33z-Q	23y-N
98	EEB375	83.83K-N	95.17ab	36.81a-c	29.2y-M	30.67n-O	47.25D-H
99	EEB376	76.5Y-2	85.5c-p	36.39a-p	46.72ab	16.5L-Q	10R-Z
100	EEB377	77.83W-Z	82.67h-u	36.33a-c	42.88bg	36.5d-C	15.5M-X
101	EEB380	89w-D	83.83f-t	35.56a-p	32.8o-G	40.33d-x	24.83w-M
102	EEB382	100c-f	72z-N	34.50a-o	35.7f-C	36.33d-C	18.67H-T
103	EEB384	83.33L-P	63.67O-S	34.18a-r	14.1T-w	35.85e-E	14.67N-X
104	EEB385	88.33z-E	82.83h-u	33.62a-p	20.58P-T	49c-i	31.27o-A
105	EEB394	76.17Z-2	71.83A-O	33.48g-w	23.1L-S	31n-N	31.67n-z
106	EEB400	76Z-2	70.5B-P	32.33w-y	13U-W	11Q	7.83V-Z
107	EEB401	94.67I-p	78.5m-B	32.27a-s	31.35s-j	33.67i-J	40.83f-n
108	EEB407	79S-Y	72.83x-L	31.62o-y	36.93d-x	25.25v-Q	18.25I-U
109	EEB408	76.17Z-2	74.17v-J	30.52c-v	38.9c-r	29.02q-P	19.33e-R
110	EEB409	74.16667	67.33I-R	30.11a-k	42.39b-i	30.5n-O	24.5x-M
111	EEB417	60	64.33M-S	30.07v-y	39.55b-p	37.83d-B	39g-p
112	EEB418	63.58333	56.75S-V	29.68t-y	7.62WX	35e-F	29.2q-D
113	EEB423	101.83c	88.17a-j	29.68a-q	30.12w-L	40.33d-x	6.65X-Z
114	EEB431	109a	85.5c-p	29.45a-g	41.69b-j	44.33c-s	16.67J-W
115	EEB433	105.17b	86.67c-m	28.64a-h	44.11a-d	30.83n-O	12.33Q-X
116	EEB434	97.83f-j	83g-u	26.97a-q	35.59g-C	37.5d-B	8.33V-Z
117	EEB436	91.17s-y	84.83e-r	24.62a-p	21.18O-T	19.83D-Q	29.17q-D

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Plant height		Thousand Grain weight		Biological Weight	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
118	EEB438	78.92T-Y	71.92A-N	24.17u-y	25.03H-R	14.95N-Q	11.5Q-Y
119	EEB439	79S-Y	72.5x-M	21.33a-r	30.58v-K	25w-Q	23y-M
120	EEB440	74.16667	70.17C-P	20.06a-q	33.81k-G	38d-A	25.5v-K
121	EEB443	65.83333	60.17Q-T	19.56a-r	30.83u-K	29.33q-O	19G-S
122	EEB444	71.83333	52.5T-V	17.35a-q	32.7p-G	31.5m-M	15.5M-X
123	EEB450	93o-t	86.67c-m	15.11a-n	30.64v-K	45.83c-p	41.67f-m
	Mean	85.45	77.06	40.66	31.67	33.33	26.01
	Range	52.33-109.67	34.00-97.67	11.34-67.30	0.80-50.87	9.67-118.33	2.0-70.0
	SE(±)	0.4	1.28	2.82	1.16	2.6	1.49

4.3.10 Number of spike per plant

In control treatment condition, the spike number per plant were exhibited the ranges of mean 1.5-39.33 with mean value 14.19. Maximum tiller number per plant were EEB382 (28.83) followed by EEB112 (27.08). The minimum tiller number per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB83 (2.25), EEB400 (2.58) etc. In drought stressed condition, the tiller number per plant were exhibited the ranges of mean 1.00-26.33 with mean value 11.68. Maximum tiller number per plant were EEB69 (25.33). The minimum tiller number per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB254 (1.5) etc.

Firoozabadi *et al.* (2022) showed that mean comparison showed that the highest grain yield was related to genotypes.

4.3.11 Row type

In control and drought treatment condition, the row type were exhibited the ranges of mean 0-6 with mean value 2.75. They have 2 types row i.e. 2 row type and six row type.

Farooq *et al.* (2022) revealed that six-row **barley** showed that the number of grains **per spike** is an important factor in determining yield and increases yield under optimal irrigation and decreases yield in water deficit condition.

4.3.13 Yield per plant

In control treatment condition, the mean ranges of yield per plant were 1.72-36.88 with mean value 13.77. Maximum values for yield per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB450 (35.22) followed by EEB401 (35.11) , EEB336 (31.05) and the minimum yield per plant were exhibited in the genotype EEB81 (1.17) followed by EEB346 (4.22) etc. In drought stressed condition, the mean ranges of yield per plant were 0.33- 28.1 with mean value 6.59. Maximum values for yield per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB114 (27.78) followed EEB318 (24.95) and the minimum yield per plant were exhibited in the genotype EEB301 (0.31), EEB443 (0.92) etc.

Adhikari *et al.* (2018) observed that the genotypes COQ/K1/DESC11, MATICO“S” produced higher yield than other genotypes.

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Row Type		No. of Spike per Plant		Yield per plant	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
1	BARI5	6a	6a	15.5e-y	14.33d-A	32.015cd	26.53ab
2	BARI7	6a	6a	11.5I-G	11.67I-H	34.02a-c	25.91a-c
3	BARI8	6a	6a	17.33d-t	9.67q-L	36.83a	24.28a-c
4	BARI9	6a	6a	10.67o-H	12.33k-F	35.685ab	24.04a-d
5	EEB11	2b	2b	17.17d-t	20.5a-i	16.1o-r	4.69I-B
6	EEB17	2b	2b	7.83u-H	21a-f	18.885i-o	5.79h-w
7	EEB18	6a	6a	6.75y-H	11.67I-H	26.08fg	3.08o-B
8	EEB23	2b	2b	18.83c-q	19.67a-k	10.82x-i	5.82h-w
9	EEB28	2b	2b	15.83e-x	15c-x	22.07i-k	5.75i-x
10	EEB32	2b	2b	19.33c-p	5.5E-O	26.56fg	6.25h-r
11	EEB35	2b	2b	18d-s	9.33r-M	11.03w-h	4.95k-B
12	EEB38	2b	2b	17.17d-t	10.33o-k	5.25h-z	4.79I-B
13	EEB40	2b	2b	16d-w	10.67n-j	21.09j-l	5.19j-z
14	EEB41	2b	2b	24.17b-e	14.17d-A	22.94h-j	5.02k-A
15	EEB42	2b	2b	15.33e-y	4.17H-O	16.985n-q	5.84h-w
16	EEB43	2b	2b	23.67b-f	13.5f-C	21.75j-l	6.04h-u
17	EEB47	2b	2b	22.67b-h	10.83m-l	17.74m-p	4.45I-B
18	EEB50	2b	2b	11.67I-F	9.17s-M	19.47k-n	5.46j-z
19	EEB53	2b	2b	23.67b-f	14.17d-A	7.915i-s	5.92h-v
20	EEB60	2b	2b	16.83d-u	14.58c-y	14.97p-u	5.5j-z
21	EEB69	6a	6a	13.83h-A	13.67e-B	26.8fg	8.63f-k
22	EEB79	2b	2b	6.67y-H	20.58a-h	11.03w-h	4.83k-B
23	EEB81	2b	2b	2.83F-H	8.5u-N	1.17	5.12k-z
24	EEB82	2b	2b	19c-q	15.33c-w	9.36b-p	4.01I-B
25	EEB83	2b	2b	2.25H	4I-O	3.85v-3	5.65i-z
26	EEB87	2b	2b	19.83b-n	14.83C-y	11.25w-g	3.3n-B
27	EEB88	2b	2b	16d-w	7.67x-O	12.11t-e	2.7p-B
28	EEB90	2b	2b	12k-E	8.42v-O	3.08x-3	9.59f-h
29	EEB91	6a	6a	13.33i-B	11.83I-G	26.67fg	12.04f
30	EEB92	2b	2b	8.5t-H	4.75G-O	16.04o-r	6.84h-o
31	EEB107	2b	2b	6.17z-H	9.83p-L	10.60y-k	4.03I-B
32	EEB111	2b	2b	16.33d-v	20.33a-j	14.80p-v	4.27I-B
33	EEB112	2b	2b	27.08bc	21.58a-d	5.35s-z	2.84p-B
34	EEB114	6a	6a	12k-E	14.5c-z	25.23gh	27.78a
35	EEB116	6a	6a	14h-A	16.67c-s	17.77m-p	23.74b-e
36	EEB117	2b	2b	37a	5.83D-O	15.07p-t	3.86I-B
37	EEB119	2b	2b	11.33I-G	10.33o-k	12.29s-d	4.01I-B
38	EEB122	2b	2b	13j-C	18.17a-n	16.98n-q	3.6n-B
39	EEB129	6a	6a	6.83x-H	7z-O	26.32fg	23.39b-e

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Row Type		No. of Spike per Plant		Yield per plant	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
40	EEB131	2b	2b	11.67I-F	16.17c-t	10.12a-l	5.23j-z
41	EEB134	2b	2b	9s-H	24.67ab	11.82v-f	1.97x-B
42	EEB135	2b	2b	14.17h-z	13.33g-D	13.65r-x	6.96h-n
43	EEB136	2b	2b	3.5E-H	6.25B-O	0.91	2.53q-B
44	EEB140	6a	6a	10.33p-H	3.17j-O	20.48j-m	7.54g-m
45	EEB142	2b	2b	15.33e-y	6.33B-O	5.89r-y	5.68i-y
46	EEB145	6a	6a	11.83I-F	4.67G-O	33.57bc	8.95f-j
47	EEB148	2b	2b	13.33i-B	13i-E	24.82g-i	2.33u-B
48	EEB150	2b	2b	20.17b-l	11.67I-H	25.83gh	6.35h-p
49	EEB152	6a	6a	13.33i-B	9.5q-M	7.67k-t	9.34f-i
50	EEB161	2b	2b	13.5i-B	9.5q-M	8.06h-s	4.3l-B
51	EEB163	6a	6a	13.83h-A	11.83I-G	29.01ef	7.58g-m
52	EEB166	2b	2b	16.67d-u	0.92O	2.93y-3	2.35t-B
53	EEB168	2b	2b	19.25c-p	8.67t-N	7.03m-u	6.24h-s
54	EEB169	2b	2b	8.83t-H	25.33a	15.12p-s	4.86k-B
55	EEB173	2b	2b	24.92b-d	14.25d-A	6.82o-v	4.79l-B
56	EEB203	6a	6a	4.5B-H	13.33g-D	25.96g	7.62g-l
57	EEB204	2b	2b	3.92D-H	11.5I-I	2.99x-3	2.75p-B
58	EEB208	6a	6a	13.42i-B	9.67q-L	13.31r-z	2.51r-B
59	EEB212	2b	2b	6z-H	8.75t-N	2.72z-3	3.64n-B
60	EEB227	6a	6a	7.08w-H	10.5o-J	30.33de	8.6f-k
61	EEB251	2b	2b	12.17k-E	6C-O	13.02s-a	2.24u-B
62	EEB254	2b	2b	3.5E-H	1.5NO	3.71w-3	5.01q-A
63	EEB255	2b	2b	5A-H	21.08a-e	14.99p-u	2.67p-B
64	EEB265	2b	2b	4.58B-H	17.33b-p	2.09 1-3	5.6i-z
65	EEB266	2b	2b	13.5i-B	7.83w-O	13.45r-y	6.04h-u
66	EEB267	2b	2b	10.17q-H	10.5o-J	10.22a-l	3.66n-B
67	EEB290	2b	2b	19.83b-n	11.67I-H	12.99s-b	3.33n-B
68	EEB292	2b	2b	14.83f-z	12.83j-E	10.02b-m	4.36l-B
69	EEB295	2b	2b	14h-A	12.17k-G	7.02n-u	4.96k-A
70	EEB296	2b	2b	19.17c-q	20.83a-g	9.16e-p	3.9l-B
71	EEB297	2b	2b	13.83h-A	7.67x-O	14.71q-v	3.73n-B
72	EEB298	2b	2b	9.67r-H	6.25B-O	2.11 1-3	5.69i-y
73	EEB301	2b	2b	10.17q-H	1.58NO	6.92n-u	1.31AB
74	EEB308	2b	2b	23.33b-g	13.33g-D	7.7j-t	3.9l-B
75	EEB309	2b	2b	13.5i-B	17c-q	8.93f-q	3.31n-B
76	EEB312	2b	2b	17.25d-t	15.67c-v	5.94q-x	1.86z-B
77	EEB313	2b	2b	13.5i-B	9.5q-M	2.071-3	2.22v-B
78	EEB318	6a	6a	10.83n-H	17.67b-o	21.23j-l	24.95a-c

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Row Type		No. of Spike per Plant		Yield per plant	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
79	EEB325	2b	2b	9.08s-H	18.67a-l	13.98r-w	3.11o-B
80	EEB335	2b	2b	10.17q-H	13.25h-D	9.23e-p	4.27l-B
81	EEB336	6a	6a	14.33g-z	10.83m-I	31.05c-e	22.7c-e
82	EEB337	2b	2b	20b-m	22a-c	10.38z-l	2.71p-B
83	EEB343	2b	2b	14h-A	13.33g-D	11.01w-h	3.81m-B
84	EEB344	2b	2b	12.33k-E	20a-j	6.45p-w	5.18j-z
85	EEB345	2b	2b	7.33v-H	18.33a-m	4.74t-1	5.28j-z
86	EEB346	2b	2b	14.83f-z	6.83A-O	4.22u-2	5.16j-z
87	EEB347	2b	2b	12.5k-E	10.67N-J	8.18h-s	2.85p-B
88	EEB352	2b	2b	11m-H	12.17k-G	8.68g-r	5.45j-z
89	EEB353	2b	2b	10.33p-H	8w-O	10.84x-i	5.78h-w
90	EEB354	2b	2b	17d-t	8.67t-N	12.28s-d	4.09l-B
91	EEB355	2b	2b	18.67c-r	7.83w-O	10.24a-l	5.46j-z
92	EEB358	2b	2b	19.5c-o	8.33v-O	10.7x-i	3.96l-B
93	EEB362	2b	2b	12.83k-D	2M-O	20.31j-n	2.07y-B
94	EEB363	2b	2b	22b-j	13.5f-C	10.19a-l	4l-B
95	EEB366	2b	2b	11.83I-F	16.83c-r	21.82j-l	1.9y-B
96	EEB370	2b	2b	22.17b-i	20.83a-g	4.27u-2	3 p-B
97	EEB371	2b	2b	23.33b-g	13.67e-B	13.32r-z	4.98k-A
98	EEB375	2b	2b	13.5i-B	13.5f-C	10.71x-i	3.59n-B
99	EEB376	2b	2b	8.5t-H	5F-O	13.27r-z	3.83l-B
100	EEB377	2b	2b	17.33d-t	12.17k-J	10.68x-j	3.05o-B
101	EEB380	2b	2b	20.33b-l	11.5l-I	12.04u-e	5.29j-z
102	EEB382	2b	2b	28.83ab	11.83l-G	3.85v-3	5.65i-z
103	EEB384	2b	2b	16.17d-v	16c-u	12.7s-c	2.71p-B
104	EEB385	2b	2b	20.17b-l	8.5u-N	16.23o-r	6.33h-q
105	EEB394	2b	2b	15f-z	12.83j-E	9.2e-p	6.16h-t
106	EEB400	6a	6a	2.58G-H	2.5L-O	20.65j-m	11.09fg
107	EEB401	6a	6a	10.83n-H	7.67x-O	35.11ab	20.45de
108	EEB407	2b	2b	12k-E	5.583E-O	3.35x-3	3.7n-B
109	EEB408	2b	2b	16.17d-v	11.17l-I	9.81c-n	3.64n-B
110	EEB409	2b	2b	17d-t	10.17o-K	14.00q-w	4.57l-B
111	EEB417	6a	6a	12.17k-E	14.17d-A	26.45fg	20.08e
112	EEB418	2b	2b	19.75c-n	10.75n-I	1.49 23	5.06k-A
113	EEB423	2b	2b	19c-q	7.33y-O	11.23w-g	3.24n-B
114	EEB431	2b	2b	13.17i-B	2.83K-O	9.17e-p	2.4t-B
115	EEB433	2b	2b	14h-A	8.17v-O	3.27x-3	5.31j-z
116	EEB434	2b	2b	10.67o-H	5.5E-O	6.640-w	5.73i-x
117	EEB436	2b	2b	15f-z	13.5f-C	4.38u-2	2.715p-B

Table 6: Mean performance of 123 genotypes for yield and different yield contributing characters in barley (continued)

Serial No.	Genotype	Row Type		No. of Spike per Plant		Yield per plant	
		Control	Drought	Control	Drought	Control	Drought
118	EEB438	2b	2b	4C-H	10.08p-K	3.08x-3	2.43s-B
119	EEB439	2b	2b	13.83h-A	9t-M	13.24r-z	6.8h-o
120	EEB440	2b	2b	21b-k	10.83m-I	19.97j-n	5.27j-z
121	EEB443	2b	2b	18.5c-r	14.67c-y	9.49d-o	1.15B
122	EEB444	2b	2b	16d-w	11.33l-I	7.46l-t	4.85k-B
123	EEB450	6a	6a	15f-z	15.33c-w	35.22ab	23.77b-e
	Mean	2.75	2.75	14.19	11.68	13.77	6.59
	Range	0.00-6.00	0.00-6.00	1.5-39.33	0.33-26.33	1.72-36.88	0.33-28.1
	SE(±)	0	0	1.41	1.18	0.47	0.6

4.4 Variability, heritability and genetic advance on selected characters for drought in barley

Different parameters such as genotypic variance (σ^2_g), phenotypic variance (σ^2_p), variance of interaction between genotype and treatment (σ^2_{g*t}), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV%), phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV%), heritability (%), genetic advance (GA) and genetic advance as percent of mean (GA%) of 13 characters were estimated to observe the variability existed among the characters. The results presented in (Table 4.) revealed that the phenotypic variances were higher than genotypic variances for all the characters.

Highest phenotypic and genotypic variances were recorded with number of grains per plant 510.4 and 504.4 respectively followed by biological weight 188.47 and 184.02, plant height 108.67 and 105.41. The low values of phenotypic and genotypic variances were observed with the characters growth habit (0.97 and 0.82) and row type (2.45 and 2.45) respectively.

The phenotypic coefficients of variance (PCV) were ranged from 6.04% for days to maturity to 92.53% for yield per plant, whereas genotypic coefficients of variance (GCV) were ranged from 6.01% for days to maturity to 91.64% for yield per plant. Vinesh *et al.* (2018) reported that the phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) values were higher than genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) values for all the traits studied by them. Medium phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) were recorded for days to flowering, effective tillers per plant, spike number per plant, row type, growth habit and plant height. Medium phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) and low genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) values were displayed for days to flowering, effective tillers per plant, spike number per plant, row type, growth habit and plant height. Low phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) and genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) values were recorded for days to maturity which suggests the limitation of selection for these traits. Fantahun *et al.* (2023) studied that phenotypic variance (δ^2_p) and phenotypic coefficient variance (PCV) were higher than their corresponding genotypic variance (δ^2_g) and genotypic coefficient of variance (GCV) respectively for all the characters studied, indicating that the expression of these characters was influenced by environment.

Heritability analysis estimates the relative contributions of differences in genetic and non-genetic factors to the total phenotypic variance in a population. It is an important concept in quantitative genetics, particularly in selective breeding. The heritability estimation varied from 68% to 99.99%, respectively for canopy temperature to row type. Heritability for yield

per plant was much higher 92.53%. All the characters revealed more than 50% heritability. The highest heritability (H^2_b) was observed for grains per spike followed by yield/ plant, tiller number/plant, thousand grain weight but the lowest H^2_b was identified days to flowering followed by growth habit. Those traits with higher heritability may be considered for selection for further analysis. The result is supported by Matin *et al.* (2019) the high value of GA% was recorded with number of grain per spike (46.00) and the low (1.72) with growth habit.

Genetic advance as percent mean expected (GAM) had a general range between 3.08% for canopy temperature and followed by 186.98% for yield per plant. Among the characters high values of GAM (>20%) were recorded for all the characters except growth habit. Characters with a high genetic advance as a percent of mean allow the improvement of this character through selection (Vinesh *et al.* 2018). Heritability and the genetic advance are also important selection parameters. It is more useful as a selection tool when considered jointly with heritability. Heritability coupled with high genetic advance was observed for characters biomass per plant, grain yield and number of tiller per plant indicating that selection for these characters could be more effective due to additive gene action (Addisu *et al.* 2015). Thus, this study revealed the presence of sufficient variability among the barley landraces in the country that can be exploited for germplasm enhancement.

The present study revealed high heritability accompanied with high genetic advance as percent of the mean for yield per plant, grains per spike and number of tillers per plant and moderate genetic advance as percent of the mean for growth habit, canopy temperature, thousand grain weight. These results could be explained by additive gene action and their selection may be done in early generations. So, there is an ample scope for the improvement of traits through simple selection (Kumar *et al.* 2013).

Table 7: Estimation of genetic parameters on some important characters of 123 barley genotypes in drought condition

Characters	σ^2_g	σ^2_p	GCV%	PCV%	h^2_b	GA	GAM
Days to flowering	42.02	42.53	9.52	9.58	99	13.27	19.5
Days to maturity	41.28	41.79	6.01	6.04	99	13.15	12.31
Plant height (cm)	105.41	108.67	13.32	13.53	97	20.83	27.03
Row Type	2.45	2.45	56.99	56.99	99.99	3.22	117.4
Growth Habit	0.82	0.97	32.42	35.24	85	1.72	61.45
Canopy Temperature (°C)	2.42	3.54	1.81	2.19	68	2.65	3.08
Chlorophyll Content	10.91	11.06	8.21	8.63	91	6.47	16.1
Number of tiller/Plant	45.70	49.12	40.44	41.92	93	13.43	80.35
Number of spike/Plant	25.04	27.81	42.83	45.13	90	9.78	83.72
Number of grain/ spike	504.50	510.40	82.23	82.71	99	46.00	168.41
Biological weight(g)	184.02	188.47	52.16	52.79	98	27.61	106.18
Thousand-grain weight(kg)	64.40	67.09	25.34	25.86	96	16.20	51.15
Relative water content	8.33	8.33	42.8	45.88	87.01	1.24	82.23
Excised water content	4.93	4.93	10.63	10.65	99.59	10.14	21.85
Proline content	0.64	0.69	11.2	11.3	98.17	17.0	22.85
Yield/Plant(g)	36.48	37.91	91.64	92.53	98	12.32	186.98

Here,

σ^2_g = genotypic variance
GCV%= genotypic coefficient of variation

h^2_b =heritability (%)

GAM=genetic advance as percent of mean

σ^2_p =phenotypic variance
PCV% = phenotypic coefficient of variation

GA =genetic advance

4.5 Estimation of correlation coefficient of thirteen characters

The simple correlation coefficient among thirteen important characters viz. days to flowering, plant height (cm), tiller number per plant, canopy temperature, chlorophyll content, number of grains per spike, thousand-grain weight (kg), biological weight (g), days to maturity, growth habit, number of spike per plant, row type, and yield per plant (g) were analyzed for 123 barley genotypes. The correlated characters and the values of the correlation coefficient on control condition and drought stress are presented in Figure 7.

In control condition, Chlorophyll content has a significant positive association with days to flowering and days to maturity but yield per plant, number of grain per spike and row type have a significant negative association. In drought conditions, biological weight has positive correlation with chlorophyll content. In case of flowering days in control and drought condition has significant positive association with days to maturity, and have a significant negative association with yield per plant, row type, number of grain per spike, number of spike per plant, plant height, growth habit, thousand grain weight in control condition and yield per plant, row type, number of grain per spike, plant height, growth habit, thousand grain weight in drought condition. Days to maturity has a significant negative correlation with yield per plant, row type, number of grain per spike, number of spike per plant, plant height, growth habit, thousand grain weight in control condition and yield per plant, row type, number of grain per spike, plant height, growth habit, thousand grain weight in drought condition. Yield per plant has a significant positive correlation with row type, number of grain per spike and significant negative with number of tiller per plant. On the other hand, in drought condition, a significant positive association with row type, number of grain per spike, biological weight, growth habit. In control and drought condition, row type has positive correlation with number of grain per spike and negative correlation with number of tiller per plant, number of spike per plant, growth habit in control and biological weight in drought condition. Number of grain per spike has significant positive association with plant height, growth habit and negative with number of tillers per plant in control condition. In drought, number of grain per spike has significant positive association plant height, growth habit, biological weight. Canopy temperature has no significance in control and drought condition. Biological weight has a positive correlation with number of grain per spike, number of tiller per plant, thousand grain weight in control condition and number of grain per spike, number of tiller per plant, plant height in drought condition. Number of tiller per plant has a positive correlation with number of spike per plant and thousand grain weight in control condition. In

control condition, number of spike per plant has a significant positive correlation with plant height, growth habit, thousand-grain weight. Plant height has a significant positive correlation with growth habit, thousand grain weight in control. In control condition, growth habit has a significant positive association with thousand grain weight and in drought condition has a significant positive association with Plant height. Firoozabadi *et al.* (2022) revealed that biological yield and thousand grain weight had the most effects on grain yield under drought stress conditions. Ramazani & Abdipour (2019); Roljević-Nikolić *et al.* (2021); Nazari *et al.* (2020) also found similar kinds of results.

(a) Control

(b) Drought

Figure 7: Correlations among 13 different characters of barley under control conditions (a), and drought conditions (b)

4.6 Estimation of regression coefficient for 123 barley germplasms

The regression coefficient between yield per plant and the other traits viz. days to flowering, plant height (cm), tiller number per plant, canopy temperature, chlorophyll content, number of grains per spike, thousand-grain weight (kg), biological weight (g), days to maturity, growth habit, number of spike per plant, row type were analyzed and showed in Figure 8-9.

4.6.1 Yield per plant vs row type

Yield per plant vs row type showed no significant relationship between Yield per plant vs row type in control ($R^2 = 0.497$, $p > 0.05$) means the variability of grain yield cannot be explained by the variability of row type (Figure 8a). A linear relationship between row type and yield per plant observed in drought condition ($R^2 = 2E-05$, $p > 0.05$). There was a linear relationship between row type and yield per plant (Figure 8b).

4.6.2 Yield per plant vs growth habit

Yield per plant vs growth habit showed no significant relationship between Yield per plant vs growth habit in control ($R^2 = 0.184$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8a). and in drought ($R^2 = 0.0607$, $p > 0.05$) means the variability of grain yield cannot be explained by the variability of growth habit (Figure 8b).

4.6.3 Yield per plant vs plant height

Yield per plant vs plant height showed a linear relationship between plant height and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.0124$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8a). and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0001$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8b).

4.6.4 Yield per plant vs number of grain per spike

Yield per plant vs number of grain per spike showed no significant relationship between Yield per plant vs number of grain per spike in control ($R^2 = 0.4823$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8a) and in drought ($R^2 = 0.5055$, $p > 0.05$) means the variability of grain yield cannot be explained by the variability of number of grain per spike (Figure 8b).

4.6.5 Yield per plant vs canopy temperature

Yield per plant vs canopy temperature showed a linear relationship between canopy temperature and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.0012$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8a) and in drought condition ($R^2 = 6E-05$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8b).

4.6.6 Yield per plant vs chlorophyll content

Yield per plant vs chlorophyll content showed a linear relationship between chlorophyll content and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.0376$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8a). and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0187$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 8b).

4.6.7 Yield per plant vs spike per plant

Yield per plant vs spike per plant showed a linear relationship between chlorophyll content and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.4405$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9a) and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0003$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9b).

4.6.8 Yield per plant vs number of tiller per plant

Yield per plant vs number of tiller per plant showed no significant relationship between Yield per plant vs number of tiller per plant in control ($R^2 = 0.0321$, $p > 0.05$) means the variability of grain yield cannot be explained by the variability of row type (Figure 9a). A linear relationship between number of tiller per plant and yield per plant observed in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0086$, $p > 0.05$). There was a linear relationship between number of tiller per plant and yield per plant (Figure 9b).

4.6.9 Yield per plant vs days to maturity

Yield per plant vs days to maturity showed a linear relationship between days to maturity and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.2581$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9a) and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.2514$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9b).

4.6.10 Yield per plant vs days to flowering

Yield per plant vs days to flowering showed a linear relationship between days to maturity and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.2563$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9a) and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.2671$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9b).

4.6.11 Yield per plant vs biological weight

Yield per plant vs biological weight showed a linear relationship between Yield per plant vs biological weight in control ($R^2 = 0.003$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9a) and linear relationship between Yield per plant vs biological weight observed in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0474$, $p > 0.05$). There was no significant relationship between Yield per plant vs biological weight, that

means the variability of root dry weight cannot be explained by the variability of Yield per plant vs biological weight under control and drought conditions (Figure 9b).

Mokarram and bijanzadeh (2016) also showed the same result between yield and biological weight.

4.6.12 Yield per plant vs thousand grain weight

Yield per plant vs thousand grain weight showed a linear relationship between thousand grain weight and yield per plant both in control condition ($R^2 = 0.0167$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9a) and in drought condition ($R^2 = 0.0067$, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 9b). Kennedy *et al.* (2017) also studied the same result.

(a) Control

(b) Drought

Figure 8: Relationship between yield per plant vs row type, growth habit, plant height, grain spike per plant, canopy temperature and chlorophyll content

(a) Control

(b) Drought

Figure 9: Relationship between yield per plant vs spike per plant, tillers per plant, days to 50% maturity, flowering time, biological weight, and thousand grain weight

4.7. Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis or clustering refers to the task of grouping a set of objects in such a way that the objects in the same group (called cluster) are more similar (in some sense) to each other than to those in other groups (clusters).

4.7.1 Cluster Analysis under control condition

Cluster analysis was performed with the relative mean values of each genotype. The standardized mean of 123 barley genotypes were employed and an UPGMA dendrogram was constructed using these values (Figure 10). In this dendrogram, 123 barley genotypes were grouped into five clusters at a cophentic correlation coefficient 0.65. Maximum 92 genotypes were occupied in cluster I followed by 13, 8, 9 and 1 genotypes in cluster II, III, IV and V respectively (Table 8).

Among the five clusters, Cluster I consisted of the largest number of genotypes. The cluster had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters.

Cluster II consisted of 13 genotypes. The cluster had the highest cluster mean days to maturity, second largest (high) mean value for canopy temperature, and moderate cluster mean values for days to flowering, plant height, chlorophyll content number of effective tillers per plant, number of total tillers per plant, biological weight, thousand seed weight. Cluster II showed the lowest cluster mean values for most of the traits viz., row type, growth habit, number of spike per plant, and yield per plant. Similar findings were found by (Shtaya *et al.* 2021) for days to flowering, plant height, thousand-grain weight, and number of spikes per plant. Cluster II had many sub-groups.

Cluster III showed the highest cluster means for days to maturity, number of grains per spike, plant height. The cluster showed the second-largest mean values for number of grains per spike and canopy temperature. The cluster showed moderate cluster values for chlorophyll content, yield per plant, biological weight, thousand-grain weight, number of spike per plant,

number of tiller per plant. The cluster showed the lowest cluster mean values for row type, growth habit. Similar findings were found by Shtaya *et al.* (2021) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Cluster number IV had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters. Similar findings were found by Shtaya *et al.* (2021) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Cluster number V includes only one genotype EEB117. Cluster number V had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters. Similar findings were found by Shtaya *et al.* (2021) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Dendrogram showed that within the cluster I had the most diversity. Variation among them may be the result of the differences in their origin. Minimum genetic diversity is present between Cluster II, III, IV and Cluster V which had better characters contributing to yield.

Considering all the characters it appeared that the genotypes in the cluster III and I had good performance. The genotypes in this cluster had relatively shorter growth duration, lower days to flowering, highest grains per spike, higher 1000-grain weight and the maximum yielding ability. These findings were in accordance with Bakhshi *et al.* (2022) and Ferioun *et al.* (2022).

Table 8: Distribution of 123 barley in five different clusters in control condition

Cluster	Number of genotypes	Genotypes in different clusters
I	92	EEB11 EEB17 EEB23 EEB28 EEB32 EEB35 EEB38 EEB40 EEB41 EEB42 EEB43 EEB47 EEB50 EEB53 EEB60 EEB69 EEB82 EEB87 EEB88 EEB90 EEB92 EEB107 EEB111 EEB114 EEB116 EEB119 EEB122 EEB129 EEB131 EEB134 EEB135 EEB140 EEB142 EEB145 EEB148 EEB150 EEB161 EEB169 EEB212 EEB227 EEB251 EEB203 EEB266 EEB267 EEB290 EEB292 EEB295 EEB296 EEB297 EEB298 EEB301 EEB308 EEB309 EEB312 EEB313 EEB318 EEB325 EEB335 EEB336 EEB337 EEB343 EEB344 EEB345 EEB346 EEB347 EEB352 EEB353 EEB354 EEB355 EEB358 EEB362 EEB363 EEB366 EEB371 EEB375 EEB376 EEB377 EEB380 EEB384 EEB385 EEB401 EEB407 EEB408 EEB409 EEB423 EEB431 EEB433 EEB434 EEB436 EEB439EEB440 EEB443
II	13	EEB18 EEB79 EEB81 EEB83 EEB136 EEB265 EEB204 EEB208 EEB254 EEB255 EEB400 EEB417 EEB438
III	8	BARI5 EEB91 EEB152 EEB163 BARI7 BARI8 BARI9 EEB450
IV	9	EEB112 EEB166 EEB168 EEB173 EEB370 EEB382 EEB394 EEB418 EEB444
V	1	EEB117

Table 9: Cluster means for 13 different characters of 123 barley in control condition

Characters	Cluster mean				
	I	II	III	IV	V
RT	2.43	3.54	6	2	2
GH	3.77	2.27	4.88	2.72	3
PH	88.05	69.13	89.69	77.59	97.5
CT	84.54	84.2	83.64	84.59	82.3
CHLC	46.91	45.48	43.02	47.57	47.4
GSP	30.04	20.07	87.02	20.1	29.67
TP	20.94	14.28	16.9	33.36	40.5
SP	14.53	5.47	13.81	21.07	37
FL	76.52	83.96	63.69	83.33	77.5
DM	115.52	123	102.75	122.39	116.5
BWT	33.53	20.03	33.83	40.57	118
TGW	43.01	25.63	41.07	37.08	48.89
YD	16.47	14.17	32.64	8.04	18.07

Here, RT=Row Type, GH= Growth Habit, PH= Plant Height, CT= Canopy Temperature, CHLC= Chlorophyll Content, GSP= Number of grain per spike, TP= Number of tillers per plant, SP= Number of spikes per plant, FL= Days to flowering, DM= days to maturity, BWT= Biological weight, TGW= Thousand grain weight, YD= Yield per plant

Figure 10. Dendrogram from UPGMA clustering for 123 barley genotypes using Euclidean genetic distance based on thirteen yield contributing characters

4.7.2 Cluster Analysis under drought condition

Cluster analysis was performed with the relative mean values of each genotype. The standardized mean of 123 barley genotypes were employed and an UPGMA dendrogram was constructed using these values (Figure 11). In this dendrogram, 123 barley genotypes were grouped into five clusters at a cophentic correlation coefficient 0.51. Maximum 79 genotypes were occupied in cluster I followed by 17, 20, 5 and 2 genotypes in cluster II, III, IV and V respectively (Table 10).

Among the five clusters, Cluster I consisted of the largest number of genotypes. The cluster had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters.

Cluster II consisted of 17 genotypes. The cluster had the highest cluster mean days to maturity, second largest (high) mean value for canopy temperature, and moderate cluster mean values for days to flowering, plant height, chlorophyll content number of effective tillers per plant, number of total tillers per plant, biological weight, thousand seed weight. Cluster II showed the lowest cluster mean values for most of the traits viz., row type, growth habit, number of spike per plant, and yield per plant. Similar findings were found by (Saed-Moucheshi *et al.*, 2022) for days to flowering, plant height, thousand-grain weight, and number of spikes per plant. Cluster II had many sub-groups.

Cluster III showed the highest cluster means for days to maturity, number of grains per spike, plant height. The cluster showed the second-largest mean values for number of grains per spike and canopy temperature. The cluster showed moderate cluster values for chlorophyll content, yield per plant, biological weight, thousand-grain weight, number of spike per plant, number of tiller per plant. The cluster showed the lowest cluster mean values for row type, growth habit. Similar findings were found Saed-Moucheshi *et al.* (2022) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Cluster number IV had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The

cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters. Similar findings were found by Saed-Moucheshi *et al.* (2022) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Cluster number V includes only two genotypes. Cluster number V had a very high mean value only for days to maturity. The cluster had the second largest (high) mean in plant height, canopy temperature, and days to flowering. The cluster had moderate mean values for chlorophyll content, number of total tillers per plant, number of filled grains per panicle, biological weight, thousand seed weight, number of spikes per panicle, and yield per plant. The majority of the genotypes in this cluster showed moderate performance in most of the yield and yield-related traits as compared to the remaining clusters. Similar findings were found by Saed-Moucheshi *et al.* (2022) for days to flowering, and days to maturity.

Dendrogram showed that within the cluster I had the most diversity. Variation among them may be the result of the differences in their origin. Minimum genetic diversity is present between Cluster II, III, IV and Cluster V which had better characters contributing to yield.

Considering all the characters it appeared that the genotypes in the cluster IV, II and I had good performance. The genotypes in this cluster had relatively shorter growth duration, lower days to flowering, highest grains per spike, higher 1000-grain weight and the maximum yielding ability. These findings were in accordance with Asraf *et al.* (2022) and Javed *et al.* (2022).

Table 10: Distribution of 123 barley in five different clusters in drought condition

Cluster	Number of genotypes	Genotypes in different clusters
I	79	EEB11 EEB18 EEB28 EEB32 EEB35 EEB38 EEB40 EEB41 EEB43 EEB47 EEB50 EEB53 EEB82 EEB87 EEB88 EEB90 EEB91 EEB92 EEB111 EEB114 EEB117 EEB119 EEB129 EEB134 EEB140 EEB142 EEB145 EEB148 EEB150 EEB152 EEB161 EEB163 EEB203 EEB204 EEB208 EEB212 EEB227 EEB251 EEB265 EEB266 EEB290 EEB295 EEB296 EEB297 EEB298 EEB308 EEB312 EEB313 EEB325 EEB335 EEB336 EEB337 EEB343 EEB344 EEB346 EEB347 EEB352 EEB353 EEB354 EEB355 EEB358 EEB366 EEB371 EEB375 EEB376 EEB377 EEB380 EEB382 EEB385 EEB401 EEB407 EEB408 EEB409 EEB431 EEB433 EEB434 EEB436 EEB439 EEB440
II	17	EEB17 EEB23 EEB60 EEB69 EEB79 EEB112 EEB116 EEB122 EEB135 EEB255 EEB309 EEB318 EEB345 EEB370 EEB417 EEB443 EEB444
III	20	EEB42 EEB81 EEB83 EEB107 EEB131 EEB136 EEB166 EEB168 EEB254 EEB267 EEB292 EEB301 EEB362 EEB363 EEB384 EEB394 EEB400 EEB418 EEB423 EEB438
IV	5	BARI5 BARI7 BARI8 BARI9 EEB450
V	2	EEB169 EEB173

Table 11: Cluster means for 13 different characters of 123 drought-tolerant barley

Characters	Cluster mean				
	I	II	III	IV	V
RT	2.66	2	3.4	3.6	4
GH	3.05	2.47	1.9	4	1.5
PH	85.76	85.88	86.73	85.93	91.58
CT	40.23	39.42	40.26	41.75	42.67
CHLC	80.1	73.58	68.44	78.13	70.08
GSP	28.49	21.53	13.04	87.13	23.42
TP	15.44	24.42	14.49	13.87	31.29
SP	11.14	17.31	8	12.67	19.79
FL	66.6	70.29	75.92	49.9	73.5
DM	105.45	109.29	114.42	88.9	112.5
BWT	24.53	42.16	16.48	26.75	40.29
TGW	34.18	33.9	20.93	28.41	28.85
YD	5.77	7.82	4.4	24.9	4.82

Here, RT=Row Type, GH= Growth Habit, PH= Plant Height, CT= Canopy Temperature, CHLC= Chlorophyll Content, GSP= Number of grain per spike, TP= Number of tillers per plant, SP= Number of spikes per plant, FL= Days to flowering, DM= days to maturity, BWT= Biological weight, TGW= Thousand grain weight, YD= Yield per plant

Figure 11. Dendrogram from UPGMA clustering for 123 barley genotypes using Euclidean genetic distance based on thirteen yield contributing characters in drought condition

4.8 Principal component analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a powerful tool in modern data analysis because this is a well-known multivariate statistical technique that is used to identify the minimum number of components, which can explain maximum variability out of the total variability (Shtaya *et al.* 2021; Kumar *et al.* 2020 and Hailu *et al.* 2016) and also to rank genotypes based on PC scores.

PCA was performed for 13 traits of barley genotypes. In control condition, only the first four principal components (PCs) exhibited more than 1.00 eigenvalue (Table 12), and showed a maximum cumulative variance of about 85% among the traits studied. A scree plot represents that visualizes the dimensionality of the data (Figure 13). In drought condition, only the first four principal components (PCs) exhibited more than 1.00 eigenvalue (Table 14), and showed a maximum cumulative variance of about 85% among the traits studied. (Figure 12) represents a scree plot that visualizes the dimensionality of the data. The scree plot is a sample line segment plot that displays the cumulative proportions of the explained variance and the number of principal components captures from the data (Shtaya *et al.*, 2022; Khoshkhoo & Jahannemaei, 2022).

Eigenvalues are variances of the principal components. The scree plot orders the eigenvalues from largest to smallest. According to (Figure 20) the horizontal axis shows the principal component number, labeled 1 to 10 where the vertical axis shows eigenvalue, labeled 0 to 5 for both control and drought conditions.

In control condition, principal Component one (PC1) has an eigenvalue of about 4.2 that captures about 32% variance. It is followed by principal component 2 (eigenvalue of about 2.83), component 3 (eigenvalue of about 1.30), component 4 (eigenvalue of about 1.19), then the eigenvalue falls steadily until component 9 has an eigenvalue of about 0.1 (Table 12). In drought condition, Principal Component one (PC1) has an eigenvalue of about 3.68 that captures about 28% variance. It is followed by principal component 2 (eigenvalue of about 2.21), component 3 (eigenvalue of about 1.47), component 4 (eigenvalue of about 1.11), then the eigenvalue falls steadily until component 12 has an eigenvalue of about 0.1 (Table 14).

The scree plot showed that the eigenvalue starts to form a straight-like line after the seventh principal component. Therefore, the remaining principal component accounts for a very small proportion of the variability and are unimportant. Principal components having more than one

eigenvalue showed more variation among the barley genotypes for the selection of the diverse parents.

In control condition, the first four PCs represent maximum variability hence, the traits falling to these four PCs may be given due importance in barley improvement programs. In this study, the first principal component accounted for 32% of the total variability with the variable plant height (0.21), number of grain per spike (0.38), yield per plant (0.35), row type (0.29), growth habit (0.36), number of spike per plant (0.14), biological weight (0.15). The second principal component accounted for 21% of the total variability. A similar result was reported by Kumar *et al.* (2021) for PC2. The variables contributing most positively were growth habit (0.40), plant height (0.15), canopy temperature (0.08), Chlorophyll content (0.13), number of tillers per plant (0.51), number of spike per plant (0.50), biological weight (0.39), thousand grain weight (0.30). The variables contributing most positively were row type (0.35), Chlorophyll content (0.03), number of grains per plant (0.26), number of tillers per plant(0.22), number of spike per plant (0.18), flowering days(0.26), days to maturity (0.26), biological weight (0.44), yield per plant(0.23) The third component accounted 10% to the variance, in which the variables contributing most positively were row type (0.35), Chlorophyll content (0.03), number of grains per plant(0.26), number of tillers per plant (0.22), number of spike per plant (0.18), flowering days(0.26), days to maturity (0.26), biological weight (0.44), yield per plant (0.23). The fourth principle component accounted 9% of variance in the total variability by plant height (0.46), growth habit (0.35), Chlorophyll content (0.62), number of grains per plant(0.26), flowering days (0.07), days to maturity (0.07), thousand grain weight (0.26). The fifth component accounted 6% to the variance, in which the variables contributing most positively were row type (0.14), plant height (0.53), canopy temperature (0.65) Chlorophyll content (0.22), number of grains per plant (0.26), number of tillers per plant(0.22), number of spike per plant (0.18), flowering days(0.26), days to maturity (0.26), biological weight (0.44), yield per plant(0.23) (Table 13).

In case of drought, the first four PCs represent maximum variability hence, the traits falling to these four PCs may be given due importance in barely improvement programs. In this study, the first principal component accounted for 28% of the total variability with the variable days to flowering (0.48), days to maturity (0.46), plant height (0.07), and number of tillers per plant (0.004). The second principal component accounted for 17% of the total variability. A similar result was reported by Alemayehu & Momina (2022) for PC2. The variables contributing most positively were the number of grains per plant (0.08), yield per

plant (0.06), row type (0.01), and growth habit (0.06). The third component accounted for 11% of the variance, in which the variable chlorophyll content (0.23), number of spikes per plant (0.08), thousand-grain weight (0.53), and growth habit (0.32). The fourth principle component accounted for 8% of the variance in the total variability by canopy temperature (0.71), chlorophyll content (0.23), days to flowering (0.08), days to maturity (0.07), biological weight (0.18), thousand-grain weight (0.08). The fifth principle component accounted for 7% of the variance in the total variability by row type (0.54), growth habit (0.01), chlorophyll content (0.26), days to flowering (0.07), days to maturity (0.07), biological weight (0.12) (Table 15).

Thus, the prominent characters come together in different principal components and contribute towards explaining the variability and tend to remain together. This may be kept into consideration during the utilization of these characters' inbreeding programs. Thus, the prominent characters come together in different principal components and contribute towards explaining the variability and tend to remain together. This may be into consideration during the utilization of these characters in a breeding program. The phenotypic value of each trait measures the importance and contribution of each component to total variance, whereas each coefficient of proper vectors indicates the degree of contribution of every original variable with which each principal component is associated. According to this, component matrix coefficients greater than 0.3 indicate an ample component effect and have the importance of that component for a particular trait in the study. Here, PCA revealed that the traits number of tiller per plant, number of grain per spike greater influence (>0.30) on PC1, Chlorophyll content, plant height, number of spikes per panicle for PC2, number of grains per panicle, plant height for PC4. Characters with high variability are expected to provide a high level of gene transfer during breeding programs (Gana, 2006; Gana, 2013; Varthini, 2014; Enyew *et al.* 2019).

a) Control

b) Drought

Figure 12. Scree plot of principal component analysis a) Control, b) drought

Table 12: Eigenvalues and percentage of variation in respect of 13 characters in 123 genotypes of barley in control condition

Principal component	Proportion of Variance	Cumulative Proportion	Eigen Values
PC1	0.32	0.32	4.20
PC2	0.22	0.54	2.83
PC3	0.10	0.64	1.30
PC4	0.09	0.73	1.19
PC5	0.07	0.80	0.87
PC6	0.06	0.86	0.78
PC7	0.04	0.90	0.50
PC8	0.03	0.93	0.45
PC9	0.03	0.96	0.34
PC10	0.02	0.98	0.26
PC11	0.01	0.99	0.17
PC12	0.01	1.00	0.13
PC13	0.00	1.00	0.00

Table 13. Rotated component matrix of 13 characters in 123 genotypes of barley in control condition

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5
RT	0.285	-0.346	0.347	-0.092	0.137
GH	0.357	0.040	-0.147	0.189	-0.141
PH	0.210	0.146	-0.043	0.459	0.531
CT	0.037	0.083	-0.489	-0.427	0.659
CHLC	-0.117	0.134	0.034	0.616	0.216
GSP	0.382	-0.199	0.264	0.026	0.220
TP	0.008	0.506	0.215	-0.242	0.009
SP	0.139	0.503	0.179	-0.213	-0.013
FL	-0.430	-0.020	0.259	0.066	0.147
DM	-0.430	-0.021	0.258	0.067	0.145
BWT	0.148	0.392	0.434	-0.016	0.093
TGW	0.220	0.297	-0.305	0.257	-0.314
YD	0.357	-0.203	0.230	-0.070	-0.003

Here, RT=Row Type, GH= Growth Habit, PH= Plant Height, CT= Canopy Temperature, CHLC= Chlorophyll Content, GSP= Number of grain per spike, TP= Number of tillers per plant, SP= Number of spikes per plant, FL= Days to flowering, DM= days to maturity, BWT= Biological weight, TGW= Thousand grain weight, YD= Yield per plant

Table 14: Eigenvalues and percentage of variation in respect of 13 characters in 123 genotypes of barley in drought condition

Principle component	Proportion of Variance	Cumulative Proportion	EigenValues
PC1	0.28	0.28	3.68
PC2	0.17	0.45	2.21
PC3	0.11	0.57	1.47
PC4	0.09	0.65	1.11
PC5	0.08	0.73	1.05
PC6	0.07	0.80	0.92
PC7	0.06	0.86	0.76
PC8	0.05	0.91	0.61
PC9	0.04	0.94	0.46
PC10	0.02	0.97	0.31
PC11	0.02	0.99	0.26
PC12	0.01	1.00	0.17
PC13	0.00	1.00	0.02

Table 15. Rotated component matrix of 13 characters in 123 genotypes of barley in drought condition

Variables	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5
RT	0.058	0.0117	-0.1377	-0.4503	0.5358
GH	-0.3737	0.0613	0.3234	-0.1417	0.0104
PH	0.0702	-0.004	-0.0651	-0.2609	-0.7666
CT	-0.0261	-0.1378	-0.1619	0.711	-0.0963
CHLC	-0.3022	-0.0339	0.2322	0.2339	0.2595
GSP	-0.3634	0.0793	-0.415	0.0305	-0.0024
TP	0.0423	-0.6144	-0.0315	-0.1416	-0.0358
SP	-0.0852	-0.5883	0.0835	-0.2416	-0.0383
FL	0.4766	-0.0436	-0.0398	0.0794	0.0689
DM	0.4686	-0.0693	-0.0395	0.077	0.067
BWT	-0.1335	-0.4699	-0.2589	0.1829	0.1263
TGW	-0.2092	-0.1202	0.5281	0.0785	-0.1143
YD	-0.3324	0.064	-0.5126	-0.1328	-0.0863

Here, RT=Row Type, GH= Growth Habit, PH= Plant Height, CT= Canopy Temperature, CHLC= Chlorophyll Content, GSP= Number of grain per spike, TP= Number of tillers per plant, SP= Number of spikes per plant, FL= Days to flowering, DM= days to maturity, BWT= Biological weight, TGW= Thousand grain weight, YD= Yield per plant

4.9 Biplot analysis

A genotype \times traits biplot was created from a two-way matrix of thirteen traits and 123 genotypes using the relative value of trait (Figure 13). The plot summarizes the information from this matrix into principal components, where the cosine of the angle between vectors connecting traits to the origin is proportional to the correlation coefficient between those traits. Again, traits on opposite sides of origin are negatively correlated and traits near each other are positively correlated. Also, traits at 90 degrees to each other are not correlated, concerning the origin. The narrow angles between two adjacent vectors in the same direction showed a strong correlation of a character in terms of discerning genotypes.

A principal component (PC) biplot reveals both PC scores of genotypes and loadings of traits. Here, the further away the traits from PC origin indicate the more influence they have on that PC. Again, loading plots indicate how the traits correlate with one another. In the plot, a minimum angle denotes positive correlation, a large one implies negative correlation, and a 90° angle indicates no correlation between two characteristics (Saremi *et al.*, 2022; Neykov *et al.*, 2022).

The traits plant height, chlorophyll content, number of tillers per plant, number of spike per plant, thousand seed weight, biological weight, growth habit, canopy temperature showed positive loadings (PC2). Again, some traits viz. row type, number of grain per spike, yield per plant had negative PC2 scores but positively correlated yield per plant. Here, the plant height vector was far away from other vectors exhibiting maximum distance with yield per plant. (Figure 13a).

This biplot expressed superior genotypes with relatively greater expression of combinations of favorable traits. The total outcome suggested that chlorophyll content, number of tillers per plant, number of spike per plant, thousand grain weight with some barley genotypes shows better performance in control condition.

The traits growth habit, number of grains per spike, and yield per plant showed positive loadings (PC2). Again, some traits viz. plant height, chlorophyll content, number of tillers per plant, number of spike per plant, thousand seed weight, biological weight, growth habit, and canopy temperature had negative PC2 scores but positively correlated yield per plant. Here, the plant height vector was far away from other vectors exhibiting maximum distance with yield per plant. (Figure 13b).

This biplot expressed superior genotypes with relatively greater expression of combinations of favorable traits. The total outcome suggested that with growth habit, number of grain per spike, chlorophyll content, and plant height some barley genotypes shows better performance in drought condition.

a) Control

b) Drought

Figure 13: The relationship between 123 barley genotypes by 13 morpho-physiological and biochemical traits

4.10 Drought susceptible index

In this study genotypes were classified arbitrarily into four different categories i.e. highly drought tolerant (DSI < 0.50), drought tolerant (DSI: 0.51-0.75), moderately drought tolerant (DSI: 0.76-1.00) and Drought susceptible (DSI > 1.00) (Yadav *et al.* 2022). These genotypes could be considered as a drought tolerant genotype and a donor for gene transfer in drought tolerance breeding.

Table 16: Drought susceptible index showing degree tolerances in 123 barley genotypes considering yield performance in both control and drought stress conditions

Serial No.	Genotype	Ys	Yp	DSI	Level of tolerance	Serial No.	Genotype	Ys	Yp	DSI	Level of tolerance
1	EEB81	5.12	1.17	-5.58	highly drought tolerant	34	EEB135	6.96	16.65	0.96	moderately drought tolerant
2	EEB382	24.28	6.85	-4.21		35	EEB353	5.78	13.84	0.96	
3	EEB90	9.59	6.08	-0.96		36	EEB355	5.46	13.24	0.97	
4	EEB83	5.65	3.85	-0.77		37	EEB370	2.97	7.27	0.98	
5	EEB116	23.74	20.77	-0.24		38	EEB91	12.04	29.67	0.98	
6	EEB418	5.06	4.49	-0.21		39	EEB438	2.43	6.08	0.99	
7	EEB298	5.69	5.11	-0.19		40	EEB131	5.23	13.12	0.99	
8	EEB265	5.60	5.09	-0.16		41	EEB161	4.30	11.05	1.01	
9	EEB318	24.95	24.23	-0.05		42	EEB436	2.72	7.38	1.04	
10	EEB114	27.78	28.23	0.03		43	EEB266	6.04	16.45	1.05	
11	EEB204	2.75	2.98	0.13		44	EEB308	3.90	10.70	1.05	
12	EEB152	9.34	10.67	0.21		45	EEB92	6.84	19.04	1.06	
13	EEB433	5.31	6.27	0.25		46	EEB35	4.95	14.03	1.07	
14	EEB166	2.35	2.93	0.33		47	EEB380	5.29	15.04	1.07	
15	EEB129	23.39	29.32	0.33		48	EEB335	4.27	12.23	1.08	
16	BARI5	26.53	35.02	0.40		49	EEB79	4.83	14.03	1.08	
17	EEB254	5.01	6.71	0.42		50	EEB112	2.84	8.35	1.09	
18	EEB346	5.16	7.22	0.47		51	EEB292	4.36	13.02	1.10	
19	BARI7	25.91	37.02	0.50		52	EEB385	6.33	19.23	1.11	
20	EEB417	20.08	29.45	0.53		53	EEB82	4.01	12.36	1.12	drought susceptible
21	EEB345	5.28	7.74	0.53	54	EEB140	7.54	23.48	1.12		
22	EEB336	22.70	34.05	0.55	55	EEB296	3.90	12.16	1.12		
23	EEB136	2.53	3.91	0.59	56	EEB60	5.50	17.97	1.15		
24	EEB142	5.68	8.89	0.60	57	EEB371	4.98	16.32	1.15		
25	EEB212	3.64	5.72	0.60	58	EEB363	3.99	13.19	1.15		
26	EEB450	23.77	38.22	0.63	59	EEB107	4.03	13.60	1.16		
27	EEB168	6.24	10.03	0.63	60	EEB42	5.84	19.99	1.17		
28	BARI9	24.04	38.69	0.63	61	EEB69	8.63	29.80	1.18		
29	EEB434	5.73	9.64	0.67	62	EEB358	3.96	13.70	1.18		
30	EEB407	3.70	6.35	0.69	63	EEB408	3.64	12.81	1.18		
31	EEB38	4.79	8.25	0.69	64	EEB309	3.31	11.93	1.20		
32	EEB344	5.18	9.45	0.75	65	EEB267	3.66	13.22	1.20		
33	EEB53	5.92	10.92	0.76	66	EEB343	3.81	14.01	1.20		

Table 16: Drought susceptible index showing degree tolerances in 123 barley genotypes considering yield performance in both control and drought stress conditions

Serial No.	Genotype	Ys	Yp	DSI	Level of tolerance	Serial No.	Genotype	Ys	Yp	DSI	Level of tolerance
67	EEB401	20.45	38.11	0.77	moderately drought tolerant	96	EEB409	4.57	17.00	1.21	drought susceptible
68	EEB394	6.15	12.20	0.82		97	EEB169	4.86	18.12	1.21	
69	EEB295	4.96	10.02	0.83		98	EEB354	4.09	15.28	1.21	
70	EEB173	4.79	9.82	0.85		99	EEB17	5.79	21.89	1.22	
71	EEB400	11.09	23.65	0.88		100	EEB203	7.62	28.96	1.22	
72	EEB352	5.45	11.68	0.88		101	EEB119	4.01	15.29	1.22	
73	EEB444	4.85	10.46	0.89		102	EEB375	3.59	13.71	1.22	
74	EEB313	2.22	5.07	0.93		103	EEB227	8.60	33.33	1.23	
75	EEB23	5.82	13.82	0.96		104	EEB347	2.85	11.18	1.23	
76	EEB439	6.80	16.24	0.96		105	EEB11	4.69	19.10	1.25	
77	EEB145	8.95	36.57	1.25		106	EEB337	2.71	13.38	1.32	
78	EEB43	6.04	24.75	1.25		107	EEB431	2.40	12.17	1.33	
79	EEB50	5.46	22.47	1.25		108	EEB41	5.02	25.94	1.33	
80	EEB111	4.27	17.80	1.26		109	EEB325	3.11	16.98	1.35	
81	EEB163	7.58	32.01	1.26		110	EEB122	3.60	19.98	1.36	
82	EEB376	3.83	16.27	1.26	111	EEB88	2.70	15.12	1.36		
83	EEB87	3.30	14.25	1.27	112	EEB384	2.71	15.70	1.37		
84	EEB28	5.75	25.07	1.27	113	EEB208	2.51	16.31	1.40		
85	EEB440	5.27	22.97	1.27	114	EEB255	2.67	17.99	1.41		
86	EEB423	3.24	14.23	1.28	115	BARI8	5.65	39.83	1.42		
87	EEB377	3.05	13.68	1.28	116	EEB251	2.24	16.02	1.42		
88	EEB150	6.35	28.83	1.29	117	EEB134	1.97	14.82	1.43		
89	EEB40	5.19	24.09	1.30	118	EEB301	1.31	9.92	1.44		
90	EEB47	4.45	20.74	1.30	119	EEB18	3.08	29.08	1.48		
91	EEB117	3.86	18.07	1.30	120	EEB443	1.15	12.49	1.50		
92	EEB32	6.25	29.56	1.30	121	EEB362	2.07	23.31	1.51		
93	EEB297	3.73	17.71	1.31	122	EEB148	2.33	27.82	1.52		
94	EEB290	3.33	15.99	1.31	123						
95	EEB312	1.86	8.94	1.31		EEB366	1.90	24.82	1.53		

Experiment No. 2: Assessment of genetic diversity in 39 barley genotypes through molecular study

In this study, ten (10) microsatellite markers were used genotypes. The molecular research was undertaken in the Molecular Breeding Laboratory of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, HSTU. The experiment's outcomes are reported under the subsequent subheadings.

4.11 Analysis of DNA fingerprinting based on SSR markers

In the beginning, DNA was taken from young leaves of 3-week-old seedlings of 39 genotypes of barley. The CTAB technique was modified to extract the DNA. Prior to PCR amplification, the quality of the extracted DNA samples was evaluated through quantification using a Thermo Scientific NanoDrop™1000 Spectrophotometer. Thirty nine different genotypes of barley had DNA quantities ranging from 93.4 to 2953. Dido *et al.* (2022) studied 384 Ethiopian barley genotypes collected from different barley growing regions of Ethiopia using 49 simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers. The 3 ng/l. SSR markers revealed the polymorphic bands after polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) examination. Here, the distance between the DNA bands of the SSR/microsatellite markers was measured using a 100 bp DNA ladder. Figure 14 displays a gel image of PCR-amplified fragments utilizing those SSR markers.

a) BMAC0577

b) BMAG808

c) WMS6

d) EBMAC624

Figure 14 Gel picture of microsatellite markers obtained from polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis using 100 bp DNA ladder (contd.)

e) Bmag125

f) Bmag006

g) Scssr25691

h) Bmac0113

Figure 14 Gel picture of microsatellite markers obtained from polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis using 100 bp DNA ladder (contd.)

i) GMS027

j) Bmag337

Figure 14 Gel picture of microsatellite markers obtained from polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis using 100 bp DNA ladder

Legends, 1= EEB11, 2= EEB35, 3= EEB40, 4= EEB41, 5= EEB47, 6= EEB53, 7= EEB60, 8= EEB79, 9= EEB82, 10= EEB122, 11= EEB129, 12= EEB131, 13= EEB134, 14= EEB135, 15= EEB142, 16= EEB203, 17= EEB251, 18= EEB301, 19= EEB336, 20= EEB345, 21= EEB346, 22= EEB377, 23= EEB417, 24= EEB450, 25= EEB23, 26= EEB88, 27= EEB91, 28= EEB107, 29= EEB112, 30= EEB292, 31= EEB297, 32= EEB335, 33= EEB337, 34= EEB343, 35= EEB344, 36= EEB355, 37= EEB380, 38= EEB382, 39= EEB431

4.12 Assessment of polymorphism from SSR Profiles

A total of 31 alleles were identified with 10 SSR markers over 39 barley genotypes (Table 17). According to the Table 2, maximum range of band sizes was found by BMAG808 (160-400bp) which was followed by EBAC624 (130-400bp) and Bmag006 (174-500bp), respectively. The number of alleles per marker ranged from 2 to 4, with an average of 3.1 alleles across the 31 allele. The marker BMAG808 produced the highest number of polymorphic alleles of four (4) followed by EBMAC624 and Bmag006. GMS027, Scssr25691, BMAC0577, Bmac0113 with three (3) each, respectively (Table 17). While WMS6 and Bmag125 markers produced the least number of polymorphic bands per locus of two (2). The PIC (Polymorphism Information Content) values of SSRs ranged from 0.42 to 0.7 with an average of 0.41. The highest PIC value (0.7) was recorded for BMAG808, and GMS027, Bmag337 and Bmac0113 both recorded second highest (0.65) and lowest by WMS6 (0.42). Dido *et al.* (2022) analysed 49 SSR markers amplified a total of 478 alleles with an average of 9.755 alleles per marker were obtained of which 97.07% of the loci were observed to be polymorphic.

Table 17: Allele number, size range and polymorphism information content (PIC) found among 39 barley genotypes for 10 microsatellite markers

Sl. No.	Markers	Allele No.	Size range (bp)	PIC
1	BMAC0577	3	146-160	0.58
2	BMAG808	4	160-400	0.7
3	WMS6	2	270-300	0.42
4	EBMAC624	4	130-400	0.63
5	Bmag125	2	136-162	0.5
6	Bmag006	4	174-500	0.6
7	Scssr25691	3	218-236	0.64
8	Bmac0113	3	208-236	0.65
9	GMS027	3	154-190	0.65
10	Bmag337	3	43-100	0.65
Total		31		
Average		3.1		0.41

4.13 Model-based population structure

39 barley genotypes were evaluated for estimation of population structure based on 10 markers using Structure software. The estimated membership fractions of the 39 genotypes for different k values, ranged from 1 to 12 (Figure 15). The population structure analysis declared the log-likelihood value (ΔK) maximized to the highest value of at $K=3$ (Figure 14), demonstrating a sharp peak expressing the classification of entire genotypes into three specific sub-groups, here denoted as Population I, Population II and Population III respectively (Figure 16).

The Population I consisted 42% of genotypes, Population II consisted 42.1% of genotypes Population III consisted of 16% of genotypes. In structure analysis, accessions were further categorized as pure or admixture, accessions with more than 0.80 score were considered as pure and less than 0.80 as admixture. Here, in population I comprised of 19 genotypes, where 6 genotypes were pure and 13 were admixed. Population II comprised of total 15 genotypes; 8 genotypes were found pure and 7 were admixed. Population III comprised of total 5 genotypes; 5 genotypes were found pure. Here, the F_{ST} population values were 0.0097 for Population I, 0.4879 Population II and 0.8614 for Population III with an average of alpha 0.0870 representing the significant differences among the populations. We calculated average distances (expected heterozygosity) between individuals in same populations. The average intra-population distances in the same cluster were 0.3402 for Population I, 0.1235 for Population II and 0.0679 for Population III. Net nucleotide distance 0.0384 was exhibited between Population I and Population II, 0.2591 between Population I and Population III and 0.03921 between Population II and Population III. Mohammadi *et al.* (2020) also revealed that $K=3$ population structure with SSR markers in barley.

Figure 15: Representation of population structure dividing in three subgroups based on K value

Figure 16: Population structure at K = 3 of 39 barley genotypes based on genotypic data using 10 (ten) microsatellite markers. Color codes are- Population I = Red, Population II = Green, and Population III= Blue

4.14 Pairwise genetic similarity

The genetic similarity coefficients based on SSR markers among the 39 barley genotypes ranged from -0.41 to 0.93 (-41% to 93%) shown in (Table 18). Similarity distances showed that V2 (EEB35) and V3 (EEB40) were the most similar genotypes with 93% similarity coefficient followed by V17 (EEB251), V16(EEB203), and V26 (EEB88) showed similarity coefficients (92%), (87%), and (86%), respectively. So, these pairs were genetically related genotypes. On the other hand, the most unrelated pairs of genotypes based on SSR data were V16 (EEB203) andV28 (EEB417); V17(EEB251) and V19(EEB336); V11 (EEB129) andV6 (EEB53); those showed the lowest similarity coefficients (-41%), (-37%), and (-39%) respectively. The higher similarity coefficients mean that they were lower genetic distances and genetically identical to each other. The lower similarity coefficients mean that they were genetically diverse and showed higher genetic distance. (Abdul-Razzak Tahir *et al.* 2021; Govindaraj *et al.* 2015) also showed the similar results in barley.

4.15 UPGMA dendrogram

The genetic distance-based results in the UPGMA (Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean) cluster analysis revealed three major clusters (Cluster I, Cluster II and Cluster III) in 39 barley genotypes with a dissimilarity coefficient. According to the Figure, two different clusters were revealed with the similarity coefficient 0.00 to 10.0.

Cluster I consisted of 5 genotypes namely-EEB88, EEB251, EEB203, EEB40 and EEB 35. Again, cluster I was further divided into 2 sub-clusters (A and B). Among them the highest and lowest similarity found between sub-cluster A comprised viz, EEB40 and EEB 35. Sub cluster-B comprised of 3 genotypes viz. EEB88, EEB251, and EEB203. Cluster II consisted of 12 genotypes viz., EEB301, EEB79, EEB129, EEB134, EEB107, EEB417, EEB60, EEB82, EEB292, EEB346, EEB345, and EEB47. Again, cluster II was further divided into 2 sub-clusters (A and B). Sub cluster-A, included 8 genotypes viz. EEB107, EEB417, EEB60, EEB82, EEB292, EEB346, EEB345, and EEB47. Sub-cluster-B consisted of 4 genotypes namely- EEB301, EEB79, EEB129, and EEB134. Among them the highest and lowest similarity found. Cluster III consisted of 22 genotypes viz., EEB135, EEB131, EEB23, EEB122, EEB336, EEB450, EEB91, EEB142, EEB344, EEB337, EEB380, EEB382, EEB431, EEB377, EEB53, EEB355, EEB41, EEB112, EEB11, EEB297, EEB335, and EEB343. Again, cluster III was further divided into 3 sub-clusters (A and B). Sub cluster-A, included 7 genotypes viz. EEB355, EEB41, EEB112, EEB11, EEB297, EEB335, and EEB343. Among them the highest and lowest similarity found. Sub-cluster-B consisted of 15 genotypes namely- EEB135, EEB131, EEB23, EEB122, EEB336, EEB450, EEB91, EEB142, EEB344, EEB337, EEB380, EEB382, EEB431, EEB377, and EEB53 and the highest and lowest similarity found between them (Figure 17). Khalil *et al.* (2020) studied that cluster analysis and dendrogram showed the highest degree of genetic similarity between variety Arabiasuad and variety Arabiabiad (0.7619).

Figure 17: An UPGMA cluster dendrogram showing the genetic relationships between 39 barley genotypes based on the alleles detected by 10 microsatellite markers

Legends, V1= EEB11, V2= EEB35, V3= EEB40, V4= EEB41, V5= EEB47, V6= EEB53, V7= EEB60, V8= EEB79, V9= EEB82, V10= EEB122, V11= EEB129, V12= EEB131, V13= EEB134, V14= EEB135, V15= EEB142, V16= EEB203, V17= EEB251, V18= EEB301, V19= EEB336, V20= EEB345, V21= EEB346, V22= EEB377, V23= EEB417, V24= EEB450, V25= EEB23, V26= EEB88, V27= EEB91, V28= EEB107, V29= EEB112, V30= EEB292, V31= EEB297, V32= EEB335, V33= EEB337, V34= EEB343, V35= EEB344, V36= EEB355, V37= EEB380, V38= EEB382, V39= EEB431

4.16 Principal component analysis

Principal Component Analysis Associations among 39 barley genotypes were computed using PCA method. Here, first principal component (PC1), and the second principal component (PC2) explained 29.6% and 10.2 % of total variation, respectively and localization of genotypes in a 2D PCA plot indicates the genetic distances among the barley genotypes (Figure 18). Here, Population I and Population II were mixed with genotypes viz., In PCA scree plot, the green line on top showed the accumulated variance explained; the blue line underneath showed the variance explained by individual PC (Figure 19). In PCA scree plot, the first three eigen values explained 49.4% of the cumulative variation, which were then plotted to identify the diversity of the genotypes (Figure 19). The first three principal components had eigen values of 29.6%, 10.2% and 9.5% and an overall maximum cumulative variation of 49.4% were observed with first three components of principal coordinates (Figure 19). Yadav *et al.* (2020) also revealed that in the two dimensional plot, with the first two principal components, the close clustering of the varieties among 88 barley germplasm accessions from a common developing centre could be seen.

Figure 18: Two-dimensional principal component analysis (PCA) based on SSR polymorphisms in the 39 barley genotypes

Figure 19: The scree plot displays the Principal coordinate analysis of the top 5 PCs for 39 barley genotypes based on SSR marker data

4.17 Interrelationship of phenotypic and molecular outcome

Among 123 European barley genotypes, EEB450, EEB 401, EEB 336, EEB318, EEB 114, EEB129, EEB 91, EEB116, and EEB417 have the highest yield both in control and drought conditions. The genotypes EEB129, EEB114, EEB318 are highly drought tolerant; EEB 450, EEB336 are tolerant; EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB 251, EEB 203 are susceptible.

In experiment II, the respected tolerant genotypes obtained from previous experiment i.e. EEB 450, EEB336, EEB 91 are located in same cluster as UPGMA cluster III. On the other hand, the respected susceptible genotypes i.e. EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB 251, EEB 203 are also located in the same cluster as UPGMA cluster I.

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

One of the most significant cereal crops in the world is barley. It is a minor crop in Bangladesh, but it has the potential to grow into one of the country's most essential crops. Genetic diversity is crucial for characterizing breeding lines and variations and provides the foundation for choosing the right genotypes for creating hybrid varieties. In the current study, the genetic diversity 123 European barley genotypes were assessed during the rabi season from December to April 2021–2022, in the experimental field and laboratory of the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding at Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur, Bangladesh.

The analysis of variance revealed a wide range of variation among the genotypes for all the yield and yield contributing characters viz. days to flowering (FL), plant height (cm) (PH), canopy temperature (CT), chlorophyll content (CC), number of grains per spike (GSP), thousand-grain weight (g) (TGW), days to maturity (DM), growth habit (GH), biological weight (BGW), row type (RT), tiller number per plant (TP), yield per plant (g) (YP). For control condition, the later days to flowering was found in EEB 82 (94) genotype and the earliest days to heading was found in EEB450 (59.5) genotype. The highest plant height was found in genotype EEB 431 (109) and the lowest plant height was recorded in genotypes EEB203 (52.92). Genotype EEB382 (43.5) and the genotype EEB129 (11.17) showed the maximum and minimum number of tiller plant⁻¹ respectively. The highest canopy temperature was exhibited in the genotype EEB382 (92.87 F) and the lowest canopy temperature was revealed for the genotype EEB166 (81.15F). The maximum chlorophyll content was revealed for the genotype EEB384 (58.6) and minimum chlorophyll content was exhibited in genotype EEB423 (39.25). Genotype EEB450 (93.67) and genotype EEB136 (11.5) showed the highest and lowest number of grain spike⁻¹ respectively. The maximum and the minimum amount of thousand-grain weight was revealed for the genotype EEB107 (57.73) and EEB81 (12.37) respectively. The highest biological weight was revealed for the genotype EEB318 (73g) and the lowest biological weight was exhibited in the genotype EEB92 (12.67g). The earliest days to maturity were revealed for the genotype EEB450 (98.5) and later days to maturity was found in the genotype EEB83 (133). Genotype EEB450 (5), EEB434 (5), EEB401 (5) etc. showed 67 erect growth habit and spreading growth habit was revealed for the genotype EEB 254 (1). In row type EEB 450 (6), EEB 91 (6) and EEB 11

(2), EEB (17) are six and two row barley respectively. The maximum and minimum number of spike per plant was found for the genotype EEB382 (28.83) and EEB83 (2.25) respectively. Maximum values for yield per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB450 (35.22g) followed by EEB401 (35.11g), EEB336 (31.05g) and the minimum yield per plant were exhibited in the genotype EEB81 (1.17g), EEB346 (4.22g) in control condition.

In drought stressed condition, the later days to flowering was found in EEB83 (82.5) genotype and the earliest days to flowering was found in EEB119 (60.78) genotype. The highest plant height was found in genotype EEB18 (96.33) and the lowest plant height was recorded in genotypes EEB83 (37). Genotype EEB112 (33.67) and the genotype EEB140 (4) showed the maximum and minimum number of tiller plant⁻¹ respectively. The highest canopy temperature was exhibited in the genotype EEB169 (92.05F) and the lowest canopy temperature was revealed for the genotype EEB053 (82.63F). The maximum chlorophyll content was revealed for the genotype EEB166 (50.42) and minimum chlorophyll content was exhibited in genotype EEB443 (32.7). Genotype EEB69 (27.78) and genotype EEB163 (4.83) showed the highest and lowest number of grain spike⁻¹ respectively. The maximum and the minimum amount of thousand-grain weight was revealed for the genotype EEB337 (50.35) and EEB81 (1.87) respectively. The highest biological weight was revealed for the genotype EEB17 (69.5) and the lowest biological weight was exhibited in the genotype EEB423 (6.65). The earliest days to maturity were revealed for the genotype EEB450 (89.0) and later days to maturity was found in the genotype EEB83 (121.5). Genotype EEB450 (4) etc. showed erect growth habit and spreading growth habit was revealed for the genotype EEB444 (1) etc. The maximum and minimum number of spike plant⁻¹ was found for the genotype EEB69 (25.53) and EEB254 (1.5) respectively. Maximum values for yield per plant was revealed for the genotype EEB114 (27.78g) and the minimum yield per plant were exhibited in the genotype EEB301 (0.31g).

Treatment comparison of 123 common barley genotypes were done for both drought stressed and control condition to identify better performance of the genotypes in respective conditions. From this experiment, all yield contributing traits showed better performance in control condition than in drought stress condition. But some drought tolerant genotypes showed better performance in drought stress condition which can be used as drought tolerant genotypes for further breeding programs. Variability analysis of drought tolerant genotypes revealed that phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation were high for yield per plant. In most of the cases phenotypic coefficients of variation was higher than the genotypic

coefficients of variation indicating environmental influence on the traits. These characters can be further improved by following simple selection procedure.

From the correlation coefficient study, for drought treatment, it was observed that yield plant⁻¹ (g) demonstrated a significant positive association with row type (0.77***), and number of grains per spike (0.71***) in drought-stressed conditions. It exhibited an insignificant positive association with plant height (0.14). For control condition, Yield plant⁻¹ (g) demonstrated significant positive association with row type (0.71***), number of grains per spike (0.69***) and growth habit (0.43***). It showed significant negative correlation with tiller per spike (-0.18*). It exhibited an insignificant positive association with plant height (0.11), biological weight (0.09), and canopy temperature (-0.04).

Character association through regression analysis studies revealed that the character yield per plant showed strongly significant positive linear association with thousand grain, canopy temperature in both control and drought condition. This indicated that the simultaneous selection of these characters was important for yield improvement.

The multivariate analysis revealed that 123 barley genotypes were distributed into five clusters. Among the five cluster, cluster number III (EEB450, EEB91, EEB152) and I (EEB90, EEB 111, EEB92, etc) holding most tolerant genotypes with the highest number of relative mean for days to 50% flowering, plant height, number of tiller per hill, chlorophyll content, biological weight, growth habit, row type, number of grain per plant, 1000-grain weight and yield per plant in control condition and cluster number IV (EEB450) , cluster II (EEB17, EEB 345, EEB 417) and cluster I (EEB 47, EEB91, etc) with the highest number of relative mean for days to maturity, days to flowering, plant height, number of tiller per hill, canopy temperature, chlorophyll content, biological weight, 1000- grain weight, growth habit and yield per plant in drought condition. Those genotypes from these clusters having high mean values may be directly used for adaptation or may be used as parents in future hybridization programmes.

The principal component analysis (PCA) revealed that the highest genetic diversity was contributed by PC1 and PC2 in both control and drought condition for chlorophyll content, number of tillers per plant, number of spike per plant, thousand grain weight and growth habit, number of grain per spike, chlorophyll content, plant height respectively. Therefore, these characters should be given importance during selection.

The results of drought susceptibility index (DSI) indicated the superiority in the genotype EEB81 closely followed by the genotypes EEB 382, EEB 90, EEB 83, EEB 116, and EEB 418 as 50 drought tolerant genotypes. Therefore, DSI can be effectively used to screen drought tolerant and suitable genotypes under drought stress condition.

In marker study (experiment 2), 10 SSR markers were evaluated in 39 barley varieties for molecular characterization. All of the SSRs were polymorphic.

Total of 31 alleles were detected and the number of alleles per locus ranged from 2 to 4 with an average of 3.1 alleles per locus. The most polymorphic microsatellite markers were BMAG808, EBMAC624 and Bmag006 with 4 alleles, followed by Scssr25691, Bmac0113, GMS027, Bmag337 and BMAC0577 with 3 alleles. The highest PIC value (0.7) was recorded for BMAG808 and GMS027, Bmag337 and Bmac0113 both recorded second highest (0.65) and lowest by WMS6 (0.42). The SSR markers in this study yielded reproducible polymorphic bands in thirty-nine genotypes of *H. vulgare*, providing a powerful and reliable molecular tool for analyzing genetic diversity and relationships in barley.

In population genetic structure analysis, population I consisted 42% of genotypes (EEB131, EEB23, EEB122, EEB450, EEB344, EEB337, EEB431, EEB355, EEB41, EEB112, EEB11, EEB297, EEB335, EEB343, EEB82, EEB292, EEB346) where 6 genotypes were pure and 13 were admixed. Population II comprised of total 15 genotypes (EEB135, EEB336, EEB91, EEB142, EEB380, EEB382, EEB377, EEB53, EEB301, EEB79, EEB129, EEB134, EEB107, EEB417, EEB60, EEB345, EEB47). Out of those 8 genotypes were found pure and 7 were admixed. Population III comprised of total 5 genotypes; 5 genotypes were found pure. This results revealed that there are three possible divergent groups in tested representative barley germplasms.

According to Nei's (1972), the highest level of genetic similarity (93%) observed in EEB 35 and EEB 40, EEB88 and EEB 251 (92%), and the lowest level of genetic similarity (-41%) observed between EEB203 and EEB107. It seems that crossing between these genotypes will give good result for breeder. The higher genetic distance between genotypes indicates that genetically they are diverse compare to lower genetic distance value.

Cluster analysis using UPGMA method delineated the 39 cultivars into three clusters comprising of 5, 12 and 22 genotypes.

The graphical views of PCA showed the spatial distribution of the genotypes. The results indicated that the genotypes EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB 251, EEB 203 were placed far away from the centroid that means they were more genetically diverse. These genotypes are not sharing any genetic similarity between themselves and between the entire thirty genotypes studied, they can be a potential parent in the future breeding programs.

As a result of genotype differences in reactions to water stress, moisture stress placed on all barley genotypes indicates their capacity for drought tolerance. The most distant parental categories were clearly distinguished between genotypes using the current genetic diversity study. Due to their drought tolerance, this would facilitate hybridization as well as the identification of suitable donors in marker-assisted selection. High-yielding cultivars that are tolerant of drought could be created using an efficient breeding method Bangladesh's disaster-prone regions.

Based on the findings of the present investigation following conclusions could be made.

- EEB81, EEB382, EEB90, EEB83, EEB450, EEB417, EEB298, EEB265, EEB318, EEB114, , EEB152, EEB336, EEB166, EEB129, EEB254, EEB346 were identified as drought tolerant and EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB203, EEB251 as drought susceptible genotypes among 123 genotypes through assessment of drought susceptible index.
- EEB 450, EEB 336, EEB 129 and EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB203 and EEB251 Population structure I and III, respectively.
- Based on the molecular diversity EEB 450, EEB 336, EEB 129 and EEB 35, EEB 40, EEB 88, EEB203 and EEB251 were identified in cluster III and cluster I as similar genotypes and might be useful for future hybridization program.
- Finally, considering the morpho-physiological and molecular study both the genotype EEB 450, EEB 336, EEB 129 might be very effective in future drought tolerant breeding program.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: Map of Dinajpur Sadar Upazila showing the experimental area

Map Courtesy: Banglapedia

Appendix II: Weather data of the experimental site during the period from December, 2021 to April, 2022

Months	Relative humidity (%)	Temperature		Total rainfall (mm)
		Minimum (°C)	Maximum (°C)	
December/ 2021	44.00	16	28	0.00
January/ 2022	51.00	15	25	0.00
February/ 2022	42.00	16	30	1.00
March / 2022	26.00	18	34	0.00
April/ 2022	45.00	22	33	1.7

Source: www.worldweatheronline.com

Appendix III: The soil nutrient composition of Genetics and Plant breeding Research plot of HSTU, Dinajpur

Physical and chemical properties	Value
Sand (%)	65
Silt (%)	30
Clay (%)	5
Textural class	Sandy loam
pH	4.70
Organic matter (%)	0.89
Total nitrogen (%)	0.04
Magnesium (meq/ 100g)	0.66
Potassium (meq/ 100g)	0.26
Phosphorus (µg/g)	55.85
Sulphur (µg/g)	9.93
Boron (µg/g)	0.25
Zinc (µg/g)	1.43

µg: Micro gram ; meq: Mili equivalent

Source: Soil Resources Development Institute (SRDI), Nashipur, Dinajpur-5200.

Appendix IV: Some photographs of research work (Contd.)

Appendix IV: Some photographs of research work

